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Graph Neural Networks for Pattern Recognition and Fast Track Finding

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ABSTRACT

Future upgrades to modern high-energy particle detectors will pose considerable challenges for traditional particle track reconstruction methods. Within the past two years, architectures that operate on Graph Neural Networks (GNN) have shown high degrees of promise. Presented here is a unique approach to GNN-based track finding which uses Gaussian mixture techniques to describe track parameter estimates. Unlike traditional methodologies whereby Multi-Layered Perceptrons are employed, the proposed GNN architecture leverages the Kalman filter as a mechanism for information aggregation, in order to iteratively improve the precision of track parameters, as well as for extraction of track candidates compatible with particle motion model. The excitation and inhibition rules of individual edge connections are designed to facilitate the “simple-to-complex” approach for “hits-to-tracks” association, such that the network starts with low hit density regions of an event and gradually progresses towards more complex areas. This paper focuses on the track finding algorithm development and its application on the publicly available dataset designed for the Kaggle TrackML challenge. The preliminary results related to track reconstruction efficiency and purity metrics are presented and discussed. The ultimate aim of this work is to develop a realistic GNN-based algorithm for fast track finding that can be deployed in future high-luminosity phases of particle detector experiments.

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1 Introduction

At its core track finding is a pattern recognition problem, where reconstruction of charged particle trajectories is a highly computationally intensive task. This is particularly problematic for particle detectors during future upgrades, such as the ‘Hi-Lumi LHC’ phase [1] where significant increases in pileup and luminosity will create huge demands for computing power. As many of the existing algorithms do not scale well with a growing data stream, this provides the necessary motivation to explore novel approaches in track finding.

In the past two years, algorithms for track pattern recognition based on GNNs have emerged as a promising technique. Presented here is a unique method that utilises a GNN-based architecture and allows the network to learn patterns as it evolves and iteratively extract track candidates. Individual hits or clusters of hits are modelled as graph nodes and track segments as graph edges. Gaussian mixture techniques are used to approximate track states densities and the Kalman filter (KF) is leveraged as a mechanism for information aggregation, in order to iteratively improve the precision of track parameters, as well as for extraction of track candidates compatible with particle motion model.

Modern silicon detectors typically consist of Pixel and Strip sensors. Here, the application of the GNN-algorithm is focused specifically on the Pixel detector, with the aim that the approach will serve as a sophisticated track seeding technique for pixel clusters and form preliminary track candidates. These seeds can then be extended into the Strips using standard track following. Such an approach could be efficient for saving computational resources if the GNN does not produce large proportions of fake tracks.

This paper is organised as follows; a general description of the GNN-algorithm is presented, and then applications of the algorithm on more specific models are discussed, considering first a toy Monte Carlo (MC) model and then the TrackML dataset [2].

2 GNN Algorithm Development

2.1 Overview

By modelling a GNN node neighbourhood as a Gaussian mixture, the GNN-based track finding is considered as an iterative mixture reduction task which includes masking incompatible node connections (GNN edges) and improving track parameter estimates. By utilising various machine learning techniques, the GNN can identify outlier edges in the network, allowing tracks to be easily extracted. To efficiently exploit a priori knowledge about charged particle dynamics, simplified KFs are embedded in the network and used for two main purposes; firstly as a mechanism for information propagation via message passing and secondly for track extraction.

After the network is initialised, it evolves iteratively through three main stages. The first stage comprises of Gaussian Mixture Reduction (GMR), taking a traditional ML approach to cluster compatible edge states whilst masking outliers. This is followed by an information aggregation stage; by leveraging message passing between nodes in a given neighbourhood, the compatibility of neighbouring states is assessed via extrapolation and application of a KF update. As connections are deactivated, the final stage involves updating the network state. After each stage a track splitting algorithm is applied to identify good track candidates, and if discovered they are extracted via the KF. See Figure 1 for an illustrative flow chart of the main stages of the algorithm, where each iteration comprises of three stages. As the algorithm progresses, the uncertainty in local track orientation decreases and the network will evolve until there are no more candidates that fulfil the criteria for a good track. This is the end state where isolated nodes, track fragments and unresolved ambiguities will remain.

2.2 Network Initialisation

The graph network is constructed using the Python package NetworkX [3], where track hits are represented as nodes and predicted hit-pairs are represented as edge connections. See Section 3.2 for further details on the hit-pair predictor. Following this initial set up, an out-of-the-box Connected Component Analysis (CCA) is applied in order to split the network into smaller, more manageable subgraphs. Within each subgraph,

Figure 1: Flow chart indicating the main stages of the GNN-based algorithm; Gaussian Mixture Reduction (GMR), information aggregation and updating the network state are applied, with track extraction using Kalman filters (KF). After stage 3, a further GMR stage would be applied repeating the iterations.

each node is initialised with a Gaussian vector state representing the local track state estimate, dependent on its neighbourhood.

An illustration of a node and its neighbourhood is shown in Figure 2, where each pairwise connection forms a track state estimate, X_{ij} , initialised with track parameters. See section 3.1 for further details on state implementation. All edges are initialised as active, where each edge has an associated prior probability and edge weight. The prior probability p_{ij} of node i and neighbour node j belonging to the same track is determined, assuming a track can produce at most one hit per layer. The edge weight w_{ij} is a mixture weight for the compatibility of the Gaussian component transmitted from node i to neighbour node j , and represent the strength of the connection. w_{ij} are initialised as uniform weights dependent on the number of neighbours local to a node, and are updated based on how the network evolves. w_{ij} are not to be confused with the traditional weights associated to features within neural networks. As all edges in the graph network are bidirectional, this ensures message passing can occur in both directions with different strength weights, such that the compatibility of the state propagated can be assessed in both directions dependent on its local environment. Given node i and its neighbour nodes j , all track state estimates X_{ij} , associated covariances C_{ij} , priors p_{ij} and mixture weights w_{ij} are stored at node i , forming a weighted Gaussian mixture. For any given node i , the neighbourhood is approximated by a Gaussian mixture given in Eq. (1) where ϕ_{ij} indicates the Gaussian component of pairwise edge connections between nodes i and j .

$$g_i(X) = \sum_j w_{ij} \phi_{ij}(X, X_{ij}, C_{ij}) \quad (1)$$

Figure 2: a) Illustration showing a bidirectional edge connection between nodes A and B, where θ is the angle of inclination to node B from the x axis. b) Initial prior probabilities for node A's edge components given its neighbour nodes B_j , where each B_j are nodes on separate detector layers. The unidirectional connections show that the state information and prior probabilities are being distributed from node A. These entities will differ from nodes B_j distributing to their corresponding neighbourhoods.

2.3 Gaussian Mixture Reduction

For nodes with a high multiplicity of connections (so called “hot” nodes), the number of Gaussian components can quickly rise. To make inferences within a reasonable amount of time, an intermediate approximation step can be used to prevent the number of components of the mixture from exploding. One popular computationally efficient approach for GMR is a clustering-based iterative algorithm. In order to approximate a high order Gaussian mixture by one with lower order, the traditional k-means clustering [4] is used to group together similar edge connections at each node and hence identify outliers which are then deactivated. As the mixture is reduced, Gaussian components that remain active are merged together to form a single merged state and covariance. This merged state is a higher precision track state estimate at each node and is propagated to further stages. GMR forms the first stage of the GNN-based algorithm.

Within k-means, the general case of $k=1$ is used to model the distribution at each node as a single track with some noisy connections. In the case where a vertex sits very close to an intersection point between two tracks, we can expect two or more clusters of edges. However, here the mixture reduction process is declared impossible where all states are propagated to later stages for further processing. This part of the network will wait until competing edges are masked and the mixture becomes more unimodal.

In order to establish whether track states can be grouped into a cluster, a deviation measure is needed to serve as a threshold. The Kullback-Leibler (KL) divergence [5] is a measure of the statistical distance between two Gaussian probability distributions and is used to determine the threshold for clustered states. The optimal KL distance used to classify components into a cluster will differ from node to node depending on its neighbourhood. For example, consider a node and its neighbourhood of connections with a high variance of edge orientation. The corresponding KL threshold will be larger in comparison to a node with a small variance of edge orientation, therefore this variance is also used as a discriminating feature. A simulation of 10,000 events, each with seven tracks, is used to build a training dataset and the corresponding MC truth is extracted for pairwise connections. Using the variance of edge orientation in the xy plane for each node and the KL distance between edge components, a Support Vector Machine (SVM) [6] is built to discriminate between the two classes. Other classification algorithms were explored, however the SVM was the most appropriate method to find a decision boundary in order to best separate the classes. Predictions are converted into a look-up-table and is used within the clustering stage.

2.4 Information Aggregation

Neighbourhood information aggregation via message passing is a key feature within graph networks and is leveraged within the second stage of the GNN-based algorithm. At each node, information is propagated to neighbouring nodes for all active edge connections. Once these neighbours obtain information from their own neighbours, state extrapolation and validation is executed.

At each node, the track state is represented by a Gaussian mixture, or a reduced mixture (the merged state $(g_i(X))$). For a given node i , if the merged state was established in the previous stage, this is distributed alongside its covariance matrix to all neighbour nodes j . If a merged state is not available, then all track state estimates are distributed to all neighbours j . The parameter estimation begins with a linear projection onto the subspace of measurements. Each track state estimate is projected via a measurement matrix, which relates the track state to the measurement values. In order to validate if the connection between nodes $i \rightarrow j$ is compatible, the Mahalanobis distance $\Delta\chi_{ij}^2$ is calculated using the residual vector between the projected state HX and the measurement at the neighbour state. If $\Delta\chi_{ij}^2$ is below some threshold d , the connection is compatible and the KF update is applied. If $\Delta\chi_{ij}^2 > d$ then the connection is deemed incompatible and deactivated. The threshold d is a hyper-parameter, representing the maximum $\Delta\chi_{ij}^2$ acceptable.

The KF computes the extrapolated track state estimate \tilde{X}_{ij} using the state transition Jacobian F_i from nodes i to node j and the corresponding extrapolated covariance matrix \tilde{C}_{ij} is given by Eq. (2). The matrix \tilde{C}_{ij} includes the addition of the process noise Q modelled by the Ornstein-Uhlenbeck (OU) process [7] which encompasses all material effects. See Section 2.7 for further details. The full derivation of F and Q are shown in Appendix A The KF is implemented using the Python package Filterpy [8].

$$\tilde{X}_{ij} = F_i X_{ij} \quad \tilde{C}_{ij} = F_i \left(\sum C_{ij} + Q \right) F_i^T \quad (2)$$

Figure 3: Track state estimates X_{00} and X_{01} projected from node B_0 to A via the measurement matrix H .

2.5 Updating Network State

As the network evolves and connections are deactivated, the local track orientation for each node changes. Therefore, the corresponding edge component's w_{ij} and p_{ij} are updated. For an edge connection between nodes i and j , the updated edge weights \tilde{w}_{ij} stated in Eq. (4) are computed using the normalised Gaussian measurement likelihood given by Eq. (3). The denominator $\sum_k w_{ik}\beta_{ik}$ is the sum of all weights and likelihoods in a neighbourhood for a given node i . The updated weights \tilde{w}_{ij} are also divided by the number of detector layers on either side of its neighbourhood N_S , in order to account for the probability that a track passing through node i was detected at layer L . For a given node, if any $\tilde{w}_{ij} < 0.1$, these edge connections are automatically deactivated as the likelihood of compatibility of this incoming track state is extremely low. This forms an additional part of the mechanism for edge activation and deactivation. After this update is complete, the iterations repeat and a further GMR would be performed on updated track states.

$$\beta_{ij} = (2\pi|S_{ij}|)^{-1/2} e^{-\Delta\chi_{ij}^2/2} \quad (3)$$

$$\tilde{w}_{ij} = \frac{1}{N_S} \frac{w_{ij}\beta_{ij}p_i}{\sum_k w_{ik}\beta_{ik}} \quad (4)$$

2.6 Track Extraction

Within the GNN-based framework it is possible to iteratively discover good track candidates at each stage of the algorithm as soon as ambiguities are resolved. Therefore, after each stage a track splitting algorithm is applied. Initially an out-of-the-box CCA is used, as the network may have connections which have been deactivated and so a potential subgraph can be separated from the main network. The criteria for good candidates are defined as follows; subgraphs must have a minimum number of four nodes within the volume of interest and must contain one node per layer such that there are no intersecting tracks and no holes. The KF is then applied in order to perform a track fit on all separated networks and iteratively predict and update track parameters. In order to assess the quality of extracted track candidates, the p-value is computed from the χ^2 -based KF track fit quality and must be greater than 0.01.

If a subgraph does not meet the criteria to qualify as a good track candidate, a Community Detection algorithm [9] is applied in order to further partition the set of nodes. Community detection is a generalisation

of CCA and works by using a distance metric, typically modularity, in order to label nodes as ‘closely connected’. Modularity is a benefit function that measures the strength of a particular division of a network using the number of edges. A popular modularity maximisation approach is the Louvain method [10], which iteratively optimises local communities until global modularity can no longer be improved.

Networks with zero extracted candidates are propagated to further stages for additional processing.

2.7 Implementation of Kalman filters

The KF is used for two different functionalities within the GNN-algorithm. The first is to propagate information in the neighbourhood and the second application is for track extraction.

Within the toy MC model each pairwise connection is modelled as a straight line segment. A linear extrapolation is applied during the information propagation stage and the KF is implemented with the addition of a non-zero noise term due to multiple scattering σ_{ms} . This basic approach models an additional source of uncertainty in the track inclination describing the average multiple scattering that a track may experience traversing through a detector and is sufficient to model straight lines trajectories.

However, for the application of the TrackML dataset one must consider the influence of the B-field. This creates a systematic effect on the track and a constant drift in ϕ , as it can bend in a particular direction dependent on the charge of the particle. Statistically such a situation can be described as a correlated noise, which affects track direction and can often be modelled by the Ornstein-Uhlenbeck (OU) process [7]. The result is one which can be substituted into the KF as a more sophisticated process noise, making the KF track fit three-dimensional. The process noise Q is implemented with the addition of a non-zero stochastic noise σ_{ou} , as well as the non-zero σ_{ms} . This represents the correlated noise and models the track curvature caused by the presence of the B-field. See Appendix A for further details. Once a potential track candidate is discovered during track splitting, the entire chain of segments is considered and must be compatible with the particle motion model.

An important aspect of the application of the KF here is that reconstruction of curved tracks is possible using a low-dimensionality model. The exact B-field map is not known, however by assuming a slow change in track direction, a special dynamic model for the KF is constructed using the OU process, which implicitly takes into account the track curvature without extending the track state with additional parameters.

3 Applications and results of GNN-algorithm on specific models

3.1 Application for toy MC Model

A 2-dimensional simulation with seven tracks was created, each track with 10 hits, see Figure 4a. The graph network structure was formed using a many-to-one mapping of hits-to-nodes and predicted edge connections were formed between node pairs. For hits in close proximity to one another clusters were formed by determining a suitable threshold and hit merging was executed where necessary, grouping them into 1 node. In order to build edge connections in the graph network and reduce all possible combinatorics an edge-predictor method was devised. The predictor uses a simple calculation whereby the track inclination of neighbouring nodes is calculated. If the inclination of a neighbour node spanning up to two layers apart is contained in a particular range, then this edge is compatible and a connection is established between the nodes. The network is initialised with its corresponding track state estimates X_{ij} , covariance matrices C_{ij} and MC truth particle.

In order to efficiently resolve ambiguities, a method was devised to automatically determine a suitable region for initiating the pattern recognition. For a given node, the variance of edge orientation σ_e^2 of its neighbourhood was considered. Figure 4b shows a heat map, indicating ‘hot’ nodes (white) which represent nodes with a high degree (number of edges associated to the node), whereas ‘cold’ nodes (orange - red) indicate regions with fewer ambiguities to resolve. This indicates that the node degree is an indirect characteristic of how messy a local neighbourhood is and provides a method to determine where pattern recognition should begin on a graph network in order to resolve incompatible edge connections. Nodes

with $\sigma_e^2 > 0.8$ were temporarily removed and the pattern recognition was initially applied to the remaining network.

Each pairwise connection between two nodes forms a track state estimate X_{ij} and is given by Eq. (5). X_{ij} comprises of the measurement at node i , m_i and the track inclination to the neighbouring node j , given by $t_{ij} = (m_i - m_j)/(x_i - x_j)$, modelling the segment as a straight line. The edge covariance matrix, S , for connections $i \rightarrow j$ are stated in Eq. (5), where σ_0^2 is the error due to measurement in the xy plane initialised to $100\mu m$. Additionally, negligible error is assumed in the x measurement due to the high precision of Pixel sensors. Matrix G relates the measurements to the state vector X_{ij} using a linear extrapolation where $dx = x_i - x_j$. The state covariance C_{ij} is derived using the standard linear algebra approach, where $C_{ij} = GSG^T$.

$$X_{ij} = \begin{bmatrix} m_i \\ t_{ij} \end{bmatrix} \quad S = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_0^2 & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma_0^2 \end{bmatrix} \quad G = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 1/dx & -1/dx \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

Figure 4: a) Simple 2-dimensional simulation of seven truth tracks where each track contains ten hits; one hit per layer. Each colour represents a different track. b) Conversion of the simulated hits in a) plotted as a Graph Network. The network contains a many-to-one mapping of hits to nodes, merging close proximity nodes where necessary and predicted edge connections are formed using a pair predictor. The heat map represents node degree, where “hot” nodes (white) contain many edge connections, whereas “cold” nodes (orange - red) contain fewer edge connections.

Figure 5 shows an example of the GNN-based algorithm described in Section 2 applied to this simulated network. Figure 5a displays the simulated network where nodes with $\sigma_e^2 > 0.8$ have been removed and a CCA has been applied, reducing the computational complexity in further stages as three smaller subgraphs have been identified. The extracted track candidates are shown in Figure 5b. Outlier edge connections have been successfully removed, as this particular simulation shows successful extraction of all seven truth tracks within two stages.

Figure 6 shows another simulation of a simple track model with application of the GNN algorithm. Similarly, nodes with $\sigma_e^2 > 0.8$ have been removed and a CCA has been applied. Figure 6b indicates the

results of the network state after the GMR stage, where outlier edge connections have been identified and are represented in grey. A precision of 65% was achieved on identifying correct outlier connections with respect to MC truth. A fast convergence was achieved in extracting 6/7 candidates after the first stage and the remaining subgraphs are propagated to further stages.

Figure 5: Results of the GNN-based algorithm for track finding a) Simulated graph network where nodes $\sigma_e^2 > 0.8$ are removed and CCA is applied. Each colour represents a separate network. b) The extracted track candidates after GMR and Information Aggregation.

Figure 6: Results of the GNN-based algorithm described in Section 2 for track finding a) Simulated graph network where nodes with $\sigma_e^2 > 0.8$ are removed and CCA is applied. b) The resulting network state after Gaussian Mixture Reduction via clusterisation is applied. Outlier edge connections are masked and represented in grey. c) The extracted track candidates after stage 1.

3.2 Application for TrackML dataset

The TrackML dataset [2] consists of simulated measurements arranged using a model layout that is common to most Large Hadron Collider (LHC) experiments. The detectors span a cylindrical geometry where particle beams collide on the z axis around $z = 0$. This is the center of collision and also the center of the detector. The Pixel detector is closest to the beamline and is represented by volumes 7, 8 and 9 highlighted in blue, see Figure 7. For simplicity the model uses endcap volume 7 as the geometry consists of parallel silicon layers, hence the dataset used in this study is limited to volume 7. An example of an event viewed in endcap volume 7 can be seen in Figure 7b. Since the TrackML model can produce up to four hits per layer for any given track, clusters of hits are merged into nodes, ensuring exactly one node per layer [11].

Figure 7: TrackML detector layout and event simulation

Figure 8: Extracted track candidates and purity distributions for application of the GNN-based track finding on endcap volume 7 of the TrackML detector

The graph network is initialised with ~ 9000 nodes and $\sim 13,000$ edges, as well as with track state estimates using the same model as described in Section 3.1. However ongoing work is in development to use a more

precise approach using a parabolic model. A non-zero σ_{ou} parameter is used here to model the constant drift in ϕ due to the presence of the B-field, see Appendix A for process noise matrix Q . Edge connections are determined using a trained classifier and the predictions are converted into a look-up-table [11]. An initial CCA is applied to the graph network splitting the network into smaller subgraphs. After stage 1, the track splitting yielded 62% of track candidates successfully extracted uniformly at all ϕ , shown in Figure 8a.

The track reconstruction efficiency is the ratio of successfully reconstructed reference tracks to the total number of reference tracks in a given volume of interest. The efficiency obtained was 92% for fully contained tracks within endcap volume 7 with $p_T > 1\text{GeV}$. Particles with four or more hits contained within the endcap are considered and only proposed tracks with four or more hits are considered. Each track is matched with the ground truth majority particle sharing with it the greatest hit number. The ratio of this to the number of hits for the reconstructed track defines the track purity, whilst the ratio of this to the number of hits of the underlying particle defines the particle purity. Additionally, both the track purity and particle purity must be $> 50\%$. This criteria coincides with the definition of an accepted track candidate stated in the TrackML competition [2]. The resulting average track purity and particle purity for all extracted candidates is 99%. The purity distributions reflect that the application of the OU process works well for the given p_T range.

4 Conclusions

The approach developed here is a unique method using a GNN-based framework for track finding, unlike the traditional approach whereby Multi-Layered Perceptrons are trained to directly classify nodes and edges. By utilising various machine learning techniques, the graph network is allowed to learn local track parameters on its own by iteratively resolving ambiguities and discover track candidates. The main stages of the algorithm comprise of a Gaussian Mixture Reduction stage and neighbourhood information aggregation stage. The use of Kalman filters for both information aggregation and track extraction embedded into the network is a novel approach and has shown to successfully extract track candidates compatible with the particle motion model. The algorithm yields promising results on both a simple MC toy model and TrackML model for the endcap region. A preliminary result of $> 90\%$ track reconstruction efficiency is achieved for fully contained tracks within the endcap volume and with $p_T > 1\text{GeV}$. It is promising to see that this methodology provides a high performance on a small dataset, however the algorithm is still within the early stages of its development. An evaluation on the pixel barrel of the TrackML dataset is a work in progress, as well as within denser hit environments in order to sufficiently assess the quality of the algorithm.

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Appendix A Jacobian and Process Noise for track extraction KF

The three-dimensional KF implementation for track extraction. The state transition Jacobian F is derived using the OU model [7] and is given by the equations below, where $dx = x_i - x_j$. The parameter α of the OU model determines the stability of the rate of change of the track azimuthal angle and is initialised to 0.1. If $\alpha \rightarrow \infty$ the track model essentially becomes a straight line, however if $\alpha \rightarrow 0$, the model becomes a parabola. The state transition F is given by Eqn. 6,

$$F = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & dx & g_1 \\ 0 & 1 & f_1 \\ 0 & 0 & e_1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

where e_1 , f_1 and g_1 are given by the following equations.

$$e_1 = e^{-\alpha|dx|} \quad (7)$$

$$f_1 = \frac{1 - e_1}{\alpha} \quad (8)$$

$$g_1 = \frac{|dx| - f_1}{\alpha} \quad (9)$$

The process noise matrix Q is derived using the OU process [7] and is given by Eqn. 10, where σ_{ou} is initialised to 10^{-5} and σ_0 to 0.1,

$$Q = \begin{bmatrix} (dx)^2(\sigma_{ms}^2 + \frac{(dx)^2\sigma_{ou}^2}{4}) & Q_{01} & Q_{02} \\ Q_{01} & \sigma_{ms}^2 + (dx)^2\sigma_{ou}^2 & Q_{12} \\ Q_{02} & Q_{12} & \sigma_{ou}^2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

where Q_{01} , Q_{02} and Q_{12} are given by the following equations.

$$Q_{01} = dx(\sigma_{ms}^2 + Q_{02}) \quad (11)$$

$$Q_{02} = \frac{1}{2}(dx)^2\sigma_{ou}^2 \quad (12)$$

$$Q_{12} = dx\sigma_{ou}^2 \quad (13)$$

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Standalone track reconstruction and matching algorithms for GPU-based High level trigger at LHCb

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ABSTRACT

The LHCb Upgrade in Run 3 has changed its trigger scheme to implement a full software selection in two steps. In the first step, HLT1, the entire implementation will be on GPUs, running a fast selection aimed at reducing the visible collision rate from 30 MHz to 1 MHz. This selection relies on partial event reconstruction. A version of this reconstruction starts with two monolithic tracking algorithms: VELO-pixel tracking and HybridSeeding on Scintillating-Fiber tracker, which reconstruct track segments in standalone sub-detectors. These segments are then joined through a matching algorithm to produce 'long' tracks, forming the basis of the HLT1 reconstruction. We discuss the principle of these algorithms, as well as the details of their implementation, which allows them to run in a high-throughput configuration. Emphasis is put on the optimization of the algorithms themselves to take advantage of the GPU architecture. Finally, we present results in the context of the LHCb performance requirements for Run 3.

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1 Introduction

The LHCb detector is a single-arm forward spectrometer, covering the pseudo-rapidity range from two to five, designed for the study of particles containing b or c quarks. LHCb detector has went through major transformation wherein more than 90% of the active detector channels have been replaced, as a result the LHCb detector was mostly dismantled and a new detector has been installed [2]. In comparison to Run-2, this new detector is capable of sustaining up to a five times higher instantaneous luminosity, $2 \times 10^{33} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$, and six times the number of primary interactions. To meet the upgrade requirements, an efficient trigger system is the key for Run-3 data taking. To handle such high luminosity and still record the data without any loss of interesting physics, the trigger system should have (a) the capability to reduce 5 TB per seconds to a manageable 10 Giga-bytes per second data rates. (b) should make a decision in the limited time budget (c) should handle granular type small size workloads of O(150) kB (d) should have built in parallelism to effectively use underlying hardware to handle high throughput and (e) should be a cost effective solution that can be integrated within the LHCb online system. LHCb has managed to meet these requirements with a revolutionary two stage full software-only High Level Trigger (HLT) system wherein partial detector reconstruction and selection is carried out in the first stage of HLT (HLT1) built using Graphical Processing Units (GPUs) [2]. The output of HLT1 stage is written to the buffer storage and alignment and calibration procedure are carried out before the full detector reconstruction and selection in the second stage of the HLT (HLT2) system using x86 based CPUs. The upgraded LHCb dataflow focusing on the real-time aspects is shown in Figure 1 and different parts have been detailed in [7],[9],[10], [11].

Figure 1: LHCb upgrade data-flow focusing on the real-time aspects.

2 LHCb detector and tracking system for Run-3

The three main tracking detectors in LHCb are the Vertex locator detector (VELO) which is a 52 plane silicon pixel detector, the Upstream tracker (UT) that is a silicon strip detector with 4 planes and the Scintillating Fiber (SciFi) detector placed after the dipole magnet. A Schematic of LHCb detector and different track types is shown in Figure 2. At the beginning of the Run-3 the VELO and SciFi are being commissioned while the UT is being prepared for installation at the end of 2022. Thus, the tracking system has to be adapted to run without UT.

Two new algorithms under commissioning at GPU based HLT1 stage of the data-flow chain are presented here. The first is a standalone track reconstruction algorithm for SciFi which produces SciFi track seeds and the second is a matching algorithm that matches these SciFi seeds with VELO tracks to create long tracks. This provides an alternate to the baseline HLT1 configuration [8] where long tracks are created by extending the VELO tracks to the SciFi stations and matched with SciFi hits. Figure 2.b shows different track types of LHCb.

The SciFi detector is built using polystyrene scintillating fibres. A total of about 10,000 km of fibre in SciFi is organized in 1024 fibre mats with each mat containing 6 layers of fibres with 512 fibres across. These

Figure 2: Schematic of (a) The upgraded LHCb detector (b) Sketch of LHCb Track types.

mats are then combined together in fibre modules with each module containing 8 mats. These modules are placed in the 3 stations (T1, T2 and T3) with each station having 4 layer (X, U, V, X) where the U and V are the stereo layers tilted by $\pm 5^\circ$ as shown in Figure 3.b. The first two stations (T1 and T2) contain 5 modules for each half and third station T3 contains 6 modules per half. Figure 3.a illustrates the SciFi detector and Figure 3.b shows the position of SciFi layers in each station with a track traversing a station in x, y, z coordinates.

Figure 3: Schematic of (a) The SciFi detector layout, and (b) Position of SciFi layers in each station with a track traversing a station in x, y, z coordinates.

Measuring a precise location of hits in 3-dimensional space is crucial for tracking algorithms. In the SciFi detector the x and z information is obtained by identification of the unique SiPM channel where the ends of the fibres are connected and their respective position in the detector. By Combining the hit information from the UV layers with respect to x and z , we can calculate the y information.

3 A standalone SciFi seeding algorithm at HLT1

The SciFi Seeding algorithm for HLT1 on GPUs is an adaptation of the HybridSeeding algorithm implementation at HLT2 level based on CPUs [3]. The algorithm has been optimized for the performance, efficiency and throughput needs of HLT1 taking advantage of the heterogeneous computing architectures support under the Allen project [8]. It supports multiple architectures of GPU and CPU what can be chosen at the compilation time and is organized in two cases optimized for varying initial layer. Each case consists of

two main stages of the algorithm, the first being *Seeding_XZ* which performs a pattern recognition in the xz -plane, that is the bending plane for tracks, followed by the second stage called *Seeding_confirmTracks* wherein the xz candidates are confirmed after adding the y information. These stages are explained below.

Seeding_XZ: In the first case, the first X layers of the three SciFi stations are used while in the second case, the second X layers are used. For every hit in the first X -layer of the T1, a small search window is opened in the first X -layer of T3 and all the hits in that window are matched to create two-hit combinations. The position and width of this search window are determined based on the assumption that the particle's origin vertex is $(0,0,0)$ and that the minimum track momentum is $p_{min} > 3$ GeV/c. At this stage the tracks are assumed to be straight lines in the bending plane and the size of the search window in the T3 is adjusted using parameters which are tuned using simulation samples and depend on the position of layer of a respective station and the momentum range.

For every two-hit candidate, a charge-momentum estimation and slope calculations are performed using the extrapolation of the doublets to $z = 0$. This allows to define a tight search window for hits in the first X -layer in T2. Taking bending into account, all the hits from the T2 first X -layer within the tolerance window are added to create three-hit combinations as depicted in the Figure 4.b. The three-hit combinations are fitted with a parabola with cubic correction estimation on simulated samples to predict positions in the remaining layers. This is then extended to remaining layers. The candidates with at-least two additional hits from remaining layers, i.e at least 5 out of 6 possible hits, are selected and a track fit is performed in the xz plane. Candidates with a high track quality are kept. This same procedure is performed in the second case where the second X layers of all stations are used as the initial set of layers. This helps in minimising the tracking performance losses due to hit detection inefficiencies from any specific layer. Each track candidate is assigned a score based on the number of hits and χ^2 value. A GPU optimized shared memory $O(N)$ voting algorithm is used for clone removal. The *Seeding_XZ* candidates still contains about 50% ghost or fake tracks as these candidates are merely the superposition of the real track candidates in the xz plane since there is no y information yet.

Figure 4: Schematic of (a) SciFi Seeding and Matching algorithm in HLT1 chain, (b) *Seeding_XZ* two-hit and three-hit combinations

Seeding_confirmTracks: For each XZ candidate, a large tolerance window for initial set of UV layer is opened. This is shown in Figure 5.a. In a tolerance window, many different fibres cross a given hypothesis and each fibre crosses that hypothesis at a different position of $x(z)$, giving y information. For all the hits collected in that window, the corresponding y and tolerance in $y(z)$ is determined. The tolerance window is updated at each hit found for subsequent layers. Tracks with a combined total of 10 hits or higher from X and UV layers are accepted and a linear model in y is used to calculate track parameters. The candidates with best χ^2 are confirmed as SciFi seeds. All these operations are carried out in parallel for all the XZ candidates.

4 VELO-SciFi track matching algorithm

VELO tracks are matched to the SciFi track seeds reconstructed by the standalone seeding algorithm to create *long-tracks*. Before beginning with the matching step, some of the VELO tracks are filtered out if they do not meet some basic criteria. The tracks generated due to back-propagation of the particles are removed and only the tracks that fall within the geometrical acceptance of the SciFi are considered for matching. This algorithm is adapted from a CPU based HLT2 matching algorithm called PrMatchNN [4]. A track state in LHCb at position z_i is defined as a vector of form $\vec{S}_i = (x, y, t_x, t_y, q/p)^T$ where x, y are coordinates, t_x and t_y are the slopes in x_z and y_z plane respectively and q/p is inverse track momentum times its charge q at $z = z_i$. A fast q/p estimation of tracks called the " p_T kink" approximation method is used to predict the tolerances at matching plane in z for a given momentum requirement, which is different for x_z and y_z planes as depicted in Figure 5.b. The actual momentum kink depends on the integrated magnetic field along the path followed by the track and is calculated using MC simulations taking the magnetic field map of LHCb detector into account. Candidates with small differences in their slope with $\Delta t_x \lesssim 1.5$ and $\Delta t_y \lesssim 0.02$ are matched. In addition, for matching planes in the x_z and y_z the differences in the extrapolated positions are required to be $\Delta x \lesssim 20$ mm and for $\Delta y \lesssim 150$ mm respectively.

Best candidates are selected using χ^2 minimization in Δx , Δy and Δt_y . Further, a clone killing procedure is applied wherein the tracks which share a VELO track are compared and only the ones with best χ^2 are kept. This produces *long-tracks* as the output.

Figure 5: (a) Tolerance windows in UV search. (b) Kink approximation in the X_z plane used in the matching algorithm.

5 GPU implementation features

To achieve the HLT1 level throughput and performance, it was necessary to design these algorithms as per the underlying GPU hardware architectures and efficiently utilize the built functionality of parallel programming from framework. The Allen framework provides built-in event level parallelization as every event in LHCb is an independent physics event. In the following, some of the key algorithm level design considerations are described.

- **GPU Memory access:** The choice of GPU memory type for a given operation can make significant difference in performance. In the SciFi seeding algorithm, SciFi hits are read multiple times in a random (non-coalesced) order and therefore the shared memory storage is preferred as compared to global memory. Each hit can be stored in a single float of 4 bytes and in the SciFi seeding algorithm we only load hits from 6 (X or UV) layers at a time. Thus if we take 300 hits as nominal for each layer then we have a total of 1800 hits in total which in turn require $7.2kB$ of shared memory. The binary search implementation for making pair candidates from hits is about 1.5 times faster using shared memory over global memory.

- **Parallelisation:** In the *Seeding_XZ* part, all the operations of creating two-hit, three-hit and multi-hit combinations are parallelised over the hits of the starting layer. In the *Seeding_confirmTracks* part, all of the operations of adding UV hits are done in parallel for each starting XZ seed from previous step. The VELO-SciFi matching algorithm is parallelised over the VELO tracks while matching with the SciFi track seeds.
- **Thread block size optimization:** From GPU hardware architecture perspective, A set of 32 threads that execute the same instructions are grouped into warps. A thread block is made up of several warps (maximum 64 for RTX A5000). A group of thread blocks is assigned to a Streaming Multi-processor(SM). An SM is a general purpose processor with limited amount of shared memory, caches, registers and execution cores. Optimal thread block size configuration is important to maximise the occupancy of the GPU and depends on the type of the GPU and its architecture. The *Seeding_XZ* and *Seeding_confirmTracks* parts require about 8 KB of shared memory per block to store the hits. This can be best met with 4 warps per block which gives a total of 128 threads. For Velo-SciFi Track Matching the block size is kept at 32.

6 Performance of algorithms.

The performance of SciFi Seeding and VELO-SciFi Matching algorithms presented above fully meets the HLT1 requirements. The sequence of HLT1 formed by these two algorithms produces *long-tracks* which is an alternative track reconstruction approach to the baseline approach called *Forward-tracking*. One should note that these performance figures are without the UT detector and are fully compatible with the baseline requirements without any cuts on transverse momentum. Few important performance parameters are presented below. Some additional performance plots are available in [5].

- **Efficiency:** Figure 6 shows the track reconstruction efficiency for *long-tracks* from B decays is 83% while for tracks with $p > 5$ GeV, the efficiency is 92%. For electrons, overall efficiency is 70% and for $p > 5$ GeV, efficiency is 75%.

Figure 6: Tracking efficiencies for HLT1 from B decays as function of momentum p using 5000 simulated events for $B_s \rightarrow \phi\phi$ and $B^0 \rightarrow K^{*0}e^+e^-$

- **Ghost rates:** The Ghost rates for all reconstructed tracks stands at about 9% while for the momentum range of $p > 5$ GeV and $p_T > 0.5$ GeV, it comes down to 5%, as shown in Figure 7.
- **Throughput:** The baseline requirement for HLT1 throughput for Run-3 is 30 MHz. That means that the HLT1 needs to be able to process the input rate of about 30 million events per second and

Figure 7: Ghost rates for HLT1 *long-tracks* from B decays as a function of momentum p and transverse momentum p_T . The plots show reconstructed tracks from 5000 simulated $B_s^0 \rightarrow \phi\phi$ events using VELO-SciFi track matching

produce output rate of about 1 million events per second. Figure 8.a shows the throughput of *VELO-SciFi Matching* sequence for different GPUs and CPUs without UT in comparison with the baseline (*Forward-tracking*) sequence with UT. In addition, Figure 8.b shows the breakdown of *VELO-SciFi Matching* sequence algorithms on RTX A5000 GPU.

Figure 8: (a) Throughput of *VELO-SciFi Matching* sequence (red) and default sequence (forward with UT) (blue) sequence on single GPU cards (NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3090, RTX A6000, RTX A5000, GeForce RTX 2080 Ti and NVIDIA V100). In addition the throughput of Allen compiled for CPU is shown for a CPU server (AMD EPYC 7502). The CPU throughput was measured on a single NUMA domain and multiplied by two. (b) Breakdown of the *VELO-SciFi Matching* sequence.

7 Conclusions and prospects

In the context of LHCb's Real Time Analysis data-flow for Run-3, two new algorithms for the GPU-based first stage of the High Level Trigger at LHCb have been presented along with their key design aspects on GPU architecture. A standalone seeding algorithm for the SciFi detector and a matching algorithm for SciFi

Seeds and VELO tracks. The performance of these algorithm meets the baseline requirements for Run-3 and integrates well with the HLT1 sequence. In addition, the availability of SciFi seeds at HLT1 level provides opportunities for adding downstream tracking to HLT1 by adding UT hits after the commissioning of the UT detector.

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Improved Track Reconstruction Performance for Long-lived Particles in ATLAS

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ABSTRACT

Searches for long-lived particles (LLPs) are among the most promising avenues for discovering physics beyond the Standard Model at the LHC. However, displaced signatures are notoriously difficult to identify due to their ability to evade standard object reconstruction strategies. In particular, the default ATLAS track reconstruction applies strict pointing requirements which limit sensitivity to charged particles originating far from the primary interaction point. To recover efficiency for LLPs decaying within the tracking detector volume, ATLAS employs a dedicated large-radius tracking (LRT) pass with loosened pointing requirements, taking as input the hits left over from the primary track reconstruction. During Run 2 of the LHC, the LRT implementation was highly efficient but suffered from a large number of incorrectly reconstructed track candidates which prohibited it from being run in the standard reconstruction chain. Instead, a small subset of the data was preselected for LRT reconstruction using information from the standard object reconstruction. In preparation for LHC Run 3, ATLAS has completed a major effort to improve both standard and large-radius track reconstruction performance which allows for LRT to run in all events, expanding the potential phase-space of LLP searches and streamlining their analysis workflow. These proceedings summarize these achievements and report on the readiness of the ATLAS detector for track-based LLP searches in Run 3.

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1 Introduction

In order to reconstruct the trajectories of charged particles (tracks), ATLAS [1] uses the Inner Detector (ID) tracking system to provide efficient, robust and precise position measurements of charged particles as they traverse the detector. The ID is immersed in a 2 T axial magnetic field and is comprised of three subdetectors. The high-granularity silicon pixel detector consists of concentric barrel layers with $r = 33, 50.5, 88.5, \text{ and } 122.5 \text{ mm}^1$ in the central region, and three disks in each of the endcaps at $|z| = 495, 580, \text{ and } 650 \text{ mm}$. The pixel detector is followed by the silicon microstrip tracker (SCT), consisting of barrel layers at $r = 299, 371, 443, \text{ and } 514 \text{ mm}$ and nine wheels in each of the endcaps with $854 < |z| < 2720 \text{ mm}$. These silicon detectors are complemented by the transition radiation tracker (TRT) composed of straw tubes which run parallel to the beamline in the barrel, enabling radially extended track reconstruction up to $|\eta| = 2.0$.

Tracks are reconstructed from the energy deposits (hits) recorded in individual detector elements of the ID. The standard ATLAS track reconstruction algorithm is optimized for reconstructing tracks that originate in the vicinity of the primary interaction point (IP), and is not efficient for reconstructing tracks that are displaced by more than 5 mm from the IP due to tight selections placed on the transverse and longitudinal impact parameters. Thus, to reconstruct displaced tracks originating from the decays of long-lived particles (LLPs), a secondary *large-radius tracking* (LRT) algorithm [2] is used which improves the ATLAS track reconstruction efficiency for a larger particle lifetime range.

In preparation for the LHC Run 3 data-taking, the LRT algorithm has undergone a substantial reoptimization. An overview of the LRT algorithm and the improvements with respect to the Run 2 implementation is given in Section 2. The performance of the updated LRT configuration is then evaluated on simulated samples of benchmark long-lived particle scenarios in Section 3, and comparisons are performed between data and simulated inelastic proton-proton collisions in Section 4.

2 Large-radius tracking

The LRT reconstruction is performed after the standard ATLAS track reconstruction, taking as input the hits that are unassociated to standard tracks. It follows the same reconstruction strategy as the standard tracking but with modified selections that are tuned to achieve improved performance for reconstructing displaced particles, most notably on the maximally allowed values of the transverse and longitudinal impact parameters (d_0 and z_0). By relaxing the selections on $|d_0|$ and $|z_0|$ to 300 mm and 500 mm, respectively, the LRT algorithm is able to reconstruct charged particles with efficiencies greater than 75% for production radii (r_{prod}) of 300 mm or less.

For the LHC Run 2 data-taking period (2015-2018) the LRT algorithm was predominantly optimized for high signal efficiency, resulting in approximately twice the computational time per event compared to the prompt pass due to a very high rate of poor-quality tracks, including “fake” tracks reconstructed from random hit combinations and tracks from soft material interactions [2]. This increased processing time was affordable because the LRT reconstruction was only applied to an $\mathcal{O}(10\%)$ fraction of the events recorded by the ATLAS detector that were selected based on event-level quantities computed during the standard reconstruction. For the LHC Run 3 (2022-2024) data-taking, the average number of simultaneous pp collisions per bunch crossing ($\langle\mu\rangle$) is expected to increase to 50 from Run 2 values that ranged between 20 and 40. In preparation for these challenging Run 3 conditions, the LRT pass has been updated, significantly reducing the computation time for track reconstruction for LLP signatures while reducing the rate of fake tracks by roughly 95%. As a consequence of these improvements, a full integration of the LRT reconstruction for LLP signatures into the standard ATLAS event reconstruction chain was achieved (see [3] for details on the Run 3 tracking software performance).

¹ATLAS uses a right-handed coordinate system with its origin at the nominal interaction point (IP) in the centre of the detector and the z -axis along the beam pipe. The x -axis points from the IP to the centre of the LHC ring, and the y -axis points upward. Cylindrical coordinates (r, ϕ) are used in the transverse plane, ϕ being the azimuthal angle around the beam pipe. The pseudorapidity is defined in terms of the polar angle θ as $\eta = -\ln[\tan(\theta/2)]$.

3 Performance studies on simulation

Two benchmark signal models are used to assess the displaced track reconstruction efficiency targeting leptonic and hadronic secondary vertex signatures. The first is a displaced heavy-neutral-lepton (HNL) signal, which results in a characteristic dilepton displaced vertex. The HNL signal mass is 15 GeV and the proper lifetime $c\tau$ is 100 mm. The second is a simplified model in which a new electrically neutral pseudoscalar boson a is produced in pairs through decays of the Higgs boson, with the a boson subsequently decaying into pairs of b -quarks. This LLP decay results in a hadronic displaced vertex signature which tends to have higher track multiplicity than the HNL signature. The a boson mass is 55 GeV and the proper lifetime $c\tau$ is 100 mm. Detailed signal descriptions of the two models can be found in Refs [4] and [5].

To assess the reconstruction efficiency in simulation, a hit-based matching scheme is used to associate reconstructed tracks to truth-level particles. The track reconstruction efficiency is then defined as the ratio of the number of signal truth particles matched to reconstructed tracks divided by the number of signal truth particles. Truth particles are subject to the fiducial selections shown in Table 1. The resulting efficiency is referred to as the “technical” efficiency, and quantifies the reconstruction performance for truth particles that are expected to satisfy the necessary requirements to be reconstructed by the tracking algorithm. The track reconstruction efficiencies for the two benchmark models are shown in Figure 1 as a function of $|d_0|$ for standard tracking, LRT, and the combined collection of standard and large-radius tracks. After $|d_0| > 5$ mm, the standard track reconstruction efficiency becomes negligible with LRT recovering the loss in efficiency with significant efficiencies out to $|d_0| = 300$ mm. The observed efficiencies are on the order of 10% smaller than those obtained with the Run 2 LRT configuration. This is due to an overall tightening of the track selections imposed to reduce the number of fake tracks reconstructed and improve the computational performance.

Table 1: Fiducial selections applied to truth particles entering into the technical efficiency calculation.

$p_T > 1$ GeV
$ \eta < 2.5$
$r_{\text{prod}} < 440$ mm
charge = ± 1
$N_{\text{hits}}^{\text{Si}} > 8$
From LLP decay

3.1 Impact on searches for displaced vertices

Many analyses which used LRT in Run 2 attempted to reconstruct the decays of long-lived particles by performing an additional secondary vertex reconstruction using both standard and LRT tracks. Thus, to evaluate the impact of the improved Run 3 LRT configuration at the analysis level it is most useful to study how the updated track reconstruction changes the LLP vertex reconstruction efficiency and the overall rate of vertices reconstructed from fake tracks, which correspond to the dominant backgrounds in such searches.

The study is performed using the benchmark model of a displaced hadronic decay described in Section 3. To compare the performance between Run 2 and Run 3, the simulated events are reconstructed using the Run 2 and Run 3 ATLAS track reconstruction configurations. Secondary vertices are reconstructed using a dedicated inclusive vertexing algorithm optimized for identifying the decays of heavy long-lived particles [7]. Identical vertex reconstruction configurations are used for the two samples.

To assess the signal vertex reconstruction efficiency and evaluate the impact of fake tracks, a truth-matching procedure is performed. Reconstructed vertices are considered matched to an LLP decay if the p_T -weighted fraction of tracks in the vertex that are matched to truth-level LLP descendants is greater than 0.5. Figure 2 shows the radial distributions of truth-matched and non-truth-matched vertices for the Run 2 and Run 3 samples. The Run 3 reconstruction has a modest increase in the number of LLP vertices and considerably fewer non-LLP vertices due to the significant increase in purity of the LRT algorithm.

Figure 1: The technical track reconstruction efficiency for displaced charged particles produced by the decay of (a) long-lived scalar particles decaying hadronically, and (b) long-lived heavy neutral leptons decaying leptonically. The efficiency is shown as a function of the absolute value of the transverse impact parameter, $|d_0|$. The efficiencies are computed using standard tracks only (blue), large-radius tracks only (pink), as well as the combined collection of standard and large-radius tracks (black) [6].

Figure 2: A comparison of the radial distributions of reconstructed secondary vertices in a simulated long-lived particle sample using the Run 2 and Run 3 track reconstruction configurations. The circular markers represent reconstructed vertices that are matched to truth-level LLP decay vertices (LLP). The dashed lines represent reconstructed vertices that are not matched to truth-level LLP decay vertices (non-LLP). The four pixel layers and first SCT layer are shown in the figure with vertical lines [6].

4 Data and simulation comparison

To further validate the improved LRT configuration, comparisons are performed between Run 2 data and simulated inelastic proton-proton collisions. Data were selected from the 2018 data taking period using an unbiased random trigger (the ‘zero-bias’ trigger) which fires on the bunch crossing occurring one LHC revolution after a low-threshold calorimeter-based trigger. This trigger runs throughout the normal ATLAS data-taking, ensuring that the data is obtained with equivalent beam conditions present in normal physics

data-taking and thus give a representative sample to study the tracking performance. The total number of recorded events is 25×10^6 and has $\langle \mu \rangle = 34$. The simulation is generated with a flat μ profile and is thus reweighted to agree with the μ profile of the data. The transverse momentum distributions of tracks were found to be consistent between data and simulation, therefore no additional reweighting is performed. Both data and simulation were reprocessed using the Run 3 reconstruction software [3]. Track-level comparisons are performed (Section 4.1), as well as comparisons of the properties of secondary vertices consistent with the decays of K_0^S mesons (Section 4.2).

4.1 Track properties

The distributions of the number of hits in the pixel and SCT ID subsystems per LRT track are shown in Figure 3. The distributions in the simulation closely match the distributions in data. Small discrepancies are consistent with those observed in the Run 2 LRT configuration [2]. The absolute value of the transverse impact parameter (d_0) for reconstructed LRT tracks is shown in Figure 4. The peaks in the distribution at $|d_0| = 50, 88,$ and 122 mm coincide with the radial positions of the three pixel barrel layers, and correspond to low- p_T secondary tracks with trajectories tangential to the material layers. The largest deviations from unity in the ratio of data to simulation are at the 10% level, indicating very good agreement between the two samples.

Figure 3: The distribution of the number of hits in the (a) pixel and (b) SCT detector in 2018 zero bias data (black markers) and simulated inelastic proton-proton collisions (filled red histogram). The simulation is normalized to the number of tracks in data. The uncertainty shown in the ratio plot represents the combined statistical uncertainties on the simulation and the data. Points in the ratio that do not lie within the visible range are shown as arrows [8].

4.2 Study of K_0^S vertices

To compare the track reconstruction efficiency between data and MC, a “standard candle” is needed to identify LRT tracks originating from a true long-lived particle decay. The K_0^S meson is an ideal candidate based on its lifetime ($c\tau = 27$ mm) and clean signature of a two-track vertex. To identify K_0^S vertices, secondary vertices are reconstructed from the combined collection of standard and large-radius tracks using an algorithm optimized for identifying two-body $V0$ decays [9]. K_0^S candidates are identified by requiring that the invariant mass of the vertex fit is in the range $[472, 522]$ MeV. No additional vetoes or background subtractions are applied to the vertex yields. The simulation is normalized to the data based off of the total number of reconstructed K_0^S candidates.

The radial distribution (R_{xy}) of the reconstructed K_0^S candidates are then compared between data and simulation, as shown in Figure 5a. Vertices in simulation are separated in three categories based on the number of LRT tracks included in the vertex fit. Significant differences in the LRT reconstruction efficiency

Figure 4: The distribution of the absolute value of the transverse impact parameter (d_0) in data (black markers) and simulated inelastic proton-proton collisions (filled red histogram). The simulation is normalized to the number of tracks in data. The uncertainty shown in the ratio plot represents the combined statistical uncertainties on the simulation and the data [8].

between data and MC would manifest as deviations in the distributions at large vertex displacement where vertices with two LRT tracks dominate. No such deviations are observed, indicating good agreement between data and simulation in the LRT reconstruction efficiency. After the first SCT layer, LRT begins to have a diminishing contribution to the total yield because particles produced in this region will traverse insufficient silicon layers to satisfy the LRT hit requirements. Figure 5b shows the fraction of K_0^S candidate vertices reconstructed with either two standard tracks or with at least one large-radius track in data and simulation. The distributions are consistent between the two samples, further indicating good modeling of the LRT reconstruction in simulation. After $R_{xy} > 70$ mm, LRT tracks account for more than 50% of the total number of K_0^S candidate vertices, highlighting the importance of LRT for the reconstruction of displaced vertices.

Figure 5: (a) The radial distribution of reconstructed K_0^S candidate vertices in 2018 zero bias data (black markers) and simulated inelastic proton-proton collisions (stacked histogram). The total number of vertices in simulation is normalized to the number of vertices in data. The four pixel layers and first SCT layer are shown in the figure with dashed vertical lines. (b) The fraction of K_0^S candidate vertices reconstructed with two standard tracks (labeled “STD” in the legend) and at least one large-radius track (labeled “LRT” in the legend) in 2018 zero bias data (circles) and simulated inelastic proton-proton collisions (histograms) [8].

5 Conclusions

The ATLAS large-radius tracking algorithm has undergone significant improvements in preparation for LHC Run 3 data taking. As a result of this reoptimization, a $\mathcal{O}(95\%)$ reduction in fake tracks was achieved with only a $\mathcal{O}(10\%)$ reduction in signal track reconstruction efficiency. The large reduction in fakes translates to a drastically reduced CPU time for the track reconstruction, which has allowed for LRT to be integrated in the standard ATLAS reconstruction chain. This will significantly simplify the workflow for LLP analyses in Run 3 as well as allow for analyses not specifically targeting LLP signatures to benefit from increased track reconstruction efficiency at large- d_0 . A study of secondary vertex reconstruction for hadronic LLP signatures indicates that the improved LRT configuration leads to a significant reduction in vertices reconstructed from fake tracks and an overall improvement in the vertex reconstruction efficiency for LLP signatures. This will translate directly to improved signal to background ratio for displaced vertex searches in Run 3. Additionally, comparisons between data and simulation show good modeling of both low-level track quantities as well as high-level properties of reconstructed K_0^S vertices using LRT tracks. These developments are expected to increase the sensitivity of long-lived particle searches in Run 3 and allow for a considerable expansion of the ATLAS LLP search program.

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The ATLAS Inner Detector tracking trigger at 13 TeV in LHC Run-2 and new developments on standard and unconventional tracking signatures for the upcoming LHC Run-3

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ABSTRACT

The performance of the Inner Detector tracking trigger of the ATLAS experiment at the LHC is presented for the data taking period of Run 2 (2015-2018). The Inner Detector tracking is used for the muon, electron, tau and b-jet triggers, and its high performance is essential for the ATLAS physics program such as precision measurements of the Standard Model and searches for new physics.

The application of Inner Detector tracking is being significantly expanded for Run 3. For the first time, full-detector tracking will be utilized for all signatures with jets and missing transverse momentum and dedicated triggers with unconventional tracking will be utilized to identify massive long-lived particles with displaced and disappearing track signatures. Several optimizations have been developed to meet computing resource limitations.

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1 Introduction

The ATLAS Inner Detector (ID) trigger runs tracking in order to enable the reconstruction of electrons, muons, taus, and b -jets for use in trigger decisions. For the Large Hadron Collider's (LHC) [1] Run 3, an expanded use of tracking is planned for jet, missing transverse momentum, and unconventional signatures. The ID trigger is a crucial element of the ATLAS trigger system to find and save events needed for the ATLAS physics program.

The ATLAS detector [2] is a multipurpose particle detector at the LHC with a forward-backward symmetric cylindrical geometry and a near 4π coverage in solid angle. It consists of an inner tracking detector surrounded by a thin superconducting solenoid providing a 2 T axial magnetic field, electromagnetic and hadronic calorimeters, and a muon spectrometer. The inner tracking detector covers the pseudorapidity range $|\eta| < 2.5$. It consists of silicon pixel (Pixel), silicon microstrip (SCT), and transition radiation tracking (TRT) detectors. An additional layer of silicon pixels, the insertable B-layer [3, 4], was installed before Run 2. Lead/liquid-argon (LAr) sampling calorimeters provide electromagnetic (EM) energy measurements with high granularity. A steel/scintillator-tile hadron calorimeter covers the central pseudorapidity range ($|\eta| < 1.7$). The endcap and forward regions are instrumented with LAr calorimeters for both the EM and hadronic energy measurements up to $|\eta| = 4.9$. The muon spectrometer surrounds the calorimeters and is based on three large superconducting air-core toroidal magnets with eight coils each. The field integral of the toroids ranges between 2.0 and 6.0 Tm across most of the detector. The muon spectrometer includes a system of precision chambers for tracking and fast detectors for triggering.

A two-level trigger system is used to select events. The first-level trigger is implemented in hardware and uses a subset of the detector information from the calorimeters and muon spectrometer to accept events at a rate below 100 kHz out of the 40 MHz collision rate. Small Regions-of-Interest (RoIs) around the calorimeter or muon spectrometer signatures are passed to the software-based High Level Trigger (HLT) that reduces the accepted event rate to 1 kHz on average depending on the data-taking conditions. The HLT uses offline-like reconstruction, including tracking, in order to determine which events to save. Tracking can be run over the entire ID (Full Scan) or in small RoIs, which vary in size but are of order 0.2 wide in pseudorapidity and azimuthal angle. An extensive software suite [5] is used in the reconstruction and analysis of real and simulated data, in detector operations, and in the trigger and data acquisition systems of the experiment.

2 Run 2 Inner Detector Trigger

The design and performance of the Run 2 ID trigger is described in detail in Ref. [6]. The tracking strategy was redesigned for Run 2 compared to Run 1, and the processing time, shown on the left of Figure 1, benefited from software optimizations. These changes resulted in a significant reduction in processing time, which was needed to meet computing requirements given the higher Run 2 average pile-up.

The tracking algorithms in the trigger start from the RoI, which may be the entire detector for Full Scan tracking. The data preparation step includes the retrieval of the hits from the SCT and Pixel detectors, clustering of those hits, and formation of space-points. The Fast Track Finder (FTF) runs the seeding and track formation. This step is unique to the trigger and is optimized for speed and efficiency with respect to the offline pattern recognition. Optionally, events may be discarded using this information in order to avoid unnecessary downstream processing. Finally, the precision tracking step runs offline-like track fitting, seeded by the spacepoints of the FTF tracks, by running the ambiguity removal tool. The purpose of the precision tracking step is to increase the purity and resolution of the tracks. Tracks are also extended into the TRT. Example Run 2 processing times for the main tracking steps for muons are shown on the right of Figure 1. The FTF performs the time consuming pattern recognition stage used to seed both the initial fast track fit used in the FTF itself and the full track fit performed by the precision tracking stage, which does not run its own pattern recognition. The tracking for isolation is significantly longer than the rest because it runs in a larger RoI and thus processes more data.

The ID tracking performed extremely well in Run 2 with high efficiencies for a variety of signatures. As an example, the efficiency for fast and precision tracking for electrons is shown on the left of Figure 2. The tracking is nearly fully efficient, with a small dip near the transition region between the barrel and end-cap

Figure 1: (left) Ambiguity resolution processing time before and after software optimizations, a newer GCC compiler, and the switch to the EIGEN library were implemented, as described in the text. (right) Run 2 processing time per muon RoI for the fast, precision, and isolation tracking steps [6].

of the ID. On the right of Figure 2 is the η resolution of muon tracks, demonstrating the improved resolution from running precision tracking on top of FTF.

Figure 2: (left) Efficiency for fast and precision tracking of electron candidates with respect to offline electrons. The small dips in efficiency around $|\eta| = 1.3$ correspond to the transition between the barrel and endcap of the Inner Detector. (right) Muon track η resolution with respect to offline muons for fast and precision tracking [6].

3 Faster Full-Detector Tracking for Run 3

A large increase in full detector tracking is planned for Run 3, but it is computationally expensive to run. Thus it was important to optimize Full Scan tracking in order to reduce the processing time. Several optimizations were implemented.

Forming seeds is one of the first steps of the tracking algorithm. Reducing the number of seeds decreases the time spent in the seeding step as well as downstream tracking steps as time is not wasted processing unnecessary seeds. Seeds are triplets of hits composed of two doublets sharing the middle hit. A machine learning based filter (Bayes classifier using a kernel density estimate) was developed to separate between doublets, pairs of hits, that will correctly be associated to a track and those that will not [7, 8]. The

classification is based on the polar angle θ of the doublets and the width of the pixel cluster w_η in η of the middle hit in the seed. The left of Figure 3 shows the predicted region of correct association to a track. The vertical structures are a result of training the classifier for Pixel barrel and end-cap doublets and standard and long pixel combinations. The area of predicted correct association is turned into a look-up-table in order to quickly evaluate if a doublet should be accepted. An operating point with a true positive rate of 95% was chosen, corresponding to roughly a factor of two reduction in the false positive rate. This reduction in bad seeds results in an overall speed up of $1.6\text{--}2.3\times$ for an average pile-up of 40–80, with a loss in efficiency of 0.7–1.0%. The right of Figure 3 shows the small loss in efficiency, mostly at larger $|\eta|$, compared to Monte Carlo truth tracks when enabling the filtering.

Figure 3: (left) Predicted classification of correct or incorrect hit association to a track for doublets from the Pixel detector based on the polar angle θ and cluster width w_η of the middle hit in a seed. (right) Efficiency versus truth track η with and without the machine learning based seed filtering [7].

A second optimization also targets the seeding for Full Scan tracking. By disabling the use of mixed seeds, those with both Pixel and SCT clusters, and using only seeds with three Pixel or three SCT clusters, the mean event processing time for the FTF step is reduced by a factor of 1.9 [9]. Using only Pixel or SCT seeds avoids the relatively large gap between the last Pixel layer and first SCT layer. The resulting loss in tracking efficiency is small, less than 1%, as shown on the right of Figure 4.

Figure 4: (left) Efficiency for Full Scan tracking both with and without seeds combining Pixel (P) and SCT (S) clusters. (right) Efficiency and normalized processing time for Full Scan tracking versus the z half-width of the tracking ROI. The standard deviation of the beam spot in z is indicated with vertical dotted lines [9].

A third optimization looks at the width of the RoI along the beam-line (z -axis). Restricting the size of the RoI in z reduces the processing time, while the efficiency of the tracking is largely unchanged for RoIs covering at least three standard deviations of the beam spot. The right of Figure 4 shows the slow decrease in efficiency for smaller RoIs, less than 1% decrease, while the processing time decreases by up to 30% for an RoI with a half width of roughly 130 mm.

4 Unconventional Tracking Triggers for Run 3

Long-lived particles (LLPs), those which do not immediately decay after production, result in a wide variety of discoverable signatures at the LHC. Thus they are an important part of the LHC's Run 3 physics program. Many of these unique signatures rely on tracking information in order to identify them, e.g. displaced vertices, jets, and leptons. During Run 2, only standard tracking was run in the trigger, with coverage in transverse impact parameter out to $|d_0| < 5\text{--}10$ mm, which is not viable for most LLP signatures. Run 2 searches generally relied on calorimeter and muons spectrometer based signatures to trigger events. These triggers had fairly high thresholds in order to keep the triggered event rate at a reasonable level, which reduced the acceptance of the trigger to LLP signatures. For Run 3, new triggers have been implemented to directly target events with disappearing tracks and displaced leptons.

Disappearing tracks result from the decay of a long-lived charged particle, for example a supersymmetric chargino, that traverses several inner layers of the ID, before decaying into invisible and low momentum particles. The low momentum particle is not tracked, so the signature in the detector is a short tracklet with a few hits on the inner silicon layers, which can not be extended into a full track. The FTF algorithm was modified in order to save tracklets that fail to become full tracks and is run in the Full Scan tracking used for the missing transverse momentum signatures. This signature has a large background, which makes it impracticable to trigger solely based on finding a tracklet. In order to reduce the background rate, a Boosted Decision Tree (BDT) was trained based on quantities such as the track parameters, quality of fit, and number of hits in the Pixel and SCT detectors. The performance of the BDT is shown on the left of Figure 5, with good separation between signal and background tracklets. Directly reconstructing the tracklet and reducing the background with the BDT allows for a lower missing transverse momentum threshold (80 GeV) compared to the default trigger (110 GeV), shown on the right of Figure 5. This results in a large increase in acceptance for models with lower momentum, e.g. roughly a factor of two for those with a transverse momentum of the chargino-chargino system of 100 GeV.

Figure 5: (left) The Boosted Decision Tree score used for separating signal-like disappearing track candidates (Monte Carlo) from background (Data). (right) Efficiency of the high level trigger to select simulated events with a long-lived chargino for the traditional missing transverse momentum trigger and the new disappearing track trigger, which allows for a lower missing transverse momentum threshold [10].

Run 2 searches for displaced leptons, for example Ref. [11], had limited acceptance in the trigger for events

with relatively low momentum electrons and muons. Models with long-lived supersymmetric staus with a mass around 100 GeV generally result in final state electrons and muons with momenta below the roughly 60 GeV thresholds needed to trigger the event. Further, the Run 2 triggers either required two objects in the event or had limited geometric acceptance. For the first time, Large Radius Tracking (LRT) [12] will be run in the trigger for Run 3 in order to reconstruct displaced tracks and directly trigger on displaced leptons. This is enabled by improvements to the algorithm [13] that reduce the number of fake tracks and reduce the processing time. The trigger runs LRT with the same configuration as the offline tracking, but still with the specialized FTF step with a different seeding algorithm. LRT can be run over the entire detector in a second pass after standard tracking on the remaining hits, as is done for offline LRT, or it can be run in RoIs as a single pass. The performance of the RoI-based LRT in terms of speed and efficiency was already sufficient without needing to complicate the algorithm. Primary differences compared to the standard tracking include using only SCT clusters for seeding, removing the ordering of seeds by impact parameter, and the tighter track selection introduced in the updated LRT configuration. Tracks are reconstructed for charged particles with a transverse momentum greater than 1 GeV and at least a small displacement of $|d_0| > 2$ mm; though, this is a soft cutoff in the case of the RoI tracking. For the Full Scan LRT, the removal of hits used for the standard tracking means there are essentially no real tracks left to reconstruct at low d_0 .

Figure 6: Efficiency of the muon (left) and electron (right) standard and large radius tracking high level triggers versus the decay radius of long-lived supersymmetric staus. The tracking used for the standard electron chain is limited to $|d_0| < 5$ mm, making the efficiency near zero by construction [14].

The efficiency of muon and electron LRT-based triggers is shown in Figure 6 versus the decay radius of long-lived supersymmetric staus, i.e. the radius at which the muons or electrons are produced. The standard tracking based trigger's efficiency falls off rapidly, and the large radius tracking based trigger recovers the efficiency out to 300 mm, the first layer of the SCT. The LRT requires eight hits on the track, so the efficiency falls off rapidly past 300 mm. The hit requirement means that for very displaced or non-pointing tracks, the inner most hits on the track may fall outside of the RoI acceptance in the azimuthal angle ϕ , limiting the ability to reconstruct such tracks. The diagram in the left of Figure 7 depicts this. The RoI is approximately a wedge originating from the origin in the $r - \phi$ plane, with some fixed opening angle in ϕ . Generally, the processing time for the LRT in RoIs is faster than for the standard lepton triggers. The thresholds of the displaced lepton triggers for Run 3 are near those of the prompt lepton triggers, approximately 25 GeV. These are well below the thresholds from Run 2 and only require a single particle to pass the trigger, resulting in a large increase in acceptance for models with relatively low momentum displaced leptons in Run 3.

The Full Scan LRT trigger may be useful for signatures without an obvious RoI, or to add LRT to all of the jets in an event. It is not in the trigger menu at the time of writing, but is used in the development of displaced jet and vertex triggers that may be included in later trigger menus. The right plot of Figure 7 shows the efficiency of the Full Scan LRT for tracks from a displaced R-hadron decay (decaying into a muon

and quark) versus its decay radius. As with the RoI case, the LRT recovers the efficiency out to large radii compared to the standard tracking. The Full Scan tracking needs to process a large number of seeds, resulting in a longer processing time relative to the standard tracking. Optimizations to reduce the processing time result in a reduced efficiency compared to the offline tracking.

Figure 7: (left) Sketch in the $R-\phi$ plane of a very displaced track (thick-dashed line) where the first hit (solid dot) is missed in the online tracking due to falling outside of the Region-of-Interest's azimuthal acceptance. This is overlaid on a depiction of a track passing through detector layers [15]. (right) Efficiency to reconstruct tracks from a displaced R-hadron (decaying into a muon and quark) versus its decay radius for the high level trigger standard and large radius tracking as well as the offline tracking [14].

5 Conclusions

The Inner Detector Trigger is a vital part of the ATLAS trigger system, which supports the ATLAS physics program. It performed extremely well during the LHC's Run 2, with a high efficiency with respect to the offline tracking. An expanded use of Full Scan tracking in jet and missing transverse momentum triggers is anticipated for Run 3, and several optimizations have resulted in large reductions in the mean event processing time due to the tracking. Triggers targeting long-lived particles making use of unconventional tracking, such as large radius tracking and reconstructing short tracklets, have been developed for Run 3. The new triggers greatly increase the acceptance of the trigger to models with long-lived particles compared to what was possible in Run 2, particularly for those scenarios with relatively low momentum particles (below roughly 60 GeV).

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Linearized Track Fitting on an FPGA

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ABSTRACT

For the ATLAS experiment at the High-Luminosity LHC, a hardware-based track-trigger was originally envisioned, which performs pattern recognition via associative memory ASICs and track fitting on an FPGA. A linearized track fitting algorithm is implemented (Track Fitter) that receives fit-constants corresponding to the track candidates from a database, performs a χ^2 -test of the track, and calculates the helix-parameters. A prototype of the Track Fitter has been set-up on an Intel Stratix 10 FPGA. The firmware was tested in simulation-studies and verified in hardware. The performance of the Track Fitter has been evaluated in extensive simulation studies.

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1 Introduction

For the High-Luminosity Upgrade, ATLAS' Inner Detector is replaced by the Inner Tracker (ITk) [1, 2]. With a planned peak instantaneous luminosity of $7.5 \cdot 10^{34} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$, a pileup of 200 inelastic proton-proton collisions is expected [3]. It was planned to include a Hardware Track Trigger (HTT) into the Event Filter System to reduce the load, for reconstructing tracks, on the processor farm [3], see Figure 1.

Figure 1: Summary of the ATLAS TDAQ dataflow.

Figure 2: Firmware diagram of the PRM [4].

The HTT is split into several units, each performing tracking in regions of the ITk. The HTT consists of two types of units: Associative Memory Tracking Processors (AMTPs) and Second-Stage Tracking Processors (SSTPs) [5]. This work focuses on the Pattern Recognition Mezzanine (PRM), which is the central component of the AMTP. The PRM houses four groups of Associative Memory (AM) ASICs that organize detector hits into track candidates, as well as an Intel Stratix 10 FPGA for data handling and track fitting (see Figure 2).

2 Track Linking

The ITk consists of thirteen detector layers [1]. To conduct meaningful physics, hits that originate from the same particle have to be connected to a track. Examining all particle hit combinations from all layers leads to an unfeasible amount of calculations. Therefore, it is paramount that the number of track candidates is reduced as early as possible.

Several methods have been developed to solve that problem [6]. The HTT utilizes *pattern matching*, a highly parallel approach to track linking that is therefore well suited to an implementation in hardware [7].

By simulating a large amount of particle tracks using extensive Monte Carlo simulations [3] and storing the resulting patterns of hits before the experiment is set up, templates are generated to which the actual hit patterns are compared to. This technique not only finds track candidates very quickly (processing time grows linearly with number of hits) but also provides track parameters [7]. Since the number of possible tracks usually exceeds the available memory resources, patterns are stored for a reduced granularity detector model. Reducing the granularity increases the number of nearby tracks that cannot be differentiated. A trade-off between resolution and storage space has to be decided through simulation [7]. Although, for track linking only coarse hit information is used, the full hit information is recovered at a later stage for the track fitting.

The template matching is performed by the AM ASICs [8] in the following way: First, the resolution of the incoming data is reduced (see Figure 2, *Cluster to SSID Encoder*). Then all hit data of one event are loaded into the AM ASICs in series. If a data package arrives that matches an entry of the pattern bank, the entry gets flagged (see Figure 3, second row). When the AM ASIC receives a signal that the event has concluded, it checks which of its patterns have more than a given threshold of matched layers (see Figure 3, third row). Then the AM ASIC starts to return the identifiers of the matched patterns (see Figure 3, fourth row).

Since the AM ASICs have not been produced in time for the prototyping stage of the PRM development, an emulator was developed. Together with a custom interface, the emulator is implemented on the FPGA and follows the algorithm of the original ASIC design, although with reduced memory and an extra interface to access the AM database more directly.

3 Track Fitting

Charged particles follow a helix-trajectory in a homogeneous magnetic field. A helix fit takes a considerable amount of processing time and requires non-linear calculations which are not ideal to be performed on an FPGA.

Instead, the computationally expensive calculation of the fits is performed offline using the simulated tracks from the AM ASIC database. For small variation in the hit-data, the circular form of the track can be approximated as a parabola so that the fit parameters p_i and the goodness χ^2 vary in a linear way [9]. Therefore, the fit parameters and goodness can be approximated using the measured hit-data of a track candidate and the constants that describe the linear variation. The database of simulated tracks is divided into regions for which the constants of the linear equations are sufficiently similar. These constants are stored in a second database on the FPGA to be used in online track reconstruction.

Each parameter and each degree of freedom of the fit need their own constants for each of the eight detector layers that is used for track reconstruction. A full set of constants for a single track fit represent roughly 5 kbit of data that have to be made available to the FPGA at each clock cycle. This necessitates the usage of an FPGA with up to 16 GB, 512 GB/s High Bandwidth Memory (HBM) like the Intel Stratix 10 [10].

For the track fitting, the FPGA receives the full-resolution hit data \vec{x} of a track candidate and retrieves the constants of the linear equations corresponding to the track candidates sector. The five helix parameters p_i are calculated with the constants \vec{C}_i and q_i [3]:

$$p_i = \vec{C}_i \cdot \vec{x} + q_i . \quad (1)$$

Figure 3: Simplified representation of the pattern recognition algorithm for a detector with six layers (columns) and a pattern bank with four entries (rows). The steps of the algorithm represent a single clock-cycle each and happen chronologically from top to bottom and left to right. The displayed event has up to three hits per detector layer from which two patterns are found.

For J degrees of freedom, the goodness χ^2 of the fit is calculated with the constants \vec{S}_j and h_j [3]:

$$\chi^2 = \sum_{j=0}^J \left(\vec{S}_j \cdot \vec{x} + h_j \right)^2 . \quad (2)$$

The resulting goodness is then compared with a preset threshold. Since only 20% of the track candidates are expected to pass the goodness test [4], the goodness is calculated first to save resources on the FPGA.

4 Firmware Implementation

Figure 4: Data-Flow through the Track Fitter. Only connections used by *data*, i.e. tracks or constants are shown; connections that are solely used by requests, commands or status signals are omitted to increase readability.

The Track Fitter receives data packages that consist of a *road*, containing up to three hit clusters per layer*, the number of clusters per layer, the identifiers of the road, its event, and of the sector that contains the constants for calculating the goodness χ^2 and the parameters of the track candidates from that road.

In Figure 4 the flow of the main data packages through the Track Fitter is visualized. The Track Distributor receives the entire data package from the Data Organizer, an entity outside of the Track Fitter (see Figure 2). It distributes the roads evenly between four channels and decodes all possible tracks from each road. The tracks and identifiers are then stored in the channel's Track Buffer I.

*The firmware is limited to three clusters so it can guarantee to match its required road-acceptance rate.

Figure 5: Histogram of the latency of the Track Fitter between receiving a track candidate and returning of the parameters (including the goodness of the fit). These data are taken from the PRM simulation.

The HBM Interface (HBM-IF) receives sector-identifiers and sends requests to the HBM for the constants from that sector. The HBM-IF receives the constants after an undetermined latency[†] and stores them internally. When the Track Buffer I receives data from the Track Distributor, it sends the sector-identifier to the HBM-IF to ask for the constants \vec{S}_i and h_i that are used in the goodness calculation, which are then stored in that channel’s Constant Buffer I.

The Track Constant Aligner I checks the data stored in the upstream buffers to ensure that the tracks, which are sent to the CHI2-unit, are accompanied by the constants from the correct sector. There is no timeout but when the buffer is full, further constants are lost.

The CHI2 unit calculates the goodness of the track and applies a threshold cut. The track is sent to the Track Multiplexer if it passes the goodness test. The Track Multiplexer sends the tracks to the Track Buffer II and their sector-identifiers to the HBM-IF to request the constants necessary to calculate the track parameters.

The HBM-IF sends a second request to the HBM and later transmits the parameter constants to the Constant Buffer II. The Track Constant Aligner II performs the same operations as the Track Constant Aligner I and sends the tracks (and the identifiers and goodness) together with the correct parameter constants to the Parameter Calculator.

5 Results

Mentor Graphics’ *Questa Sim* [12] has been used to simulate the firmware. Two simulation setups are examined: one for the entire PRM with the AM ASIC emulators and an HBM simulation model, the second one for the Track Fitter with an HBM emulator. The simulation runs with a frequency of 250 MHz, therefore the Track Fitter simulation is compliant with a road rate of 80 MHz. The Track Fitter simulation has a mean latency of 680 ns, dominated by the latency of the HBM (see Figure 5). That fulfills the road-rate and latency requirements of the Level 1 configuration of the ATLAS Phase-II Upgrade DAQ system (i.e. ≥ 65 MHz [4] and $\leq 1 \mu\text{s}$ respectively).

The PRM firmware successfully runs with a prototype Intel Stratix 10 FPGA. No tests have been performed with a frequency exceeding 100 MHz. To achieve the desired speed of 250 MHz on the prototype hardware, further optimization is necessary.

[†]99% of constant-packages are returned to the HBM-IF within a latency of 850 ns [11].

Figure 6: Top: Transverse momentum resolution of the software emulation of the HTT (red) and the offline simulation (black). Bottom: Relative transverse momentum resolution between those two simulations (red). These data refer to single muons with a transverse momentum of $p_T = 10$ GeV from pp-collisions with a center-of-mass energy of $\sqrt{s} = 14$ TeV [13].

The Track Fitter calculates the fit parameters and the goodness of dummy data perfectly reliable within the precision of its number representation (single precision floats, downsized at the output to 16 bit signed fixed point numbers that use eight bits for the exponent). For a few data-samples, the fit parameters (and goodness) have been compared bit-by-bit to the expected values and good agreement was found. Due to the limited nature of available test data, an extensive measurement of fit performance has not been conducted but further studies are underway. Since the implementation in the Track Fitter is mathematically sound, the quality of the fits depends only on the quality of the linearization of the fit parameters and the size of the sectors (see also [9]). Software emulation studies have shown that the HTT is able to reconstruct 95% of all tracks [13] with a momentum resolution that is not more than 75% worse than the offline algorithm (see Figure 6). More information about these performance studies can be found in [13].

6 Conclusions

The linearized track fitting approach was proven to work in simulation and in prototype hardware. Even though the HTT project was canceled, the design presented here can be used for further developments and can possibly be implemented in a modified form as part of the ATLAS Event Filter System, see Figure 1. Investigations on the performance of the Track Fitter without the HBM and dedicated hardware are currently conducted.

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ACTS GPU Track Reconstruction Demonstrator for HEP

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ABSTRACT

Track reconstruction speed in high-energy physics experiments becomes more important with increasing accelerator luminosity, data volumes, and measurement densities. Heterogeneous computing with GPU is a promising way to accelerate the analysis considering that the track reconstruction is parallelizable. Therefore, the ACTS community initiated R&D projects to develop the GPU track reconstruction demonstrator. In this work, we introduce its recent progress in tracking algorithm implementation and realistic detector setup.

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1 Introduction

A Common Tracking Software (ACTS) [1, 2] is an open source track reconstruction toolkit for high energy physics (HEP) experiments written in the C++ language. The project serves as an analysis toolkit for various experiments, as well as an R&D platform for the applications of GPGPUs [3] in track reconstruction. The massively parallel nature of GPGPUs has great potential to accelerate the data analysis of future HEP experiments with larger data size. With that prospect, pilot studies [4] have been conducted by the ACTS community to offload several track reconstruction algorithms to GPU architectures. Although the first benchmark results are encouraging, embedding GPU algorithms in existing track reconstruction pipelines remains an open problem because run-time polymorphism and dynamic allocation of memory massively used in ACTS is not GPU-friendly.

In an effort to resolve the aforementioned issues, the ACTS community has developed a novel GPU track reconstruction demonstrator for both offline and online [5] analysis. In this work, we present the recent progress in the GPU demonstrator development: Section 2 introduces the R&D libraries of the ACTS GPU demonstrator. Section 3 highlights the currently implemented algorithms and their performance. Section 4 describes a compile-time polymorphic tracking geometry and its track propagation tool. A summary follows in Section 5.

2 R&D Libraries for the GPU demonstrator

The ACTS GPU demonstrator follows an experiment-independent design while aiming to match the physics performance of existing CPU-based algorithms with a realistic detector setup. The demonstrator should also support a variety of heterogeneous programming platforms; CUDA [6] and SYCL [7] are currently the primary targets. We support both the mature but vendor-specific CUDA platform and the more recent and widely applicable SYCL platform. The ACTS R&D ecosystem in which these points are investigated is shown in Figure 1.

2.1 vecmem

`vecmem` [8, 9] is a memory management library with a user-friendly interface for a variety of programming platforms that include CUDA and SYCL. In host code, it utilizes polymorphic memory resources [10] to allocate memory through STL-like containers. It also supports STL-like containers on the device to provide a similar user interface between host code and device code. Caching allocation exists as well where the memory allocation time can be saved by reusing the previously allocated memory.

2.2 algebra-plugins

`algebra-plugins` [11] is a library that provides different implementations of vector and matrix algebra operations necessary for track reconstruction algorithms. It supports various backends such as `cmath` (custom implementation), `Eigen` [12] and `SMatrix` [13]. The development of custom implementations of `cmath` backend is motivated by the need of having native support for CUDA and SYCL. Users can determine which backend and floating-point precision to use at compile-time.

2.3 covfie

`covfie` [14] is a library for general vector field calculation, which supports a wide range of possible vector fields, including the sampled inhomogeneous magnetic fields found in HEP experiments. Similar to the design of `algebra-plugins`, the GPU APIs, vector field dimension, and interpolation algorithm can be determined at compile-time.

2.4 detr_{ay}

detr_{ay} [15, 16] is a tracking geometry library with a GPU-friendly design that relies on static compile-time polymorphism. It also supports the track propagation functionality required for track reconstruction algorithms. Components of the tracking geometry are stored in **vecmem** containers which are compatible with both host-side execution and device-side execution. **covfie** is integrated into **detr_{ay}** for the track propagation with an inhomogeneous magnetic field.

Figure 1: ACTS GPU R&D projects. The dependencies between the projects are represented by arrows.

3 Tracking Algorithm Implementations

tracc [17] makes use of all other libraries introduced in Section 2 to perform the track reconstruction on GPU. It covers track reconstruction algorithms from the raw data processing to the precise fitting of charged particle trajectories as explained in Ref [1] and illustrated in Figure 2. The rest of this section will describe the implementation and performance of the cell clusterization and seeding on GPU, while Section 4 is dedicated to **detr_{ay}** tracking geometry which is an essential step towards the implementation of a parallel (Combinatorial) Kalman Filtering [18, 19, 20, 21] on GPU.

3.1 GPU Implementation

One of the challenges in implementing GPU algorithms is avoiding the dynamic allocation of memory. This means that the size of output vector containers must be known before executing the kernel. An intuitive solution for this would be allocating the vector size as large as a theoretical limit. For example, if there are N hits in an event, the number of clusters should be less than or equal to N , where N is the theoretical limit. Clearly, this approach will waste a significant amount of memory, therefore, it was not considered a plausible option. As an alternative, a vector size can be estimated by investigating the number of output objects as a function of the number of the input objects. However, it is not a convenient solution because the hard coded sizes need to be updated whenever there is a change in the detector setup. The adopted solution is to run two kernels instead of one: a counting kernel and a populating kernel. The counting kernel estimates the number of output objects after which a suitably large output vector can be allocated on the host, and the populating function fills the output vector. Even though this comes at the cost of running some functions twice and the counter variables need to be reset to zero after the populating kernel, this method was selected for the purpose of code maintainability and to optimize memory operations.

Figure 2: The track reconstruction chain of `tracc`.

Figure 3 and 4 show the time measurement [22] for the cell clusterization with the SparseCCL algorithm [23, 24] and seeding as a function of the number of $t\bar{t}$ interactions per event, respectively. The computing environment was an Intel i7-10750H (2.6 GHz base frequency) CPU and an NVIDIA RTX 2070 GPU. The algorithms were benchmarked in both single-precision and double-precision floating point mode with the `cmath` backend of `algebra-plugins`. The input data [25] was prepared by ACTS simulation with $t\bar{t}$ interactions (14 TeV center-of-mass energy collision) in the trackML detector [26] which conceptually follows the upgraded design of ATLAS and CMS detectors [27, 28]. There was no notable speedup gain from the GPU over the single-core CPU implementation for the cell clusterization algorithm which we believe to be due to imbalance in the workloads between threads, which could be further optimized. In case of the seeding algorithm, both the CUDA and SYCL implementations achieved a speedup of roughly one order of magnitude over the single-core CPU implementation for single precision while the speedup dropped to a factor five for double precision. The speedup drop in seeding with double precision is expected as the GPU hardware has fewer double-precision arithmetic units. The same effect was not seen in the cell clusterization as it has much less floating point arithmetic compared to the seeding.

Figure 3: (Preliminary) Cell clusterization time averaged over 10 events as a function of the number of $t\bar{t}$ interactions per event with 14 TeV center-of-mass energy collision. (a) The left figure is measured for single precision, and (b) the right one is measured for double precision. SYCL uses the CUDA backend for GPU measurement.

Figure 4: (Preliminary) Seeding time averaged over 10 events as a function of the number of $t\bar{t}$ interactions per event with 14 TeV center-of-mass energy collision. (a) The left figure is measured for single precision, and (b) the right one is measured for double precision. SYCL uses the CUDA backend for GPU measurement.

4 Towards a Parallel CKF: Tracking Geometry

A tracking geometry is necessary for the implementation of the CKF method because the algorithm needs to look up the measurements of a detector surface encountered during the track propagation. In this section, we explain a design of such a tracking geometry and its track propagation functionality with an inhomogeneous magnetic field interpolation.

4.1 Detector Description

The `detray` tracking geometry consists of several component types which are inter-linked through index variables. A surface stores the indices of masks, which describe the shape and dimensions, and an affine transform matrix which carries the rotation and translation information. A volume represents a section of the detector as an aggregation of surfaces, including its own boundary (virtual) surfaces called portals and physical surfaces.

To facilitate host-server communication, the tracking geometry is implemented using static polymorphism. Masks of different types are stored in a tuple, and the required mask types are declared at compile-time in detector specific metadata. Since it is not possible to access tuple elements with run-time index variables, the tuple container of masks is unrolled using variadic templates to retrieve the specific mask that is referenced by a particular surface in the tracking geometry. With the shape information being pushed entirely to the lightweight mask objects, the rest of the data, i.e. the transform matrices, surfaces and volumes can be stored in standard vector containers due to their fixed types.

The tracking geometry is built inside the host code and passed over to the device if required: the host geometry transferred via an intermediate view type object constructs the corresponding device geometry inside the kernel function.

4.2 Track Propagation

In `detray` track propagation, track parameters of charged particles are advanced using a fourth order Runge-Kutta-Nyström (RKN) method [29]. The step size of the RKN method is dynamically adjusted by the local error expected from the gradient of the magnetic field while it is limited by the distance to the closest surface. A straight-line ray is shot to find candidate surfaces, which the track might intersect, and the corresponding distances to the surfaces. The distance to the closest surface is updated for every step, and the list of candidates is renewed when the track enters a new volume through a portal.

For the GPU implementation, one track was mapped to each thread of a kernel function because the tracks can be propagated independently from each other during the propagation. Figure 5 shows the time

measurement [30] of propagation in the trackML detector in a constant 2 T magnetic field. Tracks of 10 GeV were generated at the origin of the detector and shot in isotropic direction. Similarly to the seeding algorithm, the CUDA implementation showed an order of magnitude of speedup over a single CPU core, while the `cmath` and `Eigen` backends did not show significant difference in performance one from each other, regardless of the hardware.

Figure 5: (Preliminary) Propagation time in the pixel section of the trackML detector as a function of the number of tracks in log-log scale, estimated for (a) single and (b) double precision, respectively. Tracks of 10 GeV were generated in isotropic direction in a homogeneous magnetic field of 2 T.

4.3 Magnetic Fieldmap Interpolation

In most HEP experiments, the magnetic field is inhomogeneous throughout the detector. Therefore, it is common for such magnetic fields to be described by a set of field vectors at discrete, uniformly sampled points. In lieu of a continuous field map, values must be interpolated from nearby sample points. `covfie` supports a trilinear interpolation method [31], implemented both in software as well as in hardware through the use of GPU texture-fetching units. The integration of these magnetic field accessors into the `detray` track propagation is still under development.

5 Summary

The ACTS community has initiated R&D projects to run tracking algorithms in GPUs. `vecmem` is a memory management tool developed in order to provide a convenient interface to the GPU APIs. `algebra-plugins` provides vector and matrix operations necessary for track reconstruction. In order to allow for a realistic detector descriptions, `detray` and `covfie` have been set up to provide track propagation through tracking geometries and interpolation of inhomogeneous magnetic fields, respectively. `tracc` integrates these libraries for track reconstruction and we have demonstrated clusterization and seeding algorithms using CUDA and SYCL. While the first benchmark results on track reconstruction and propagation are promising, the overall performance needs to be optimized with the `vecmem` caching allocation and multi threading method for apple to apple comparison between CPU and GPU. Ongoing developments include the implementation of (Combinatorial) Kalman filtering using the `detray` track propagation.

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Line Segment Tracking in the HL-LHC

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ABSTRACT

The major challenge posed by the high instantaneous luminosity in the High Luminosity LHC (HL-LHC) motivates efficient and fast reconstruction of charged particle tracks in a high pile-up environment. While there have been efforts to use modern techniques like vectorization to improve the existing classic Kalman Filter based reconstruction algorithms, Line Segment Tracking takes a fundamentally different approach by doing a bottom-up reconstruction of tracks. Small track stubs from adjoining detector regions are constructed, and then these track stubs that are consistent with typical track trajectories are successively linked. Since the production of these track stubs is localized, they can be made in parallel, which lends way into using architectures like GPUs and multi-CPU's to take advantage of the parallelism. The algorithm is implemented in the context of the CMS Phase-2 Tracker and runs on NVIDIA Tesla V100 GPUs. Good physics and timing performance has been obtained, and stepping stones for the future are elaborated.

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1 Introduction

The reconstruction of charged particle tracks is at the heart of object reconstruction in the experiments at the Large Hadron Collider. The tracker provides accurate estimates of momentum and energy of the decay particles and hence plays a crucial role in the reconstruction of parent particles. Algorithms such as vertex and jet reconstruction, and calculation of the missing transverse momentum and b-jet tagging rely crucially on tracking.

Charged particle track reconstruction is the most expensive and the most time consuming step in the object reconstruction pipeline. Since this process is combinatorial in nature, it scales exponentially with the multiplicity of hits in the detector. With increased pp collisions in the HL-LHC [1], the pile-up will increase around 4-5 times compared to its existing value in the LHC. This implies that tracking times will increase by more than an order of magnitude in the HL-LHC if we stay with the same tracker and algorithms used in the CMS Experiment during Run 2 [2]. This implies the existing iterative tracking algorithms will be too slow to be able to efficiently reconstruct tracks in a timely manner in the HL-LHC. In addition, computational performance of single thread processors is plateauing while computational demands are increasing. However, the current era is also marked by the advent of multi-threaded and multi-core CPUs, and innovations in the co-processor sphere like Graphical Processing Units (GPUs) and Field Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs) which are able to provide massive increases in computational processing speed, and hence are expected to dominate High Performance Computing (HPC) workflows in the near future. This motivates a re-design of track reconstruction algorithms to take advantage of these new architectures and break the computational barrier in the near future.

In this work, we present a bottom-up localized track reconstruction algorithm for the CMS outer tracker (Figure 1) called Line Segment Tracking, wherein charged particles are grouped together to reconstruct entire tracks from the ground up. An advantage of this algorithm is that it is readily parallelizable, since only localized information is required at each step to reconstruct track constituents. The outer tracker (Figure 1)

Figure 1: Outer tracker geometry and module structure in CMS at the HL-LHC [3]

is composed of bi-layer P_T modules (Figure 1 right). A P_T module has two silicon layers that are ≈ 2 to 4mm apart. These closely spaced modules ensure hits can be correlated to get preliminary estimates of the transverse momentum, using which track stubs made up of hit pairs consistent with a track hypothesis can be selected. These track stubs can be used as fundamental building blocks of any tracking algorithm. The usage of the track stubs ensure that the effective number of initial seeds is reduced, thereby reducing combinatorics without any loss of efficiency.

Line Segment Tracking was originally inspired by the XFT algorithm used at the CDF Experiment at the Tevatron, Fermilab [4]. A previous version of this algorithm was introduced in the 2020 edition of Connecting the Dots [5]. A similar algorithm was used in the context of grouped layer tracker layout design [6] which showed promising results on the combinatorics reduction front.

2 Line Segment Tracking in the HL-LHC CMS Outer Tracker

2.1 Overview

Line Segment Tracking (LST) is a parallelized track reconstruction algorithm that does a bottom-up reconstruction of tracks by creating track objects from correlated hit pairs (stubs). These short objects are then linked to create longer objects with a greater number of associated hits. This process is repeated until entire tracks are reconstructed. Since the reconstruction of the higher order objects only depends on lower order objects in the immediate neighbourhood, the reconstruction is highly local and hence can be parallelized effectively. The hits are first clustered into Mini-doublets, which are comprised of two hits. Mini-doublets then link up to create segments (four hits). Segments then link up to create Triplets (6 hits), which can then be linked to create Quintuplets (10 hits) and so on. Various physics and geometrical selections are applied at each linking level to reduce combinatorics and ensure only legitimate track candidates are created.

In addition, tracking seeds from the inner pixel tracker are incorporated as segments, which when linked with a Triplet or a Quintuplet can create a Pixel Triplet or a Pixel Quintuplet. The addition of the pixel track seeds helps in reducing the combinatorial fakes and essentially provides a link between the inner and outer trackers.

2.2 Mini-doublets and Segments

The track stub created in a bi-layer module consistent with the P_T threshold is called a Mini-doublet. These are denoted by the green dot in Figure 2. These are the fundamental building blocks of our algorithm. Since we only have localized information at this juncture, we only rely on the slope information consistent with a particle coming from the origin, and account for additional error terms which take care of multiple scattering and uncertainties in the luminous region.

Figure 2: Mini-doublets (Green dots) linked using module maps to create segments

Line Segments are produced by linking two mini-doublets from modules across different layers (Figure 2). A “segment candidate” is formed from two mini-doublets in different layers and then physics selections are applied to check if this can be a legitimate segment from a true track. To reduce our search window for the number of possible connections, we derive a “module map” which is a lookup table that details the list of possible module connections from a given module. This was derived from first principles by computing the possible track trajectories as helices that can start from the edges of a given module that are compatible with the P_T threshold (in our case, 0.8 GeV), and then listing all the modules in the adjacent layer that intersect these helices. This map was then verified using simulated samples for correctness. A first principles approach like this helps us take all possible edge cases into account, which would be quite difficult if we relied only on simulations to compute the module map.

2.3 Triplets and Quintuplets

Two line segments having a common mini-doublet can be linked to form a Triplet (also called a T3), as shown in Figure 3a. The requirement of a common mini-doublet greatly reduces the combinatorics. Other selections here include the χ^2 obtained from fitting a straight line to the three “anchor hits” of the mini-doublet in the r-z plane, the anchor hit being the more-precise hit on the pixel side for a PS module, and the hit on the lower side of a 2S module.

Similarly, two triplets with a common mini-doublet can be joined to form a Quintuplet (also called a T5), as shown in Figure 3b. In addition to applying a straight line pointing criterion similar to the triplet case, we also require that the circles formed from the anchor hits of the inner and outer triplets have radii close to each other. Such circles are trivially created from the three points of a triplet. This is followed by a global circle fit using all the five anchor hits and a selection based on the χ^2 of the resulting hit. The χ^2 cuts are derived empirically for different categories of quintuplets and provide good reduction of the spurious linkages.

Figure 3: Triplet and Quintuplet

2.4 Linking the pixel and outer trackers - Pixel Triplets and Pixel Quintuplets

Pixel track seeds produced in the inner tracker are incorporated in LST as line segments, called Pixel Line Segments (pLS). The outer tracker objects can be linked to these pixel line segments to produce objects such as Pixel Triplets and Pixel Quintuplets (Figure 4). Selections similar to that used for the Quintuplets are used here, the difference being that the straight lines and circles in the r-z and x-y plane, respectively, are not fit but rather the estimates from the pixel detector are used and the consistency of the outer hits to this hypothesis is checked. The incorporation of the pixel line segments ensure that only those tracks from the interaction vertex that are also consistent with the inner pixel are ultimately incorporated, thereby reducing combinatorial fakes even further.

2.5 Cross-cleaning and Track Candidates

The final track candidate collection consists of pixel quintuplets, pixel triplets, Quintuplets and pixel line segments, added in that sequence. The Pixel Quintuplets are the cleanest objects that also span almost the entire length of the outer detector. So these will serve as the main component of our final track candidates. To ensure track duplicates between different objects are not added to the final collection, we “cross-clean” the objects. So when Pixel Triplets are added to the final collection, only those Pixel Triplets that are not near a Pixel Quintuplet (in η - ϕ space) are added. This ensures that the Pixel Triplets added are those that exclusively correspond to those tracks which could not produce a Pixel Quintuplet possibly due to a missing mini-doublet and/or hit somewhere that resulted in the underlying objects not being produced. Similarly, the Quintuplets after undergoing cross-cleaning correspond mainly to the displaced tracks, since they will not have any pixel track seeds (this can be seen in the transverse impact parameter, Δ_{xy} , efficiency distributions

Figure 4: Pixel linked objects - Pixel Triplet and Pixel Quintuplet

in Figure 7a). Finally, the Pixel Line Segments that follow a strict set of criteria (they need to not be a part of any other object, they should be appreciably far away in $\eta - \phi$ space with the other objects etc) provide coverage mainly in the forward region (this can be seen in the η efficiency distributions in Figure 6b).

2.5.1 Track Extensions and Final Track Collection

A subset (approximately half) of the track candidates can be linked with triplets in the outermost regions of the tracker to create longer tracks that can span the entire length of the outer tracker. These extended tracks along with those track candidates that cannot be extended, make up the final collection of track candidates by the algorithm.

3 Physics performance

To measure the physics performance and fine-tune the cuts, a dataset of the simulated detector response to a $t\bar{t}$ decay in a pile-up 200 environment was produced. A track candidate produced by Line Segment Tracking is said to be matched to a “true” (simulated) track if 75% of the associated hits match. The efficiency is computed as the fraction of true tracks in a P_T or η bin that have a matched track candidate.

The fake rate is calculated as the fraction of reconstructed tracks that are fakes (not matched to true tracks), while the duplicate rate is calculated as the fraction of reconstructed tracks that are duplicates. When two or more reconstructed tracks match with a simulated track, all of them are considered duplicates of one another and get included in the computation of the duplicate rate.

3.1 Efficiency performance

The track candidate reconstruction efficiency distributions as a function of P_T and η are shown in Figures 5a and 5b as a function of P_T and η , respectively. The turn-on region is at 0.8 GeV, and we see good reconstruction efficiency above that, comparable with the existing Combinatorial Kalman Filter Based tracking algorithm for the CMS [7, Figure 10.2]. The η distributions are computed with an implicit P_T cut of 0.9 GeV. The contributions to the track candidate efficiency plots broken up into individual components are shown in Figure 6. The Pixel Quintuplets (pT5) contribute the highest to the efficiency, while the Pixel Line Segments (pLS) not linked to an outer tracker object contribute in the forward ($|\eta| > 2$) regions.

The displaced track reconstruction performance is measured by computing the efficiency as the function of the x-y distance from the interaction point (Δ_{xy}). In addition to checking the physics performance on the $t\bar{t}$ + Pile-up 200 sample (Figure 7a) in which the Quintuplets (T5) contribute the most to displaced track reconstruction (non-zero Δ_{xy}), we also verified the physics performance on a sample of displaced muon

Figure 6: LST efficiency on $t\bar{t}$ + PU200 sample

tracks originating from a point displaced from the origin in a 5cm cube (Figure 7b). Good reconstruction efficiency has been achieved, given the fact that no extra steps in the algorithm are dedicated specifically to reconstructing displaced tracks. These promising results show that this can be improved further.

Figure 7: LST efficiency with displaced tracks - PU200 and muon cube

3.2 Fake and duplicate rates performance

Figures 8a and 8b show the distribution of fake rates as a function of P_T and η . The Pixel Line Segments (pLS) contribute the highest, especially in the forward region ($|\eta| > 2.5$), with almost all the fakes attributable to them in the forward region. These fake rates can be reduced further with fine-tuning of selection parameters and a full fit of hit patterns.

Since efficient cross-cleaning is done, the duplicate rates (Figures 9a and 9b) are quite low. A low duplicate rate means that the final collection of tracks is compact and repeated reconstruction is reduced.

Figure 8: LST fake rates on $t\bar{t}$ + PU200 sample

Figure 9: LST duplicate rates on $t\bar{t}$ + PU200 sample

4 Line Segment Tracking on the GPU

4.1 GPUs overview

Graphical Processing Units (GPUs) (Figure 10) have numerous compute cores compared to CPUs. However they compromise on caches and data transport. In addition, GPUs also tend to have lower clock speed (approx 1 GHz), compared to CPUs (2-5 GHz). If GPUs can be programmed such that the compute cores can do work on existing data while the caches wait for new data, tremendous speed-ups can be achieved. This technique is called latency hiding and is central to GPU programming.

CUDA (formerly an acronym for Compute Unified Device Architecture) is a GPU programming framework for Nvidia GPUs which provide high level functions to develop software that runs on GPUs. The Line Segment Tracking implementation for GPUs is written in CUDA and targets the recent generation of GPUs.

4.2 GPU Implementation of Line Segment Tracking

Figure 11 shows a visual representation of the GPU implementation. Each block, which corresponds to creating a particular class of track object, is parallelized. The entire flow, however, runs in sequence, since the algorithm requires that objects be hierarchically built upwards. Each of these object creation steps get their own kernel, in addition to a kernel that deals with pre-processing the hits and loading them into

Figure 10: CPUs vs GPUs [8]

GPU memory. Multi-streaming and efficient memory management play an important role in improving performance.

Figure 11: GPU implementation flowchart. Only the more important steps are explicitly shown, the others are represented by dots (...)

4.2.1 Memory management

Since GPUs work on the Single Instruction Multi-thread (SIMT) principle, it is imperative that the data be stored in such a way that the compute cores get to use all the data that streams into the caches. Since GPUs are programmed such that multiple cores perform the same computational task in parallel on different data, cache hit rates and memory transfers from the device memory will be maximized when adjacent compute cores (that work on adjacent units of memory) get to use their respective data without any delays. This implies that the data need to be stored in a specific manner, commonly called the Structure of Arrays (SoA) data representation framework.

In the SoA data representation framework, the data corresponding to a particular quantity in memory is stored continuously for all objects in a single array. For example, if we want to store the P_T information for mini-doublets, we store this for all mini-doublets continuously in an array (as opposed to creating a class object for each mini-doublet, which will have the P_T value as one of its members). This would mean that when the P_T values are required for some computation, the compute cores will be readily able to access them with very high cache hit rates.

To reduce the huge overheads in memory allocation in the GPUs, we developed a caching allocator based on the CUB library developed by Nvidia [9], which exponentially allocates memory based on the current demand, i.e., if 5MB of memory is requested, the caching allocator makes 8MB available, which means that the allocations for the next 3MB have zero overhead (when they happen). Since our framework has memory allocation and deletion spread all over, as opposed to all of it happening in one place in the beginning of the code, the caching allocator provides around 32% improvement in compute time.

4.2.2 Event level parallelization: Multi-streaming

While classic event level parallelization tries to get multiple events, and their entire reconstruction processes to run in parallel, the sheer amount of compute cores required for object creation in the Line Segment Tracking case limits this application. However, the GPU downtimes can be used to do part of the work from multiple events in tandem. Figure 12a shows the timeline of GPU usage when collision events get processed sequentially. The situation we have is that all the compute cores in the GPU are used for a period of time, followed by an interval of little to no work, which is when preparations for the next cycle of high intensity workload happens. Our variant of multi-streaming attaches events to streams, but the work gets distributed such that these downtimes are used for doing some work pertaining to a different stream. Figure 12b shows how tasks from different streams (each row corresponds to a stream here) get tessellated. However, here are significant overlap regions where the GPU needs to work on two kernels, which means that compute cores get split between these kernels which result in a reduction in performance (and increase in time) of individual kernels, but the overall timing gets greatly improved.

Figure 12: GPU timelines for the single stream and eight streams case

4.3 Timing performance

The complete timing performance, replete with individual object breakdowns when tracks from $t\bar{t}$ pile-up 200 events are reconstructed on a Tesla V100 GPU can be seen in Table 1. Our best timing performance is 34 ms/event on a single stream, and 26 ms/event on eight streams. A caveat is that this timing performance does not take into account the extensive initial copy of hits from CPU to GPU, or the tracks from GPU to CPU. The timing performance is comparable to the latest results from the performance of the CMS Track Pattern recognition algorithms [10], which also reconstructs tracks with P_T above 0.8 GeV. Line Segment Tracking is also comparable on the cost front with the CMS track pattern recognition algorithm scaled to 64 cores, since two 32 core Intel Skylake Gold Xeon Processors (commonly used in the multi-CPU efforts) have a similar price to a Tesla V100 GPU.

Number of streams	Average time per event (ms)
1	33.7
2	27.3
4	26.2
6	26.3
8	25.7

Table 1: Line Segment Tracking timing performance - $t\bar{t}$ + PU200, Tesla V100 GPU

5 Conclusions

Line Segment Tracking is a parallelizable track reconstruction algorithm targeting the Phase 2 CMS Detector. The backbone of the algorithm is the stub created from the bi-layer module, called the mini-doublet. The higher order objects are successively built by linking lower order objects which can then create entire tracks, with each step of the process being parallelizable. Selections and cuts are applied to reduce the overwhelming combinatorial backgrounds. Good reconstruction efficiency and low fake rates have been achieved on $t\bar{t}$ + pile-up 200 samples, competitive with the CKF implementation used by CMS. The GPU implementation of the algorithm has innovative memory management and multi-streaming techniques, and provides competitive timing performance on Nvidia Tesla V100 GPUs.

Our future work will involve revisiting some of the physics selections and looking at methods to reduce the combinatorial background and improve the efficiency even further. A substantial amount of effort will go into improving the reconstruction efficiency of displaced tracks. On the optimization and computational performance front, we have currently only scratched the surface. Our future efforts in this front will go towards efficient computation of mathematical parameters for physics selection, in addition to improving memory throughput by exploring data types such as half precision floats. Plans to improve memory coalescing and optimizing register usage will help in improving our timing performance further. Our final target is to deploy this in the CMS software backend for HLT and offline reconstruction in time for HL-LHC.

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Exploration of different parameter optimization algorithms within the context of ACTS software framework

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ABSTRACT

Particle track reconstruction, in which the trajectories of charged particles are determined, is a critical and time consuming component of the full event reconstruction chain. The underlying software is complex and consists of a number of mathematically intense algorithms, each dealing with a particular tracking sub-process. These algorithms have many input parameters that need to be supplied in advance. However, it is difficult to determine the configuration of these parameters that produces the best performance. Currently, the input parameter values are decided on the basis of prior experience or by the use of brute force techniques. A parameter optimization approach that is able to automatically tune these parameters for high performance is greatly desirable. In the current work, we explore various machine learning based optimization methods to devise a suitable technique to optimize parameters in the complex track reconstruction environment. These methods are evaluated on the basis of a metric that targets high efficiency while keeping the duplicate and fake rates small. We focus on derivative free optimization approaches that can be applied to problems involving non-differentiable loss functions. For our studies, we consider the tracking algorithms defined within A Common Tracking Software (ACTS) framework. We test our methods using simulated data from ACTS software corresponding to the ACTS Generic detector and the ATLAS ITk detector geometries.

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1 Introduction

The reconstruction of charged particles' trajectories, commonly known as tracking, is one of the most important but computationally extensive tasks of the full event reconstruction chain. Precise and efficient measurements of charged particle trajectories are critical for the entire physics program: from reconstructing low momentum tracks in order to identify primary vertices, through using medium momentum tracks to identify heavy flavor decays and calculate jet energies, to accurately measuring high momentum messengers of electroweak particles or new physics. The underlying tracking software consists of a number of mathematically complex algorithms, each dealing with a particular tracking sub-process. These algorithms depend on a number of input parameters whose values need to be determined. Great efforts are put into optimizing these input parameters as these efforts yields both resource savings and physics performance improvements. However, it is difficult to know the configuration of these parameters that can produce the best performance. The values of these input parameters are highly dependent on the underlying tracking geometry and material configuration. They are also affected by other factors such as the number of simultaneous pp collisions known as pile-up, center-of-mass energy of collision, target physics process, etc. A different set of these parameter values is needed if underlying tracking geometry or material configuration changes. Currently, most of these optimizations are performed using the physicist's previous experience or specialized brute-force techniques. Approaches that can automatically tune these parameters for high performance are greatly desirable. Hyperparameter tuning algorithms used in machine learning offer a number of different approaches in which the optimal parameters can be learned. These approaches have the potential to reduce the effort spent in finding the configurations, as well as they can scan a larger range of parameters, allowing for potentially more efficient solutions. With the upcoming High Luminosity Large Hadron Collider (HL-LHC) upgrade, we expect more complex tracking environment which would require more refined parameter tuning.

In this study, we have explored five different optimization approaches, which include: Evolutionary Algorithms [1], Optuna Hyperparameter optimization [2], Lipschitz Optimization [3], Scikit Optimization [4] and Orion Hyperparameter tuning [5]. These approaches are described in more detail later. Initial studies on this topic were presented in [6]. This work expands on that initial work, include a systematic study of several optimization algorithms and two components of charged particle reconstruction.

2 Problem Summary

2.1 Testing Framework

We have used "A Common Tracking Software (ACTS)" [7] for our studies which is a community-driven tracking software suite consisting of high-level track reconstruction modules. ACTS provides track reconstruction algorithms within a generic, experiment-independent open-source software toolkit. It includes data structures and algorithms for performing track reconstruction in addition to a tool for fast track simulation. The algorithms are designed to be inherently thread-safe to support parallel code execution. The implementation is designed to be fully agnostic to detector technologies, and the event processing framework, so that it can be used with different experiments. A number of detector geometries has already been implemented within ACTS. Some of these are: the Belle-II Detector [8], the ATLAS ITk geometry [9], the sPHENIX Detector [10] and the LDMX Detector [11]. The underlying tracking algorithms need to be tuned as per the specific detector geometry in order to achieve ultimate physics performance. Therefore, ACTS provides ideal environment for our studies and allows us to tune same parameters for different detector geometries.

ACTS provides Generic detector geometry which is equivalent to a typical full silicon LHC detector. The Generic Detector is a hermetic detector with silicon based tracker consisting of high granularity pixel layers surrounded by outer tracking layers. A schematic of Generic detector has been shown in Figure 1. In order to perform our studies, we have used 14TeV $t\bar{t}$ dataset with pile-up = 140 and 200. The data is generated using Pythia8 [12] and simulated through Generic detector using the ACTS fast simulation algorithm. The input particles are required to have $P_T > 1\text{GeV}$ and $|\eta| < 2.5$.

Figure 1: A schematic of ACTS Generic detector used in this study. This figure is taken from [13].

2.2 Tracking Algorithms

Two different tracking algorithms from the ACTS tracking framework were considered for these studies:

- **Track finding/fitting:** The combinatorial kalman filter (CKF) [14] algorithm implemented within ACTS framework is used. CKF combines both track finding and fitting in a tree-search based algorithm. In ACTS, the main bottleneck in CKF performance is the track seeding algorithm, the algorithm that provides initial track seeds to CKF. There are around 20 parameters in track seeding algorithm. Many of these parameters are dependent on the underlying detector geometry. However, other geometry independent parameters can significantly impact track seeding performance. We have chosen to optimize the following geometry independent parameters:

1. **maxPtScattering:** Upper P_T limit for scattering angle* calculations.
2. **impactMax:** maximum value for impact parameter.
3. **deltaRMin:** minimum distance in r between two measurements within one seed.
4. **deltaRMax:** maximum distance in r between two measurements within one seed.
5. **sigmaScattering:** number of sigma used for scattering angle calculations.
6. **radLengthPerSeed:** average radiation lengths of material on the length of a seed.
7. **maxSeedsPerSpM:** number of 3-D space-points in top and bottom layers considered for compatibility with middle space-point.
8. **cotThetaMax:** maximum cotTheta angle between two space-points in a seed to be considered compatible.

- **Vertex finding/fitting:** The Adaptive Multi Vertex Finder (AMVF) [15] algorithm implemented within ACTS framework is used. AMVF performs simultaneous vertex[†] finding and multi-vertex fitting with the help of a multi-vertex fitter. We have considered the following 5 parameters of AMVF for optimization:

1. **tracksMaxZinterval:** maximum z -interval used for adding tracks to multi-vertex fit.
2. **maxVertexChi2:** maximum χ^2 value for tracks to be compatible with fitted vertex.
3. **maxMergeVertexSignificance:** maximum significance on the distance between two vertices to allow merging.
4. **minWeight:** minimum weight assigned to the track for track to be considered compatible with vertex candidate.
5. **maximumVertexContamination:** maximum vertex contamination value.

*the angle by which particle scatters after colliding with detector material.

[†]Actual proton-proton collision points.

2.3 Optimization Algorithms Explored

We have performed optimization of CKF and AMVF parameters using 5 different optimization algorithms. Optimized parameter performance corresponding to each optimization algorithm has been compared with the default parameter performance of ACTS.

Each algorithm starts with a random initial parameter configuration chosen from the input parameter range. The algorithms run for a number of iterations and, at each iteration, evaluate the score of the current parameter configuration where the score/objective function is based on the tracking algorithm performance. At each new iteration, the algorithms try to maximize or minimize the score by providing better parameter configuration using dedicated parameter estimation methods. The algorithms use different estimation methods. They typically keep track of previous configurations and scores to get better configurations at new iterations. An overview of these optimization algorithm is provided below:

- **Evolutionary Algorithms (EA) [1]:** This algorithm is based on a process analogous to the genetic evolution in living organisms. It starts by initializing a population of individuals where each individual refers to one configuration of the input parameter set. We considered a population of size 50 with each individual assigned to same initial configuration. Then, at each iteration, called a generation, the fitness of each individual is computed using a customized score function based on the tracking or vertexing algorithm performance. After the fitness evaluation, simultaneous selections and mutations are performed on randomly chosen individuals from the population such that better performing ones are more likely to stay for next generation, and worse performing ones are more likely to be removed. We used a total of 16 generations for the evolution of our parameters. This algorithm maximizes the score function and provides the configuration with the best score in the end.
- **Optuna HyperParameter Optimization (Optuna) [2]:** Optuna is an optimization framework that consists of multiple hyper-parameter sampling algorithms for parameter selection at each trial. For our studies, we have used Tree-structured Parzen Estimator (TPE) which fits one Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM) $l(x)$ to the set of parameter values associated with the best objective values, and a second GMM $g(x)$ to the remaining parameter values. It chooses the parameter value x that maximizes the quasi-likelihood ratio $\frac{l(x)}{g(x)}$.
- **Lipschitz Optimization (LIPO) [3]:** Lipschitz optimization is based on a simple parameter-free mathematical model for finding the best x that maximizes the score function $f(x)$. The key idea is to maintain a piecewise linear upper bound of $f(x)$ and use that to decide which x to evaluate at the next step. It defines the upper bound of the function $f(x)$ as $U(x) = \min_i (f(x_i) + k \cdot \|x - x_i\|_2)$ such that $U(x) \geq f(x) \forall x$, k is the Lipschitz constant. This algorithm picks new points at random and checks if the upper bound at the new point is better than the best point seen so far, and if so, it selects this point as the next step to evaluate.
- **Scikit Optimization (Skopt) [4]:** This is an optimization framework built inside Python's sklearn library [16]. It consists of a number of different parameter optimization techniques. For this study, we have used the forest_optimize algorithm which performs sequential optimization using decision trees. Skopt runs over a number of iterations and minimizes the score function to provide the best parameter configuration.
- **Orion HyperParameter Tuning (Orion) [5]:** Orion is an asynchronous framework for black-box function optimization. It can be used as a command-line interface as well as python interface. It also implements a number of different optimization methods including random search and grid search. For our studies, we have used the random search method based on the uniform probability distribution provided to the search parameters.

2.4 Performance Evaluation: Score/Objective Function

The score or objective function is one of the most important component of these optimization studies. Performance and outcome of the optimization algorithms are highly dependent on the form of score function

used. The score function is constructed using the performance metrics of the underlying tracking algorithm. Positive weights are given to quantities that we want to increase while negative weights are given to quantities that we want to decrease. Likewise, higher weights are given to more important quantities.

2.4.1 Construction of Score Function for the CKF

The important metrics determining the performance of CKF algorithm are:

- **Track Reconstruction Efficiency:** fraction of generated particles that have created at least 9 measurements on the traversed detectors and are matched with reconstructed tracks with greater than 50% probability.
- **Fake Rate:** Fraction of reconstructed tracks that are not associated with any truth particle.
- **Duplicate rate:** Fraction of reconstructed tracks associated with same truth generated particle.
- **Run Time:** Time taken in running the CKF algorithm.

Based on these performance metrics, we constructed the following score function for measuring the CKF performance for different parameter configurations:

$$\text{Score/Objective Function} = \text{Efficiency} - \left(\text{FakeRate} + \frac{\text{DuplicateRate}}{k} + \frac{\text{RunTime}}{k} \right), k = 7$$

where k is tuned for optimal tradeoff between different quantities.

2.4.2 Construction of Score Function for the AMVF

The important metrics determining the performance of AMVF algorithm are:

- **Eff_total:** Number of vertices reconstructed by AMVF algorithm out of total detector accepted vertices.
- **Eff_clean:** Number of reconstructed vertices associated to a single true generated particle out of all vertices within the detector acceptance.
- **Eff_split:** fraction of reconstructed vertices where more than one reconstructed vertices are associated with same truth particle.
- **Eff_merge:** fraction of reconstructed vertices where one reconstructed vertex is associated to more than one truth particle.
- **Eff_fake:** fraction of reconstructed vertices that are not associated to any truth particle.
- **Resolution:**

$$\frac{\Delta R}{R} = \sqrt{\sum_{\text{vertices}} \frac{((x_{\text{reco}} - x_{\text{truth}})^2 + (y_{\text{reco}} - y_{\text{truth}})^2 + (z_{\text{reco}} - z_{\text{truth}})^2)}{x_{\text{truth}}^2 + y_{\text{truth}}^2 + z_{\text{truth}}^2}}$$

Based on these performance metrics of the AMVF, the following score function has been constructed:

$$\text{Score/Objective Function} = (\text{Eff_total} + 2\text{Eff_clean}) - (\text{Eff_split} + \text{Eff_merge} + \text{Eff_fake} + \text{Resolution})$$

2.5 Integration of two frameworks

In order to perform the optimization studies, we have integrated the ACTS tracking framework with our parameter tuning framework as represented in Figure 2. The tuning framework provides input parameter values to the ACTS tracking framework. Next, the tracking algorithm runs with these values and returns the tracking performance to the tuning framework. The tuning framework computes a score based on the tracking performance and runs a parameter estimation method to evaluate new configuration of input parameters and pass it again to the ACTS framework. This continues for a number of iterations until optimization algorithm achieves satisfactory score and corresponding parameter configuration with high performance.

Figure 2: A representation of integration of ACTS tracking software framework with parameter optimization framework.

3 Results

Performance metrics for the CKF and the AMVF have been evaluated corresponding to different optimized parameter configurations and compared with the default parameter configuration.

3.1 CKF Optimization Results

The track reconstruction efficiency and duplicate rate as a function of track P_T and η for different parameter configurations is presented in Figure 3. The black solid circles correspond to the default configuration while the colored markers represent optimized configurations. A clear improvement in performance is observed with optimized parameters over all the P_T and η range, specially in high η range. The table 1 shows the improvements in terms of the average values of the metrics for different configurations. The fake rate is negligible for both the default and optimized parameters.

	Default	EA	Optuna	LIPO	Skopt	Orion
Score	69.06	78.88	75.38	77.28	77.05	77.79
Efficiency	93.6%	96.5%	96.7%	96.8%	96.5%	96.3%
Duplicate Rate	72.6%	56.8%	59.8%	60.3%	56.6%	58.7%
Fake Rate	5.56E-03%	6.2E-03%	5.2E-03%	6.8E-03%	5.7E-03%	8.8E-03%
time/event (sec)	50.2	31.1	46.8	37.2	40.2	33.9

Table 1: CKF performance metrics for default and optimized configurations.

The parameter values obtained using different optimization algorithms are found to differ from each other as can be seen in Figure 4. This variation clearly states that there are multiple local minima in the parameter

Figure 3: Comparison of CKF performance between different optimized configurations and default configuration for tracking efficiency vs. η (upper left), tracking efficiency vs. P_T (upper right), duplicate rate vs. η (lower left) and duplicate rate vs. P_T (lower right). Black solid circles represent performance corresponding to default configuration while colored markers represent optimized configurations.

space of CKF performance.

Figure 4: Parameter configurations obtained for CKF from different optimization algorithms.

3.2 AMVF Optimization Results

The number of reconstructed vertices tagged as total, clean, fake, split and merged corresponding to optimized parameters are compared with the default configuration in Figure 5. With the optimized parameters there are more clean and fewer fake vertices compared to the default. However, there is a trade-off between the total and split vertices. The position resolution in x , y and z are compared in Figure 6 and shows more centered z -resolution for optimized configurations. The parameter values obtained by different optimization algorithms are presented in Figure 7, again emphasizing on the presence of multiple local minima in AMVF space.

Figure 5: Comparison of AMVF performance between different optimized and default configurations for total (upper left), clean (upper middle), fake (upper right), split (lower left) and merged (lower right) reconstructed vertices. Black solid circles represent performance corresponding to the default configuration while colored ones represent performance corresponding to the optimized configurations.

Figure 6: Comparison of AMVF resolution in x , y and z for different optimized configurations and default configuration. Black lines represent resolution corresponding to the default configuration while colored lines represent the optimized configurations.

Figure 7: Parameter configurations obtained for the AMVF from the different optimization algorithms.

4 CKF optimization using the ATLAS ITk geometry within ACTS

We used the same optimization techniques for the ATLAS ITk geometry [17], which is shown in Figure 8, within the ACTS framework. We optimized the same CKF parameters using $t\bar{t}$ data with pile-up = 200 having $P_T > 1\text{GeV}$ and $|\eta| < 4.0$. We used the same CKF score function with $k = 5$.

Figure 8: Diagram showing ATLAS ITk geometry.

The comparison of performance for track reconstruction efficiency and duplicate rate as a function of P_T and η is shown at [18].

5 Conclusions

We have presented the implementation and performance of five different derivative-free optimization algorithms within the context of ACTS software framework and demonstrated our results using ACTS Generic detector and ATLAS ITk detector, both integrated within ACTS framework. We have performed our studies using Combinatorial Kalman Filter and Adaptive Multi Vertex Finder tracking algorithms. The performance of optimized parameters have been compared with default configuration currently present within ACTS framework. Our results show that the different optimization algorithms are able to automatically find better performing parameter configurations. These studies demonstrate the potential of such algorithms to be used for the automatic tuning of tracking algorithms to different detector geometries.

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ATLAS Inner Detector alignment towards Run 3

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ABSTRACT

The algorithm used in the alignment of the Inner Detector of the ATLAS experiment is based on the track-to-hit residual minimization in a sequence of hierarchical levels mimicking the detector assembly: from large mechanical structures to individual modules. It aims to describe the detector geometry and its changes in time as accurately as possible, such that the resolution is not degraded by an imperfect positioning of the signal hit in the track reconstruction. The ID alignment during Run 2 has proven to describe the detector geometry with a precision at the level of μm . Moreover, the hit-to-track residual minimization procedure is not sensitive to deformations of the detectors that affect the track parameters while leaving the residuals unchanged. Those geometry deformations are called weak modes. The minimization of the remaining track parameter biases and weak mode deformations has been the main target of the alignment campaign of the reprocessed Run 2 data. New analysis methods for the weak mode measurement have been therefore implemented, providing a robust geometry description, validated by a wide spectrum of quality-assessment techniques. These novelties are foreseen to be the new baseline methods for Run 3 data-taking, in which the higher luminosity would allow an almost real-time assessment of the alignment performance.

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1 Introduction

The enormous amount of data collected by the ATLAS experiment [1] at the LHC [2] in Run 2 (139 fb^{-1}) and expected for Run 3 ($\approx 280 \text{ fb}^{-1}$) requires a precise reconstruction of the emerging products from Large Hadron Collider (LHC) collisions. The Inner Detector (ID) [3] tracking system must provide an accurate measurement of the positions of the charged particles as they cross its sensors to deliver a robust and precise reconstruction of the particle trajectory. A limited knowledge of the sensor position would turn into a degraded resolution of the position measurement or, in the worst case, a wrong reconstructed position. The precise determination of the ID geometry is therefore a crucial ingredient in all measurements using track information, from Standard Model processes to new physics searches.

In Run 2, the ID consisted of Pixel Detector [4], including the insertable B-Layer [5], a semiconductor tracker (SCT) [6] and a transition tracker (TRT), summing up to 750 000 degrees of freedom necessary to uniquely define its geometry down to single sensor position and orientation. The process of determining the ID geometry is called *alignment* [7]. The alignment procedure consists in the minimization of the track-hit residuals*. The procedure is organized in a sequence of hierarchical alignment levels addressing different structures of the detector from supporting structures to positions of the single sensor modules. The geometry of large structures is frequently measured as changing significantly within the LHC fill, while the module-level alignment is much more stable in time and requires less updates. This alignment procedure is however not sensitive to correlated distortions of the detector geometry (e.g. coherent rotation of the ID barrel layers). These distortions, called *weak-modes*, are of particular relevance as they may affect the track reconstruction.

During the LHC Long Shutdown 2, the ATLAS collaboration significantly improved the existing reconstruction algorithms to cope with the challenges of Run 3 data-taking [8]. One of the most prominent novelties was the replacement of the Neural Network used in Run 2 (Run 2 NN [9]) used in the estimation of the Pixel hit position and corresponding uncertainty. This was substituted by a *Mixture Density Network* (MDN) [10, 11]. The use of MDN removed a small bias in the reconstructed Pixel hits which translated in a change in the track-hit residuals. Consequently, a new alignment of the ID was necessary, as described in Section 2 [12]. Furthermore, a new technique was developed for the assessment of weak-modes affecting the reconstructed track momentum [12] and described in Section 3.

2 Inner Detector alignment campaign

The MDN algorithm was introduced in the Run 3 software suite for the track reconstruction as it outperforms the Run 2 NN in an environment with high hit occupancy, expected in Run 3 [10, 11]. Furthermore, it is not affected by a small bias in the position reconstruction as the Run 2 NN [12]. This bias on the reconstructed track position in local- y coordinate[†] in simulated events is shown in Figure 1a.

The NN position bias was absorbed by the alignment procedure through adjusting the detector geometry in Run 2. When these alignment constants are used in the track reconstruction with the new software suite exploiting the MDN algorithm, an opposite position bias appears in data events, as shown in Figure 1b. Therefore, a dedicated alignment was needed to remove the distortion introduced by the Run 2 NN bias.

Since the position bias had a strong dependence over the track position along the beam axis, a module-level alignment was required. Since the bias showed to be stable over time, see Figure 1b, only seven sets of constants were delivered to cover the whole Run 2 data-taking of pp collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 13 \text{ TeV}$. Three sets

*A signal of a detector element generated by a crossing charged particle is called *hit*. The distance between the measured hit and the position in which the reconstructed track crosses the detector element is called *track-hit residual*.

[†]Local- y (local- x) coordinate is defined as the coordinate of the track or hit position on the sensor module in the direction of lower (higher) resolution. In this case, local- y (local- x) corresponds to the beam ($r\phi$) direction in the global coordinate system [7, 12].

Figure 1: Observed bias on the IBL track-hit residuals in the direction along the beam axis depending on the incident angle of the track into the Pixel modules. (a) The local- y residual in simulated events with the MDN algorithm (red) and Run 2 NN (gray). (b) The local- y residual in data events with the MDN algorithm (open markers) and Run2 NN (filled markers). Data events from 2107 data-taking are displayed in green, while data events from 2018 are displayed in purple. [12]

more were produced to cover special runs and heavy ion collision periods.

The alignment procedure consisted in two rounds. The first round aimed at the minimisation of the track-hit residual, that brought the mean of the residual distribution to be compatible with zero. The second round targeted the minimisation of the observed weak-modes, addressing a bias in the transverse impact parameter (d_0) and momentum. The bias in d_0 is assessed in data enriched of $Z \rightarrow \mu^+ \mu^-$ events as a function of the (η, ϕ) coordinates of the muons. These values are used as constraints for the tracks used in the following iteration of the alignment procedure in order to adjust the detector geometry to minimize such bias. This procedure is repeated until convergence of the derived alignment constants is reached. The results of these two rounds in terms of track-hit residual minimization and d_0 bias removal are shown in Figure 2: despite the first round of alignment removed the bias in the local- y position, the second round was needed to remove the d_0 bias.

As mentioned above, the second round of alignment also aimed at the minimisation of a momentum bias, specifically in the measurement of sagitta. This bias was also quantified in $Z \rightarrow \mu^+ \mu^-$ events, where the momenta of positive and negative muons are expected to be roughly the same. A sagitta bias δ_s alters the reconstructed momentum (p'_T) of a particle with respect to its original momentum (p_T) in a charge (q) dependent way according to:

$$p'_T = p_T (1 + qp_T \delta_s)^{-1} \quad (1)$$

The presence of δ_s introduces a bias in the p_T distributions of positive and negative in opposite directions, as shown in Figure 3a. The discrepancy of the mean values of the positive ($\langle p_T^+ \rangle$) and negative ($\langle p_T^- \rangle$) momentum distributions is used to estimate δ_s with:

$$\delta_s = -\frac{1}{\langle p_T \rangle} \frac{\langle p_T^+ \rangle - \langle p_T^- \rangle}{\langle p_T^+ \rangle + \langle p_T^- \rangle} \quad (2)$$

The extracted value of the measured sagitta bias is used as constrain of the tracks in the alignment iterations described above. The reduction of the sagitta bias is evident in Figure 3b. This procedure has shown not to cancel any physics-motivated momentum asymmetry in data events, as shown in Figure 3c. The forward-backward asymmetry (A_{FB}) [13] in $Z \rightarrow \mu^+ \mu^-$ events is observed also in data after the alignment procedure as in simulated events, while the “wobble” due to the presence of a sagitta bias is reduced.

Figure 2: Observed biases in the alignment procedure. Grey points indicate the initial conditions, the red points stand for the results of the first alignment round using only track-hit residual minimization, and the green points show the results of the alignment that uses constrains on the track parameters. (a) Track-hit residuals in the IBL and Pixel detectors. There are 4 group of points that correspond to the IBL, and then the 3 layers of the Pixel system. The points in each group correspond to the different ladders of modules segmented in ϕ . (b) Profile of the transverse impact parameter (d_0) versus the track η . [12]

Figure 3: Comparison of the p_T spectrum of the positive and negative muons in $Z \rightarrow \mu^+\mu^-$ events (a) before using track parameter constraints in the alignment and (b) after the alignment round with track parameter constraints. (c) Reconstructed forward-backward asymmetry(A_{FB}) using the Collins-Soper frame [13] in $Z \rightarrow \mu^+\mu^-$ events in MC and data events from 2017. The plot shows the values for the asymmetry before (blue) using track parameter constraints in the alignment and after (green) the alignment round with track parameter constraints. [12]

The performance of the alignment constants are quantified in terms of remaining biases in the track parameters using a sample of $Z \rightarrow \mu^+\mu^-$ in data. The difference in the transverse (longitudinal) impact parameter between the positive and negative muon δd_0 (δz_0) are shown in Figure 4a (Figure 4b) to be well below $1 \mu\text{m}$ ($5 \mu\text{m}$). Robust physics performances is observed during Run 2, as shown from the stable value of the di-muon reconstructed mass over time in Figure 4c.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 4: Remaining biases in the (a) transverse and (b) longitudinal impact parameter after the alignment campaign versus the time during Run 2. (c) Reconstructed mass of the di-muon system versus the time during Run 2. [12]

3 New method for sagitta bias measurement

The value of the extracted sagitta bias measured with Equation 2 is intended as *global bias*, as it affects the mean of the distribution. Local gradients of the bias over the detector are instead indicated as *relative bias*. In the past, the alignment procedure used two methods to assess them separately. The ratio of the measurements of energy in the calorimeter and momentum in the ID of electrons from Z boson decay was used to measure the global sagitta bias (E/p method) [7]. A *Mass* method [7] was instead implemented to measure the relative bias. Equation 2 provided an estimation of the global sagitta bias without the use of a

completely different sample of events and therefore preferred over the E/p method.

Since this procedure was not optimal, a new method has been developed to measure both global and relative bias simultaneously. The method is based on $Z \rightarrow \mu^+\mu^-$ events and differs from the existing *Mass* method on the choice of the figure of merit to be minimised to measure the bias. The *Mass* method is based on the minimisation of the difference between the reconstructed di-muon mass $m_{\mu\mu}$ and a reference mass ($m_{\mu\mu,0}$). From Equation 1, this difference can be written as:

$$\frac{m_{\mu\mu}^2 - m_{\mu\mu,0}^2}{m_{\mu\mu}^2} = (p_T^-\delta^- - p_T^+\delta^+) \quad (3)$$

where $\delta^{+/-}$ stands for the bias affecting the reconstruction of the positive and negative muon momenta ($p_T^{+/-}$). In case of a global bias ($\delta^+ \approx \delta^-$) in $Z \rightarrow \mu^+\mu^-$ events (in which $\langle p_T^+ \rangle \approx \langle p_T^- \rangle$), the difference $m_{\mu\mu}^2 - m_{\mu\mu,0}^2 \approx 0$. Therefore, the *Mass* method can not be sensitive to a global sagitta bias. Conversely, the width of the reconstructed di-muon mass distribution would increase in presence of a global (and/or relative) sagitta bias. The new *VarMin* method [12] exploits this behaviour and measures the sagitta bias by minimising the width of the reconstructed di-muon mass. The mathematical derivation, documented in Ref. [12] resolves in the solution of a N -dimensional system of linear equation, where N stands for the number of sections in which the detector is segmented in the (η, ϕ) coordinates. The unknown $\vec{\delta}$ consists in the values of the sagitta bias in each section of the detector that minimise the overall width of the di-muon mass distribution.

The measured sagitta values on the same set of data events using the *VarMin* and *Mass* methods are shown in Figure 5a and 5b, respectively. The results are almost identical as indicated by the high correlation factor shown in Figure 5c. This result also indicates that the level of the global sagitta bias is almost negligible after the alignment campaign as *VarMin* method is expected to be sensitive to it, while the *Mass* method is not. The value of the sagitta bias during Run 2 data-taking is shown in Figure 6, showing to be below 0.1 TeV^{-1} over the detector for the whole Run 2 with a mean value (i.e. global bias) around 0.02 TeV^{-1} .

Figure 5: Measured sagitta bias (η, ϕ) maps from $Z \rightarrow \mu^+\mu^-$ data events from 2018 data-taking as obtained with the *Mass* (a) and *VarMin* (b) methods. The detector is split in 24×24 uniformly spaced (η, ϕ) sectors. (c) Comparison of the sagitta bias as computed with the *Mass* and *VarMin* methods. Each point has as coordinates the computed sagitta bias with each method for the same (η, ϕ) sector. [12]

Eventually, the *VarMin* method outperforms the *Mass* method in terms of execution time. Both methods use iterations over the set of events in order to converge to the final measured value of sagitta bias. As shown in Figure 7, while the *Mass* method needs almost six iterations to obtain negligible corrections, the *VarMin* method converges in three iterations, drastically reducing the execution time.

Figure 6: The sagitta bias on tracks, measured in $Z \rightarrow \mu^+ \mu^-$ events following the VarMin method and for the data from the Run 2. [12]

Figure 7: Corrections of the sagitta bias per iteration using (a) *Mass* and (b) *VarMin* methods. Each line shows the sagitta bias computed for a given (η, ϕ) cell. For the sake of clarity, only a fraction of the total number of cells are drawn: just the 24 cells of the 12th row ($\phi \approx 0$) in Figure. 5. The line colors are used to distinguish each cell. [12]

4 Conclusions

The accurate determination of the geometry of the ATLAS tracking system plays an important role both in high-precision measurements of the Standard Model as well as in searches of new physics. A poor knowledge of the position and orientation of the detector elements affects the track reconstruction and ultimately physics measurement. The ATLAS alignment procedure of the Inner Detector has proven to deliver a robust description of the detector geometry and minimise the bias on the track parameters during Run 2.

The ATLAS reconstruction software suite has been renewed during the Long Shutdown 2 in order to improve the performances of the implemented algorithm in preparation of Run 3. The inclusion of a new algorithm (MDN) for the hit position estimation induced a movement of the track-hit residuals, calling for a new alignment campaign. New alignment constants covering the whole Run 2 data-taking have been delivered to be used within the new reconstruction software suite for improved analysis of Run 2 dataset and future combination with Run 3 data. The delivered description of the geometry has proven to minimise the biases on the track parameters down to a negligible level.

Weak-modes are coherent deformation of the detector geometry that are not caught by the alignment

procedure. Methods based on resonance decays are used to estimate them and used as input for the alignment algorithm to adjust the geometry to minimise them. A new method for the measurement of charge-dependent momentum biases (sagitta biases) is implemented, the *VarMin* method. This method outperforms the existing *Mass* method as it is sensitive to global biases and requires almost half the execution time to provide consistent results. This improvement is expected to be of a great importance in Run 3 of the LHC as it is planned to be used in the alignment iterations, so that a quick, automatic and accurate minimization of the sagitta bias during the alignment iterations will be possible.

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LHCb's Forward Tracking algorithm for the Run 3 CPU-based online track-reconstruction sequence

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ABSTRACT

In Run 3 of the LHC, the LHCb experiment faces very high data rates containing beauty and charm hadron decays. Thus the task of the trigger is not to select any beauty and charm events, but to select those containing decays interesting for the LHCb physics programme. LHCb has therefore implemented a real-time data processing strategy to trigger directly on reconstructed events. The first stage of the purely software-based trigger is implemented on GPUs performing a partial event reconstruction. In the second stage of the software trigger, the full, offline-quality event reconstruction is performed on CPUs, with a crucial part being track reconstruction, balancing track finding efficiency, fake track rate and event throughput. LHCb's CPU-based track reconstruction sequence for Run 3 is presented, highlighting the "Forward Tracking", which is the algorithm that reconstructs trajectories of charged particles traversing all of LHCb's tracking detectors. To meet event throughput requirements, the "Forward Tracking" uses SIMD instructions in several core parts of the algorithm, such as the Hough transform and the cluster search. These changes led to an improvement of the algorithm's event throughput by 60%.

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1 Introduction

During Run 3 of the LHC, LHCb will take data with new tracking detectors, new readout electronics and a new, purely software-based trigger [1, 2]. These upgrades to the LHCb experiment are necessary to efficiently process the data from 30 MHz of non-empty pp bunch crossings at the LHCb design luminosity of $\mathcal{L} = 2 \times 10^{33} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ producing millions of beauty and charm hadrons per second. At these signal rates a hardware trigger is not anymore able to efficiently reduce the amount of data recorded as its bandwidth is already fully saturated by hadronic B decays [2, 3]. This problem is solved by a purely software-based trigger system that analyses and selects events in real time, *i.e.* performing the full, offline-quality event reconstruction. The most crucial part of the reconstruction sequence is the charged track reconstruction. The Run 3 LHCb detector employs three tracking detector technologies, a hybrid pixel detector (VELO, Vertex Locator) surrounding the pp interaction region [4], a silicon microstrip detector (UT, Upstream Tracker) [5] placed upstream of a dipole magnet and three stations of large-area scintillating fibre detectors (SciFi) [5] located downstream of the magnet. The whole LHCb detector is a single-arm forward spectrometer covering the pseudorapidity range $2 < \eta < 5$. The software trigger is split into two parts, the first stage is the *High Level Trigger 1* which performs a partial event reconstruction on GPUs [6–9], the second stage, called *High Level Trigger 2* (HLT2), reconstructs the full event using CPUs and selects decay candidates which are then sent to permanent storage for further analysis [10]. The full HLT2 event reconstruction includes charged track reconstruction, track parameter estimation using a Kalman filter, hadron, electron and muon identification and photon reconstruction. The HLT2 charged track reconstruction sequence is outlined in Sec. 2. One of the algorithms in this sequence is the *Forward Tracking*, highlighted in Sec. 3.

2 CPU-based charged track reconstruction in HLT2

LHCb defines five different track types described in Ref. [11]. Among these are VELO, T and Long tracks. VELO and T tracks have hits only in the VELO and SciFi detectors, respectively, while Long tracks traverse the whole tracking system and are required to have hits in both, the VELO and SciFi detectors, and can optionally have hits in the UT detector. Because they use all tracking detectors, Long tracks have the best momentum resolution and are therefore most used for physics analysis.

In HLT2, two independent algorithms reconstruct Long tracks, the *Forward Tracking* and the *Matching*, each of which employs a different track reconstruction method. The Forward Tracking and Matching both take VELO tracks as input, the reconstruction of which is done by the VELO Tracking described in Ref. [12]. The Matching further takes T tracks, reconstructed by the Hybrid Seeding algorithm described in Ref. [13], and matches them to VELO tracks which consequently become Long tracks. To find the correct combinations of VELO and T tracks, the Matching evaluates a multilayer perceptron trained on simulation and decides whether there is a match depending on the response of the neural network. The Forward Tracking is described in Sec. 3. Both algorithms are designed to find as many Long tracks as possible, which leads to a large overlap between the two sets of found Long tracks. In Run 2, this redundancy was accepted and resolved by selecting Long tracks according to their quality after applying a Kalman filter. This procedure increased the reconstruction efficiency [14]. In Run 3, however, the timing constraints posed by the real-time analysis trigger strategy favour avoiding redundancy. This is achieved by the reconstruction sequence shown in Fig. 1a. First the VELO tracking and Hybrid Seeding are run. The Matching then combines VELO tracks with T tracks. Residual VELO tracks, that could not be matched, are given to the Forward Tracking as input, which tries to create a Long Track using only SciFi hits that are not already taken into account by a Long Track found by the Matching.

The event throughput of the HLT2 reconstruction sequence is shown in Fig. 1b, including contributions from the Kalman filter and particle identification. Avoiding the aforementioned redundancy in the Long Track reconstruction, the HLT2 reconstruction sequence reaches more than 500 events per second and computing node, with the Forward Tracking not being a throughput-dominating component. More performance metrics such as reconstruction efficiencies of the HLT2 charged track reconstruction can be found in Ref. [15].

Figure 1: The Run 3 Long Track reconstruction sequence is shown in (a). Colours indicate that objects belong together. The throughput contribution of different components in the HLT2 reconstruction sequence is shown in (b) [16]. RICH, Calorimeter and Protoparticles refer to particle identification, the Track Fit is a Kalman filter. The Hybrid Seeding algorithm is called Seed Tracking here.

3 HLT2 Forward Tracking

The goal of the Forward Tracking is to find a forward extension of a given VELO track in the SciFi tracker and to estimate a preliminary* momentum of this Long Track. The SciFi detector consists of three stations, each with four layers of scintillating fibre modules. Therefore, the forward extension is a set of ten to twelve SciFi hits, with each hit belonging to a different layer of the SciFi detector. The hits the Forward Tracking algorithm searches for form a slightly curved trajectory that is compatible with originating from a VELO track. The line is curved in the xz - and yz -projection[†] because of fringe magnetic fields within the SciFi stations. The central problem to solve is finding the single correct combination of a VELO track with SciFi hits among the many possible extensions, or finding that no such combination is present, while keeping the reconstruction efficiency and event throughput high and the fake track fraction low. The complexity scales with the number of input tracks and the total number of hits recorded by the SciFi detector. Typical events with inelastic pp collisions lead to $\mathcal{O}(10^2)$ VELO tracks and $\mathcal{O}(10^3)$ SciFi hits. The Forward Tracking uses a method similar to a Hough transform [17] to efficiently and robustly spot hits forming the line pattern matching a VELO track. The following Sections 3.1-3.3 describe important components of the algorithm performed on individual input tracks.

3.1 SciFi hit selection

Starting from a state vector $(x, y, \frac{\partial x}{\partial z}, \frac{\partial y}{\partial z}, \frac{q}{p})$ containing the position, slopes and so far unknown charge q and momentum p at the end of the VELO, *i.e.* a VELO track, the Forward Tracking defines a polynomial $P(\frac{\partial x}{\partial z}, \frac{\partial y}{\partial z}, p)$ parameterising the propagation of the track in the xz -plane through the magnetic field down to the SciFi layers. As the momentum and charge are not known yet, this parameterisation is used to calculate x_{\min} and x_{\max} positions for each layer assuming a minimum reconstructible track momentum p_{\min} , *e.g.* $p_{\min} = 1.5$ GeV, and both possible charges. Only SciFi hits with $x \in [x_{\min}, x_{\max}]$ are selected for further processing, reducing the complexity of the problem. The determination of this hit search window by a polynomial is computationally cheap and therefore preferred over numerically solving the equations of motion

*The best momentum estimate is obtained by applying a Kalman filter to the track found bound by the Forward Tracking, using the preliminary momentum estimate as input.

[†]The LHCb coordinate system is a right-handed system with positive z running along the beamline from the interaction point into the detector and positive y pointing upward.

in the magnetic field in a real-time application.

3.2 Simplified particle trajectory

Similarly to the parameterisation used to define the hit search window (Sec. 3.1), the Forward Tracking defines a simplified particle trajectory by treating the magnet as an optical lens as described in Ref. [18]. Just like the model of light rays refracted by a thin lens, the particle's movement in the xz -plane through the magnetic field is modelled by a straight line that gets a kick at the centre of the magnetic field and propagates further as a straight line with a different slope. Once a single hit (x, z) downstream of the magnet is taken into account, predicting the x coordinate at a given z position is a simple linear extrapolation within the model. Deviations from this model occur because of fringe magnetic fields that reach into the SciFi detector and are corrected for by parameterising the effect using polynomials as described in Ref. [19].

3.3 Hough-like transform

The main component of the Forward Tracking applies a map-reduce pattern inspired by the Hough transform to sieve out sets of SciFi hits that do not form a matching extension to the VELO track.

The x positions of SciFi hits selected by the search window described in Sec. 3.1 are mapped to a reference plane at a fixed z position. All hits' x positions at the reference plane are calculated using the simplified trajectory introduced in Sec. 3.2 and filled into a histogram. The histogram counts the number of unique SciFi detector layers that are present among the hits in one bin. This way, hits that do not qualify as an extension to the VELO track form a flat distribution, while hits that match the VELO track accumulate in a few bins as depicted in Fig. 2. Subsequently, the histogram is scanned for small groups of neighbouring bins exceeding a layer-count threshold, thus reducing the large set of hits from within the search window to none, one or several small sets of hits, which become candidates for the VELO track extension. The found hit sets are then cleaned from outliers, fitted using a third-order polynomial function and further selected according to the fit result. The remaining candidates are promoted to Long tracks and their charge and momentum are estimated.

Figure 2: Sketch of the key components of the Forward Tracking. Starting from a VELO track (blue), a smallest-momentum hit search window is calculated (black dashed line). The x positions of hits in the twelve SciFi detector layers (three stations T1, T2 and T3 with four layers each in light blue) are projected to the reference plane (orange) using a simplified track model (not shown here). The rightmost part of the figure shows the histogram counting the number of unique SciFi detector layers depending on the projected x positions. Hits belonging to the VELO track are shown in green, and other hits are in red.

3.4 Event throughput optimisation

Optimisation of tracking algorithms usually deals with a trade-off between event throughput, track reconstruction efficiency and fake track fraction. However, the capabilities of modern CPUs offer new opportunities to improve the throughput of an algorithm without compromising the other two metrics.

The throughput performance of the Forward Tracking is optimised by exploiting data-level parallelism using the vector registers of the CPU. These registers contain the operands for a single CPU instruction that acts on multiple data points at once (SIMD, single instruction multiple data). For this to work efficiently, an appropriate choice of data structures is crucial. Therefore, information about SciFi detector hits is stored in a structure-of-arrays layout, *i.e.* all x positions are arranged successively in memory. This enables fast data loading to SIMD registers as well as fast storing of the computed result. The Forward Tracking mostly applies this form of parallelism in the computationally expensive map-reduce part explained in Sec. 3.3. The mapping of hits' x positions to the reference plane is done for multiple hits at once using single instructions and likewise the threshold scan reducing the data is performed on several histogram bins in parallel. Using the Advanced Vector Extensions 2 (AVX2), SIMD registers hold 256 bits equal to eight single precision floating point or integer numbers that then can be processed in parallel. Adapting the Forward Tracking algorithm to efficiently use AVX2 improves its event throughput by 60% without losses regarding reconstruction efficiency or fake track fraction.

3.5 Reconstruction performance

The Long track reconstruction efficiency achieved by the Forward Tracking is shown in Fig. 3. A high efficiency is particularly important for studies of charm and beauty decays with many final state particles in which track reconstruction inefficiencies have a large impact on the total decay reconstruction efficiency. The integrated efficiency for reconstructing hadrons and muons originating from a B meson is around 90%, while tracks with a momentum higher than 10 GeV reach more than 95% efficiency. Electrons are in general harder to reconstruct with high efficiency as they lose energy predominantly via bremsstrahlung when interacting with the detector material which unpredictably alters their trajectory. This effect is particularly visible in Fig. 3b in the high pseudorapidity region in which particles traverse more material. It is also this region that

Figure 3: Long track reconstruction efficiency of tracks reconstructed by the Forward Tracking algorithm versus momentum (a) and pseudorapidity (b) for reconstructible electrons and non-electron particles from B decays (empty blue and filled black circles, respectively) within $2 < \eta < 5$ [16]. The underlying histograms show the corresponding distributions of the reconstructible particles. Being reconstructible requires a minimum number of hits in different tracking detectors as described in Ref. [11].

exhibits the highest fake track fraction, as shown in Fig. 4b, partly because of increased multiple scattering and hadronic interactions due to the material, but even more because of the higher SciFi hit density in

the very forward direction leading to more possible random hit combinations. Fig. 4a shows the fake track fraction in dependence of the fake track momentum. The integrated fake track fraction coming from the Forward Tracking amounts to 15%. It is afterwards reduced by applying a Kalman Filter and evaluation of a fake track classifier.

Figure 4: Fake track fraction of Long tracks reconstructed by the Forward Tracking algorithm as a function of fake track momentum (a) and pseudorapidity (b) [16].

4 Conclusion

The Forward Tracking is one of the algorithms finding Long tracks in LHCb's Run 3 HLT2 reconstruction sequence. To avoid the redundancy in Long track finding with the Matching algorithm and hence to improve the throughput of HLT2, the Forward Tracking is only run on residual VELO tracks and SciFi hits. Including the Kalman filter and particle identification algorithms, the HLT2 reconstruction sequence reaches its goal of an event throughput of more than 500 events per second and computing node. The Forward Tracking uses a method similar to the Hough transform to recognise the line patterns left by particles traversing the SciFi detector. With this, it reaches more than 90% reconstruction efficiency for tracks originating from a B meson decay and a fake track fraction of 15%. Hence, the HLT2 reconstruction sequence and the Forward Tracking are well prepared for data taking during Run 3 of the LHC.

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Track Finding and Neural Network-Based Primary Vertex Reconstruction with FPGAs for the Upgrade of the CMS Level-1 Trigger System

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ABSTRACT

The CMS experiment will be upgraded to take advantage of the rich and ambitious physics opportunities provided by the High Luminosity LHC. Part of this upgrade will see the first level (Level-1) trigger use charged particle tracks from the full outer silicon tracker as an input for the first time. The reconstruction of these tracks begins with on-detector hit suppression, identifying hits (stubs) from charged particles with transverse momentum (p_T) > 2 GeV within the tracker modules themselves. This reduces the hit rate by one order of magnitude with 15,000 stubs being produced per bunch crossing. Dedicated off-detector electronics using high performance FPGAs are used to find track candidates at 40 MHz using a road-search based pattern matching step. These are then passed to a combinatorial Kalman filter that performs the track fit for $O(200)$ tracks. This overall track finding algorithm is described, as is the ongoing work developing the track fitting firmware and a boosted decision tree approach to track quality estimation. The tracks are used in a variety of ways in downstream algorithms, in particular primary vertex finding in order to identify the hard scatter in an event and separate the primary interaction from an additional 200 simultaneous interactions. A novel approach to regress the primary vertex position and to reject tracks from additional soft interactions uses a lightweight 1000 parameter end-to-end neural network. This neural network possesses simultaneous knowledge of all stages in the reconstruction chain, which allows for end-to-end optimisation. The improved performance of this network versus a baseline approach in the primary vertex regression and track-to-vertex classification is shown. A quantised and pruned version of the neural network has been deployed on an FPGA to match the stringent timing and computing requirements of the Level-1 Trigger. Finally, integration tests between the track finder and vertexing firmware are shown using prototype hardware

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1 Introduction

The Compact Muon Solenoid (CMS) experiment [1] is one of two general purpose detectors situated around the Large Hadron Collider (LHC). The LHC provides CMS with a 40 MHz bunch crossing rate and an average of 25 simultaneous proton-proton interactions per bunch crossing (pileup). At this bunch crossing rate the amount and bandwidth of data produced by CMS is too large to process and store. Therefore a two-stage trigger [2] is used to select events based on their physics potential. The first hardware-based trigger, Level-1, was originally designed to make decisions on lower granularity calorimeter and muon system data with a fixed latency $< 4 \mu\text{s}$ and output rate of 100 kHz. This is followed by a CPU farm high level trigger with an output rate of 1 kHz for storage and offline analysis.

By 2029 the LHC will have completed its High Luminosity (HL) [3] upgrades which will increase its instantaneous luminosity by three times, this will provide 3000 fb^{-1} of integrated luminosity for the general purpose LHC experiments by the end of the 2030s. While this increased luminosity aids searches for new rare process physics and precision standard model measurements it poses a large challenge to the current detectors and triggering systems with pileup (PU) increasing to a maximum of 200.

To maintain physics sensitivity with the HL-LHC and exploit advancements in both detector and computing hardware the CMS experiment is being upgraded [4], including the trigger system [5]. The high pileup would see current Level-1 accept rates increase to 4MHz, so in order to reduce this to a new rate of 750 kHz, silicon tracker tracks will be used at Level-1 for the first time. This necessitates a new outer tracker for CMS which will stream data to a new all-FPGA trigger system. The use of these tracker tracks also allows for the identification of the hard scatter, or primary vertex, in an event leading to the separation of the primary interaction from additional pileup interactions reducing the impact of background pileup on downstream triggering algorithms and maintaining controllable trigger rates.

2 The CMS Phase-2 Upgrade

The Phase-2 upgrade of CMS is a wide program of replacements and upgrades to the detector. Including a replacement of the endcap calorimetry to give high-granularity 4D shower reconstruction, higher η coverage in the muon systems and upgraded electronics throughout the detector subsystems. The all-silicon tracker will be replaced with a higher radiation tolerant, higher η coverage tracker [6], schematically shown in Fig. 1. The outer tracker will be used as input to the Level-1 trigger as the inner tracker data bandwidth is too high and the data too difficult to extract to process in the fixed trigger latency. In order to reduce the data bandwidth to within manageable levels, new " p_T " modules [7] for the outer tracker have also been designed consisting of two closely spaced layers (1.6 - 4.0 mm) of silicon and on-module correlation logic giving a tuneable p_T cut on charged particle tracks of 2-3 GeV. Due to this on-detector p_T cut, the number of pairs of hits or 'stubs' being passed to the Level-1 trigger (at the full 40 MHz) is reduced by a factor of 10 compared to no p_T cut. This will still see $\approx 15,000$ stubs per bunch crossing needing to be processed, matched to charged particle trajectories and fitted all within $4 \mu\text{s}$ to meet the latency requirements of the Level-1 trigger.

The Phase-2 upgrade of the Level-1 trigger will see the total rate being increased to 750 kHz with a longer latency per event of $< 12.5 \mu\text{s}$ due to improvements to on-detector buffers. This, combined with the use of state-of-the-art FPGAs, will see more complex algorithms being used at Level-1. With access to tracker tracks it will become possible to perform particle flow reconstruction which allows the Level-1 trigger to reconstruct full events with all detector subsystems. However, the use of these algorithms is highly dependent on the ability of the trigger to reduce the impact of pileup. The most important tool for reducing this background pileup is the reconstruction of the primary vertex (PV) in an event. Tracks will be used to locate the hard scatter in an event which other trigger objects can be associated to, such as the tracks themselves or energy deposits in the calorimeters, thus allowing for the vetoing of additional energy in the detector from pileup. Another key part of the upgraded trigger is the use of machine learning techniques, these are particularly suitable for finding optimal solutions on reduced inputs that the environment of the trigger provides. This allows for a reduction in the lengthy algorithmic and firmware development process of more traditional approaches.

Figure 1: A slice in r - z of the Phase-2 CMS tracker. In green and yellow the inner tracker with increased η coverage up to 3.8 and in red and blue the new outer tracker consisting of p_T modules with a tuneable p_T cut and an η coverage < 2.4 .

3 Track Finding

In order to reconstruct tracks from collections of hits or ‘stubs’ from the detectors p_T modules a two-part ‘hybrid’ algorithm formed of two previously demonstrated algorithms [8],[9] will be used. The first part is a tracklet pattern recognition step used to form track candidates from pairs of seed stubs, and secondly, a combinatorial Kalman Filter (KF) fits the tracks and calculates the helix parameters. The algorithm follows these main steps:

- Tracklet seeds are formed from stub doublets in specific combinations of adjacent layers and disks.
- Tracklet helix parameters are calculated from the seed using the constraint that the track originated from the interaction region.
- The tracklet is projected to the remaining layers and disks and stubs are matched to it within a set window.
- Duplicate tracklets are merged which share three or more layers and disks.
- A combinatorial Kalman Filter seeded from the tracklet candidate has associated stubs iteratively added to it, updating the KF state and covariance matrices. This selects the best stub combination for the track and calculates the p_T , η , ϕ and z_0 (the track’s distance from the beamspot, along the beam line).

This track finding algorithm performs well with a $> 95\%$ efficiency for all tracks $|\eta| < 2.4$, $p_T > 2$ GeV. While this has been successfully demonstrated in emulation the firmware development is ongoing with key sections of the track finding chain being tested in hardware. Due to the geometry of the CMS tracker a $\cosh(|\eta|)$ relationship between transverse impact parameter (z_0) resolution and η can be seen in Fig. 2, this relationship is important when designing vertex finding and association algorithms where the resolution of the tracks themselves dominate the achievable resolution of a vertex. Also shown is the fraction of non-genuine (or fake) tracks (those not associated to real tracking particles as defined in Monte Carlo simulations based on stub matching) as a function of p_T . These fakes are produced when combinations of stubs that do not originate from a real charged particle are combined by the track finding. As these represent a large fraction ($\approx 10\%$) of tracks at higher p_T strategies for reducing the number of fakes is important to not influence downstream trigger performance where algorithms typically rely on high p_T signatures.

Figure 2: Track z_0 residuals are calculated in a number of η bins and the 68% and 90% quantiles are shown for each bin, also shown is the expected $\cosh(|\eta|)$ fit.

Figure 3: Non-genuine fraction of reconstructed tracks (number of non-genuine tracks / total number of reconstructed tracks) for multiple p_T bins showing a relative increase at higher p_T s.

3.1 Track Quality

In order to reduce the number of non-genuine tracks the quality of the track fit can be used. The KF produces uncertainties in the $r - \phi$ and $r - z$ planes that can be combined to give a $\chi_{r\phi}^2$ and χ_{rz}^2 fit as well as an additional χ_{bend}^2 which depends on the detector geometry. Together, these fitting parameters, as well as additional constraints on the number of stubs a track has been formed from, can be used to impose quality criteria on tracks. These have been shown to be useful in highly p_T sensitive calculations such as track-based E_T^{miss} where E_T^{miss} trigger thresholds can be reduced by up to 50% by imposing strict quality cuts on tracks.

While a single working point per individual algorithm performs well it is more useful for downstream users to have flexible working points based on the overall 'quality' of a track which can be derived from various track features. For this reason, Boosted Decision Trees (BDTs) were trained using track helix and fit parameters to identify real versus fake tracks in a binary classification task [10]. These BDTs outperform the discrimination power of a single tuned cut as shown in Fig. 4 while also providing a flexible threshold for multiple downstream algorithms.

These BDTs were designed to be lightweight with a tree depth of 3 and with 60 iterations due to firmware constraints in the Level-1 trigger. Custom HDL was used to give BDTs with $< 1\%$ resource usage on the target FPGA (Xilinx UltraScale+ VU13P) used for the track finding algorithm and with a total latency of 33 ns running at 250 MHz making them a viable option for track quality assessment.

4 Vertex Finding

The primary vertex is the location along the beam line of the hard proton-proton scatter in an event. Offline, it is estimated as the reconstructed vertex with the highest track $\sum p_T^2$ [11]. It is important to locate this vertex at Level-1 as it reduces the impact of pileup on downstream algorithms. When other trigger objects are associated to the vertex the trigger can have cleaner energy sums, better lepton isolation and a reduction in the number of objects being passed to downstream algorithms making them computationally feasible in the strict latency requirements.

Figure 4: Track finding efficiency versus non-genuine fraction for the track-based E_T^{miss} cut on χ^2 and the BDT approach for track quality estimation.

4.1 Baseline Approach

The baseline approach to vertex finding [5] creates a histogram in z_0 of all tracks weighted by their p_T . This histogram consists of 256 bins in a z_0 range of -15,15 cm. A three bin window is then passed across the histogram in order to find the three consecutive bins with the highest total weight. The centre of the middle of these three bins is returned as the primary vertex. This method has been implemented in firmware and run in hardware with a latency of 81 ns at 360 MHz. There are some key issues with this method; firstly, there is no accounting for the high p_T fakes as shown in Fig. 3. These can appear with other pileup tracks as high p_T clusters in the histogram returning a fake vertex. Secondly, there is no correction for the degradation in z_0 resolution in high η tracks as shown in Fig. 2 which leads to a worse resolution of the PV.

However, to associate tracks to this vertex and filter out PU tracks, an η dependent window in z_0 is used. This is reasonably effective with a 91% rate of correctly assigning PV tracks to the vertex and a 10% rate of assigning fake or PU tracks to the vertex. This is a fast method but does not take into account the quality of the tracks which can degrade the performance as well as other track features that could better discriminate pileup from PV tracks.

5 End-to-End Vertex Finding

By taking into account multiple track features when weighting the baseline approach's histogram it is possible to improve the performance. Additional weightings such as $\frac{1}{\eta^2}$ (as an approximation of the fit in Fig. 2) can be shown to give a 10% improvement in the core of the vertex error residual. Cuts on the output of the track quality BDT shown in Section 3.1 can give a 40% improvement in the tails of the residual. The combination of these features is non-trivial so an iteratively learnt approach using a dense neural network was employed. Additionally, it was found that allowing for a more complex pattern recognition of the peak in the weighted

histogram improved performance when replacing the baseline’s three bin window with a 1D convolutional neural network. Finally, the track-to-vertex association also benefits from more complex track features aside from η and distance to the vertex so another dense neural network was used for this binary classification task. While the regression of the primary vertex is an important target for developing this algorithm, the association of tracks to this vertex is ultimately the most important information being passed to downstream physics algorithms. For this reason, an end-to-end approach was adopted which uses both an event-level primary vertex regression and track-level track-to-vertex association that are learnt simultaneously allowing the histogram weighting and peak pattern finder to be optimised for the track-to-vertex association as well.

5.1 Architecture and Back Propagation

The network has three main parts as shown in Fig. 5 with the weight network feeding into a differentiable histogram leading to the 1D convolutional pattern recognition and then outputting to a differentiable ArgMax to regress the PV position with a pseudo-Huber loss function. The difference in position between vertex and track z_0 along with other features is then used to perform the track-to-vertex association with a binary cross entropy loss function.

In order to perform back propagation and allow the weight network to learn from both the PV regression and track-to-vertex association losses, custom histogram and ArgMax layers were written. The histogram with bin h_i is filled with track z_0 , weighted by weight w which is a learnt function of track features:

$$h_i = \sum_{j=0}^{tracks} \delta(j \in \text{bin } i) w(p_{T,j}, \eta_j, MVA_j) \quad (1)$$

resulting in the following gradients

$$\frac{\partial h_i}{\partial z_0} = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\partial h_i}{\partial w} = \sum_{j=0}^{tracks} \delta(j \in \text{bin } i) \quad (2)$$

which are implemented as custom TensorFlow operations.

The ArgMax layer has an input of a vector x (in this case the convolved histogram) of N elements and is defined as:

$$\sum_{i=0}^N i \frac{e^{x_i/T}}{\sum_{j=0}^N e^{x_j/T}} \quad (3)$$

where T is a tuned hyperparameter of the network which allows this layer to return an approximate one-hot encoding of the convolved histogram.

5.2 Performance

This end-to-end approach outperforms the baseline approach. Firstly, it sees a 55% reduction in the tails of the residual due to better filtering of fake clusters caused by high p_T fake tracks, this is shown in Fig. 6. Secondly, in the track-to-vertex association the end-to-end approach better discriminates PV tracks from PU and fakes with a rate of 96% at the same 10% false positive rate as shown in the receiver operating characteristic curve in Fig. 7. It is also able to pass down a flexible threshold for downstream algorithms to use as opposed to a set working point given by a traditional cut-based approach.

Figure 5: End-to-end network architecture showing the three distinct networks in colour as well as the position of the histogram and ArgMax layers.

Figure 6: True PV - Reconstructed PV for the Baseline and NN approaches. NN refers to the floating point approach while QNN is the quantised approach described in Section 5.3

Figure 7: Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve for the Baseline and NN approaches to track-to-vertex association. Shown as true positive rate versus false positive rate.

5.3 Implementation

As this end-to-end approach uses the same building blocks as the baseline approach, much of the baseline approach's firmware can be reused and individual parts of the network can be inserted. For this reason the network is split into three individual parts, the weight, pattern and association networks, shown in Fig. 5. These are run through the hls4ml [12] tool that generates High Level Synthesis (HLS) firmware for each network which are then wired within the existing baseline approach.

Due to the overall parallelism of the system architecture of the Level-1 trigger the weight and association networks that operate at a track-level are to be implemented multiple times. This makes the small resource usage and low latency of these parts of the network critical. Two approaches were used in order to reduce the network size. Firstly, quantized aware training restricts the bitwidths of learnt weights and biases in the training phase using the QKeras package [13]. This allows fine tuned setting of fixed bitwidths for each layer thus reducing the total amount of FPGA resources needed per operation in the network while maintaining the performance of the network. Secondly, network pruning [14], the technique of iteratively removing close to zero weights over multiple training cycles, is used to reduce the total number of operations needed by the network, this is particularly useful for reducing the number of multiplications required at inference time.

The resource usage of a Xilinx UltraScale+ VU9P running at 360 MHz is shown in Table 1. Both floating point and a quantised and pruned version of the network are shown demonstrating the large reduction in resource usage especially in reducing the Digital Signal Processor (DSP) usage which is a limiting factor in these FPGAs. The performance of these two version of the network are shown in Figs. 6 and 7 where little difference is seen between the NN and QNN.

6 Integration Testing

In order to validate the functioning of the upgraded Level-1 trigger, testing of algorithms on their target hardware is required. Custom carrier boards for specific FPGAs were designed for different parts of the trigger with the track finding being performed on the Apollo [16] board and much of the Level-1 trigger using either the Serenity [15] or APx boards. Both the boards and algorithms have reached a level of maturity that

Network	Latency (ns)	Initiation Interval (ns)	LUTs %	DSPs %	BRAMs %	FFs %
NN (Q) Weights	22 (14)	2.7 (2.7)	2.52 (0.90)	19.98 (0.00)	0.00 (0.00)	0.72 (0.36)
NN (Q) Pattern	58 (42)	51 (35)	4.27 (4.43)	3.74 (0.00)	5.28 (5.28)	3.22 (3.15)
NN (Q) Assoc.	30 (25)	2.7 (2.7)	0.54 (7.92)	107.64 (0.54)	0.00 (0.00)	2.70 (2.34)
Baseline	44	2.7	2.40	0.00	1.90	1.40

Table 1: Resource usage and latencies of a Xilinx VU9P running at 360 MHz for the floating point Neural Network (labelled NN) and the quantised and pruned version (labelled Q and in parenthesis in the table). Shown are total resource usage for all replications of the weight and association networks, corresponding to the number of parallel track streams used in the Level-1 trigger (the pattern network is only implemented once). Also included is the baseline approach, the NN approaches are additional to these resources and latency as they use existing parts of the baseline firmware. These resource usages are estimates from a Vivado synthesis of the networks and the latencies are from a C-Simulation of the RTL logic using ModelSim.

allows for system integration testing to begin. Single board tests of parts of the track finding chain have been completed with sub sections of the tracklet algorithm being interfaced with the Kalman Filter and compared to software emulation. Single board tests have also been performed with both the baseline and end-to-end approaches to vertex finding. Another part of these tests is the integration of subsystems. High speed 25 GB/s fibre optic connections are used to transmit the output of one algorithm to another running on separate hardware. This has led to a demonstration of the track finding output step outputting tracks to the vertex finding and a vertex being recorded in output buffers, an algorithmic overview is shown in Fig. 8 and the corresponding hardware setup for this is shown in Fig. 9. This not only allows for the hardware boards themselves to be tested but also the performance of algorithms in more ‘real-world’ scenarios with data being received over fibre optics.

Figure 8: Overview of algorithms and links used for board-to-board integration testing of the track finder to vertex finder.

Figure 9: Hardware demonstrator of the track finding output running on the board on the left outputting tracks over five fibre optic links to the vertex finding running on the board on the right where the vertex is calculated and stored in buffers.

7 Conclusion

The HL-LHC upgrade program will expand the physics reach of the CMS experiment and with key upgrades to both the detector and trigger system it will maintain and expand its physics capabilities despite the high pileup conditions. An improved outer tracker using specialised modules with a tuneable on-detector p_T cut will allow tracker tracks to be reconstructed at the Level-1 trigger for the first time. A tracklet pattern recognition followed by combinatorial Kalman Filter will be used to reconstruct tracks within $4 \mu\text{s}$ and an additional BDT for track quality will be used to reduce the impact of fake tracks in downstream algorithms. Global event variables such as the primary vertex will also be reconstructed in the Level-1 trigger reducing the impact of pileup on downstream algorithms and improving trigger performance. A novel approach to the regression of this vertex and track-to-vertex association using an end-to-end neural network is shown to outperform the baseline approach while maintaining low latency and low resource usage. Finally, the demonstration of these systems is underway with key integration tests between the track finder and vertex finding being completed.

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ATLAS ITk Track Reconstruction with a GNN-based pipeline

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ABSTRACT

In preparation for the upcoming HL-LHC era, ATLAS is pursuing several methods to reduce the resources consumption needed to reconstruct the trajectory of charged particles (tracks) in the new all-silicon Inner Tracker (ITk). This includes the development of new algorithms suitable for massively parallel computing architecture like GPUs. Algorithms for track pattern recognition based on graph neural networks (GNNs) have emerged as a particularly promising approach. Previous work using simulated data from the TrackML challenge show high track reconstruction efficiency. In the present document we describe a first functional implementation of a GNN-based track pattern reconstruction for ITk, achieving a high GNN track reconstruction efficiency and promising fake track rate.

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1 Introduction and strategy

During the upcoming High Luminosity phase [1] of the Large Hadron Collider [2] (HL-LHC) the peak instantaneous luminosity of the accelerator will be increased to an unprecedented 7.5 times the nominal luminosity. The bunch crossing time (25 ns) will remain unchanged: higher instantaneous luminosity will be achieved by increasing the number of protons per bunch. This leads to an increase of the average number of inelastic proton-proton collisions per bunch crossing $\langle \mu \rangle$ (pile-up) expected to reach 200 during the Run 5. As a result, the ATLAS experiment [3] will be implementing significant upgrades to the detector and to the data acquisition system in order to cope with the increased data rates and pile-up, including construction of a new silicon-only Inner Tracker with improved granularity, ITk [4].

Even with the upgraded detector, the HL-LHC conditions will lead to a steep increase in computing resources needed to process and analyse the data. Assuming a flat budget, the expected improvements in computing hardware may not be able to provide this increased capacity, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Projected evolution of compute usage from 2020 until 2036, under the conservative (blue) and aggressive (red) R&D scenarios. Figure taken from Ref. [5]

The offline reconstruction of ITk data represents a non-trivial fraction of computing resource needs, about 20% [5]. The CPU resources needed for event reconstruction tend to be dominated by charged particle reconstruction (“tracking”). Significant effort is therefore being invested into the reduction of computing resources needed for tracking. This includes improvements of existing algorithms and the development of new ones, based on machine learning (ML), suitable for massively parallel computing architectures like GPUs.

The authors of Ref. [6] identified the use of Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) as a promising ML solution for charged particle tracking at the HL-LHC. Since this publication, significant effort has been invested in the development of algorithms based on GNNs [7–12]. Excellent performance of GNN-based algorithms on the TrackML dataset [13] has recently been demonstrated in Refs. [8, 9].

We present a first functional implementation of a pattern recognition algorithm based on GNNs for ATLAS ITk. The method is illustrated in Figure 2.

It proceeds in three steps:

1. Graph construction: Collision events recorded by the ITk can be represented as graphs. Graph nodes represent space points created from energy deposits in the ITk (clusters). Two nodes can be connected by an edge. The existence of an edge means that the two nodes could potentially represent two successive space points on a track. Features are attached to each node (the space point coordinates) and each edge (geometric quantities calculated from the two nodes).
2. Edge labeling: A GNN assigns an edge classification score to each edge in the graph. The classification score is a value between 0 and 1. The GNN is trained to assign a high score to edges that connect two successive space points from a target particle and a low score to other edges.

Figure 2: Schematic overview of the GNN-based track finding pipeline [14].

3. Graph segmentation: Track candidates (lists of nodes) are built from the graph based on the edge classification scores.

It is assumed that the track candidates found by this pattern reconstruction could then be run through a track fitting algorithm for track parameter estimation, and that further selections on the track candidates would be applied after fitting.

2 Simulated sample

The results presented in these proceedings are based on simulated $pp \rightarrow t\bar{t}$ events in which at least one of the top quarks decays leptonically, produced at $\sqrt{s} = 14$ TeV with a pile-up of $\langle\mu\rangle = 200$. The ITk, displayed in Figure 3, is divided into two sub-detectors:

- The pixel sub-detector: closest to the luminous region, pictured in red in Figure 3. It comprises 9416 silicon modules.
- The strip sub-detector: surrounds the pixel sub-detector, pictured in blue in Figure 3. It comprises 8944 silicon modules which are instrumented on both sides.

Figure 3: Schematic overview of ITk [15].

Space points are three-dimensional objects reconstructed from clusters. Pixel clusters directly translate into pixel space points. The combination of information of two strips clusters are needed to create strip space points. Figure 4 shows the creation of a particular kind of strip space point called *ghost* space point,

which is caused by an overlap of strips fired by a given particle and strips on the other side of the module fired by another particle.

Figure 4: Schematic view of the creation of *ghost* space points created by a combinatorial ambiguity leading to two misconstrued space points.

In this study we use space points rather than clusters to reduce the numbers of nodes - and therefore edges - created within a graph.

3 Graph construction

A GNN classifier acts on data represented by a graph. In a $t\bar{t}$ event with a pile-up of $\langle\mu\rangle = 200$, $O(10^5)$ space points per event are expected. A fully connected graph of such an event would have $O(10^{10})$ edges, most of them representing nonphysical connections. A key feature of graph construction is therefore the choice of the edge connections.

We define four categories of particles:

- Target particles: All primary particles (from the $t\bar{t}$ pair and the soft interaction) with $p_T > 1$ GeV and leaving at least 3 space points.
- Electrons: Which are excluded as a simplification.
- Non-target particles: All secondary particles, and primary particles (from the $t\bar{t}$ pair and the soft interaction) with $p_T < 1$ GeV that leave at least 3 space points.
- Non fiducial particles: are particles with a radius $r > 26$ cm or a pseudo-rapidity $|\eta| > 4$.

As we aim to reconstruct target particles, the choice of edges must guarantee the existence of edges connecting successive space points of target particles, while keeping the total number of edges low. Two kind of graph construction algorithms have been developed - the *Module Map*, a data-driven approach, and the *Metric Learning*, a machine learning approach.

3.1 The Module Map Approach

The *Module Map* is a list of connections between triplet of silicon modules used to create all possible edges in a graph. It is created by following the trajectory of target particles inside the ITk. As all space points left by a target particle are sorted by their distance from the particle vertex before being followed, a direction *inside-out* is given to each module triplets and therefore to each created edges. This direction is then used during the final step of the reconstruction 5.

To learn all possible module connections, 90000 simulated $t\bar{t}$ events are used. Connections induced by the inefficiencies of the silicon modules are also learned. Therefore, edges linking two space points of non-successive layers can also be mapped and constructed. The resulting module map comprises 1242265 triplet connections. To further reduce the number of edges, cuts are applied on geometric parameters. These cuts

are automatically adjusted, separately for *each* module connection, such that no true edge coming from target particles is rejected in the training sample of 90000 $t\bar{t}$ events. The graphs created using this method have on average 2.7×10^5 nodes and 1.3×10^6 edges.

3.2 The Metric Learning Approach

In the *Metric Learning* approach, a multi-layer perceptron (MLP) is trained to embed each space point into an N-dimensional latent space, based on the space point positions and the direction and dimensions of the module containing the cluster. The MLP is trained using a hinge loss L defined as:

$$L = \begin{cases} x & \text{if true pair,} \\ \max(0, r_{emb} - x) & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

This teaches the MLP to embeds space points belonging to a given target particle to be close to each other, as measured by euclidean distance x . The embedding radius r_{emb} in the latent space is a hyperparameter of the model that can be adjusted to create graphs of various size and efficiency.

The graph is then constructed by connecting space point within the radius r_{emb} in the latent space, using a fast Fixed Radius Nearest Neighbor (FRNN) algorithm [16]. Edges are learned to be created between successive space points of the same target particle. Although FRNN creates two edges for each node pair (one in each direction), duplicate edges are chosen at random and removed for memory efficiency. Thus, while directionality is not retained by the metric learning construction, it can be recovered by following the increasing radius of the space points, and can thus be used during the final step of the reconstruction 5.

Additional filtering is done using another MLP dedicated to prune the graph. The selection requirements are adjusted to obtain graphs with the same size as the ones created using the Module Map method.

3.3 Graph edge construction efficiencies

The graph edge construction efficiency of both graph construction methods is defined as the ratio of the number of edges coming from target particles found in a graph over the total number of expected edges coming from target particles. Only the edges linking successive space points of target particles are considered. Figure 5 shows the graph edge construction efficiency as a function of η (Figure 5a) and p_T (Figure 5b).

Figure 5: Graph edge construction efficiency as a function of η and p_T using the Module Map and Metric Learning methods [14].

The drops at $|\eta| = 1$ found in the Module Map efficiency have for origin the lower efficiency found in the strip barrel, where the space point spatial longitudinal resolution is lower than in the pixel sub-detector. Building a Module Map using more events should mitigate this inefficiency. High- p_T tracks represent a small

fraction of the defined target particles training set, which explains the efficiency degradation at high- p_T of the Metric Learning method.

In the following sections of this note, the Module Map method is used to build the graphs. Space point coordinates in (r, ϕ, z) -space are attached to each node as *features*. For each edge, the observables $(\Delta\eta, \Delta\phi, \Delta r, \Delta z)$ are computed from the space point coordinates of origin and destination node, and they are attached to the edge as features.

4 Deep geometric learning of track patterns

4.1 Graph Neural Network model

The GNN model used for this study has an encode-process-decode architecture. At the encode stage, an encoder transforms the features attached to each node and each edge into a \mathcal{D} -dimensional space latent representation. The encoder is implemented using two MLPs: one for the node features and one for the edge features. At the process stage, an interaction network [17] is applied iteratively (called a *message-passing* mechanism) \mathcal{L} times, to update the latent features of the graph. This mechanism propagates information through the graph so that the GNN classify edges based on track patterns. The interaction network is divided into two steps. An edge network updates the latent features of each edge, using an MLP applied to the latent features of each adjoining node and the previous iteration's edge latent features. A node network then updates the latent features of each node using as input a concatenation of the latent features of the node with the sum of the latent feature of the incoming and outgoing edges.

At the decode stage, a decoder implemented using an MLP transforms the latent features of each edge into an edge classification score, capturing the pseudo-probability that the edge represents two successive space points of a track.

4.2 Training the Graph Neural Network model

The GNN model described in Section 4.1 ($\mathcal{L} = 8$, $\mathcal{D} = 128$, two layers in each of the MLPs) is trained using 400 graphs produced with the Module Map method. The events used to produce the graphs are also used during the Module Map creation, so that their efficiency is guaranteed to be 100%. The amsgrad [18] optimizer is used with a fixed learning rate of 5×10^{-4} . Given the size of the graphs described in 3.1, the model was trained on an Nvidia A100 with 80 GB of memory using *large model support* [19]. The full memory capacity of the GPU is used as well as 97 GB of memory on the host. A binary cross-entropy loss function is used with weight w_{edge} given to each class:

$$w_{edge} = \begin{cases} 1.0 & \text{if true edge,} \\ 0.1 & \text{if fake edge,} \\ 0.0 & \text{if masked edge.} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

A *true edge* is defined as an edge linking two successive space points of a target particle. A *fake edge* is defined as: a) An edge linking space points of different particles; b) An edge involving an electron(s) or non fiducial particle; or c) An edge linking nonsuccessive space points of the same particle. A *masked edge* is defined as an edge linking two successive space points of non-target particle. A weight 0.0 is given to masked edges in order to not confuse the GNN by setting to false edges from non-target particles that can have similar topology to the one of the target particles.

Figure 6 shows the GNN edge classification performance after training. Background rejection rate is given as $1/\epsilon_{bkg}$ where ϵ_{bkg} is the fraction of fake edges that pass the classification requirement. Signal efficiency is defined as the number of true edges above a given classification score cut over the total number of true edges.

4.3 Edge classification performance

In this section, the performances at edge-level of the GNN edge classifier described above are obtained considering a cut on the edge classification score $s = 0.5$. All performances shown in the following are

computed using 100 events withheld from those used during the GNN training. Those 100 events have been used during the module map creation so that their graphs construction efficiency is 100%.

Per-edge efficiency is defined as the number of true edges passing a given cut on the classification score over the number of total true edges. A per-edge purity is defined as the number of true edges passing the cut over the total number of edges passing the cut. Masked edges do not appear in these performance calculations.

Figure 7 shows the performance of the GNN edge classifier as a function of the pseudo-rapidity η . A drop in the central region is found in the efficiency (Figure 7a) and in the purity (Figure 7b).

Figure 6: Graph Neural Network classification performance, based on GNN per-edge efficiency and GNN fake rate (red). The black dashed curve shows the performance of randomly classifying edges as true or false [14].

(a) GNN per-edge efficiency vs. η

(b) GNN per-edge purity vs. η

Figure 7: Performance of the GNN edge classifier as a function of the pseudo-rapidity η [14]. The asymmetric drop at $\eta=4$ could be explained by a lack of training statistics in that particular region, future trainings with larger samples will permit to conclude.

Figure 8 shows the GNN edge classifier performance as a function of the transverse momentum p_T for the full detector (red curve), for $|\eta| > 2$ (blue curve) and for $|\eta| < 2$ (green curve). High- p_T particles tend to be produced in the central region, where the efficiency is found to be the lower, see Figure 7a.

Figure 9 shows the performances of the GNN edge classifier in the (z, r) plan. Figure 9a shows the efficiency, which is found to be high across the full detector. Figure 9b shows the purity. The drops already seen in Figure 7 are again seen, and found to be in the layers of the strip sub-detector. The lower purity and efficiency in these layers can be explained by the lower spatial space point resolution in the z direction.

Figure 8: GNN per-edge efficiency as a function of the transverse momentum p_T [14].

(a) GNN per-edge efficiency in (z, r) plane

(b) GNN per-edge purity in (z, r) plane

Figure 9: Performance of the GNN edge classifier in the (z, r) plane. The position in (z, r) of an edge is defined by the position of its source node [14].

Figure 10 summarizes the origin of all fake edges. An edge composed of two non-successive space points from the same particle is considered fake. This means that this edge *jumps* one (or more) space point in the track of a particle. This could imply that space points will be missing in the reconstructed track if edges linking successive space points are not well-classified. In this paper, electrons and non-fiducial particles are considered as fake. They represent around 10% of the total fake edges.

A ghost is a strip space point being an accidental combination of two clusters which do not belong to the same particle. In Figure 10, fake edges linking a well-constructed node (representing a space point with both clusters coming from the same particle) with a ghost node are studied. Only ghosts having one of their two clusters belonging to the same particle as the well-constructed node are represented in this bin. If such a fake edge is included during the track building stage, this would lead to a cluster on the created track being wrongly associated.

Figure 10: Origin of the fake edges [14].

5 Tracks reconstruction from Graph Neural Network output

The last stage of the pipeline presented in these proceedings is the tracks reconstruction stage based on the edge classification score and the graph topology. This stage is divided into two steps.

In the first step, a low cut of $s = 0.1$ on the edge classification score is applied to the graphs. This reduces the number of edges from $O(10^6)$ to $O(10^4)$. A set of *connected components*, are so created in the graph, where each node is linked to others via one or more paths. If a single path exist - i.e. if each node in a connected component has at most one incoming and one outgoing edge - then that connected component is directly labeled as a track candidate.

If more than one path exists, connected components are disentangled using a walk-through algorithm, called *Wrangler*. A topological sort is first applied such that nodes with no incoming edges are considered as starting points for Wrangler. Given one of these starting nodes, we choose the outgoing edge with the highest classification score, given a minimum score of $s > 0.3$. The attached node is then added to a track candidate. If other outgoing edges have a classification score $s > 0.8$, attached nodes are also used to build new track candidates. Then the procedure is repeated until no more node can be add to the track candidates. Wrangler can therefore build several track candidates from a starting node. The ambiguity is solved by keeping only the longest track candidate created.

To present the GNN track reconstruction efficiency, two kinds of matching criteria are used. Note that matching is done without any track fitting. A *standard matching* is defined as a track candidate having more than 50% of its space points belonging to the same truth track. A *strict matching* is defined as a track candidate having all space points belonging to the same truth track and no space points missing from this truth track.

Figure 11 shows the performance of the GNN track reconstruction efficiency as a function of η (Figure 11a) and p_T (Figure 11b). The performances are given relative to the target particles.

A fake track is defined as a track candidate not matched to any truth track. The ratio of fake tracks created to all target track candidates is found to be $O(10^{-3})$. Fitting the tracks is expected to reduce this amount and will be the object of a dedicated future study.

6 Conclusions and future prospects

We present the first GNN-based track reconstruction algorithm based on ATLAS ITk simulated data for HL-LHC. The GNN track reconstruction efficiency shows promising results on a realistic scenario. In the future, a high priority will be given to completing a comparison with the Kalman Filter currently used

Figure 11: GNN track reconstruction efficiency vs p_T [14].

in the ATLAS reconstruction chain. This will require an implementation of the pipeline presented in this proceedings in a tracking framework, such as ACTS and Athena. A dedicated study and tuning of the GNN architecture will be made to improve the performance degradation in the strip barrel sub-detector.

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Track Reconstruction using Geometric Deep Learning in the Straw Tube Tracker (STT) at the PANDA Experiment

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ABSTRACT

The PANDA (anti-Proton ANnihilation at DArmstadt) experiment at the Facility for Anti-proton and Ion Research will study strong interactions at the scale at which quarks are confined to form hadrons. A continuous beam of anti-protons, provided by the High Energy Storage Ring (HESR), will impinge on a fixed hydrogen target. The anti-proton beam momentum spanning from 1.5 GeV¹ to 15 GeV [1] will create optimal conditions for studying many different aspects of hadron physics, including hyperon physics.

Precision physics studies require a highly efficient particle track reconstruction. The Straw Tube Tracker in PANDA is the main component for that purpose. It has a hexagonal geometry, consisting of 4224 gas-filled tubes arranged in 26 layers and six sectors. However, the challenge is reconstructing low-momentum charged particles given the complex detector geometry and the strongly curved particle trajectory. This paper presents the first application of a geometric deep learning (GDL) pipeline, inspired by the Exa.TrkX project, to the track reconstruction task in the PANDA experiment. The pipeline is suitable for graph-based data and uses graph neural networks (GNNs) as the underlying learning algorithm. The pipeline reconstructs more than 95% of particle tracks and creates less than 0.3% of fake tracks. The promising results make the pipeline a strong candidate algorithm for the experiment.

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¹Natural units, $c=1$

1 Introduction

The PANDA experiment [1] will provide unique opportunities to study Quantum Chromodynamics (QCD) in the confinement domain where an anti-proton beam impinges on a stationary target (proton or heavy atoms). Dynamic beam momentum, ranging from 1.5 GeV to 15 GeV, allows in-depth studies of Nucleon Structure, Strangeness Physics, Charm and Exotics and Hadrons in Nuclei [2]. Generally, these studies are performed using the PandaRoot [3] simulation framework to simulate nuclear reactions, for example, the Λ hyperon production in $\bar{p}p \rightarrow \bar{\Lambda}\Lambda \rightarrow \bar{p}\pi^+ + p\pi^-$ reaction. To successfully reconstruct a physics reaction, one needs high-precision track reconstruction. The main challenge lies in reconstructing particles with low transversal momentum (p_T), for example, pions. The weakly decaying hyperons, like Λ particles, fly a considerable distance ($c\tau(\Lambda) = 7.89$ cm) in the detector before decaying. Thus, the presence of displaced secondary vertices is an additional challenge. Tracking algorithms explored in Ref. [4] try different combinations of detector measurements using a helix fitting to determine the quality of track candidates. However, our work presents the first application of a GNN as an alternative approach to track reconstruction in PANDA. The GNNs are better suited for non-Euclidean data because of the expressive power of the graph structure.

The paper is organized as follows. A brief introduction to the PANDA experiment is given in Section 2. The GDL pipeline is discussed in Section 3 whereas results, *track evaluation*, are given in Section 4. Finally, the conclusion is given in Section 5.

2 The PANDA Experiment at FAIR

The PANDA (anti-Proton ANnihilation at DArmstadt) experiment is currently under construction at FAIR (Facility for Anti-proton and Ion Research) [5, 6]. Figure 1 shows a schematic diagram of the PANDA experiment. The detector provides almost 4π coverage surrounding the interaction point (IP) and will record data at the expected interaction rate of 20 MHz. The Straw Tube Tracker (STT) in the target spectrometer is the most demanding detector for reconstructing particle trajectories.

Figure 1: Schematic of the PANDA Experiment

The STT consists of 4224 straw tubes, the single-channel drift tubes, distributed in 27 layers and six sectors in a hexagonal shape, as shown in Figure 2 (left). The green tubes (15 - 19 layers) are parallel to the

beam axis intended for xy -position whereas blue and red tubes (8 layers) are skewed to $\pm 2.9^\circ$ polar angle with respect to the beam axis for reconstructing the z - component. The STT detector angular acceptance in polar angle, θ , is from 22° to 140° . A particle needs a minimum p_T of 50 MeV to arrive at the innermost layer and a minimum p_T of 100 MeV to traverse through the STT fully*.

When a charged particle traverses the STT detector, it ionizes the gas inside the tube. The ionized electrons then drift towards the centre of the tube, where an anode wire creates a *hit*. The xy position of the hit is the position of the anode wire. The distance between the closest approach of the particle trajectory to the anode wire is the *isochrone radius*. We use both the xy position and the isochrone radius as inputs. It is possible to reconstruct the z -component of the hit position by using the skewed straw layers, but that would require a dedicated algorithm to achieve high accuracy. We leave that work to the future.

Figure 2: Left: a cross-sectional view of the STT detector. Right: zoom-in view of straw tubes in black circles and the isochrone radius in blue circles and a track in red.

3 Geometric Deep Learning Pipeline

To perform track reconstruction using *Geometric Deep Learning (GDL)*, we build a complete pipeline on top of the Exa.TrkX [7] pipeline. The core idea is to first represent a collision event as a graph in which nodes are the hits recorded by the STT detector and edges are connections between two adjacent hits, and then to train a Graph Neural Network (GNN) to learn the relational information between hits. Our pipeline consists of four discrete stages (see Figure 3): data preparation, graph construction, edge classification, and track formation.

Figure 3: Stages of Geometric Deep Learning pipeline used for reconstructing tracks with the STT detector.

*Under solenoid magnetic field of 2 T

3.1 Data Preparation

The input data is simulated using the PandaRoot analysis framework [3]. Five $\mu^+\mu^-$ pairs per event are generated using the particle gun in the momentum range of 100 MeV/c to 1.5 GeV/c. Muons are isotropically generated within the geometric acceptance of the STT detector (see Section 2). The choice of this relatively low momentum range is motivated by the fact that the existing algorithms have difficulties in reconstructing low- p_T particle trajectories because these trajectories are spiralling, strongly curved, and overlapping [4, 8].

A total of 100,000 events are generated, containing about a million tracks. The data is split into 90% for training, 5% for validation, and 5% for testing.

3.2 Graph Construction

The graph construction step is to convert the raw input data, represented as point clouds, into bi-directed graphs. To that end, we use a heuristic method that captures all true edges while it keeps fake connections low. The method builds all combinatorial connections between hits in two consecutive radially outward layers in nearby sectors. Figure 4 shows the true graph (left) where edges are connections between hits coming from the same particle and the input graph (right) in which only the connections between the innermost two layers are shown. If a particle leaves two hits in the same layer, both hits are included in the graph.

Figure 4: Graph representation of an event: (*left*) True Graph, (*right*) Input Graph

3.3 Edge Classification

We use the same Graph Neural Network architecture used in Ref. [9], also known as Interaction GNN. The schematic of this network is shown in Figure 5.

The Interaction GNN contains three sub-networks: the Encoder Module, the Graph Module and the Output Module. The Encoder Module comprises a node network and an edge network, encoding input node features into a vector of hidden features and creating edge features with the neighbouring node features. The Graph Module is an interaction network [10] in which aggregated neighbouring edge features are passed to the node network, and the neighbouring node features are passed to the edge network. This way, information is exchanged between nodes and edges, namely message passing. The message passing step is performed $N = 8$ times. The output from the Graph Module is passed through the output module that performs

Figure 5: Interaction Graph Neural Network (Interaction GNN)

binary classification of edges using the cross-entropy loss. As a result, an edge score is obtained for each edge.

The performance of the interaction GNN is evaluated using the Area Under the Curve (AUC) of the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve. The higher the AUC value, the better the model performance. In addition, we define the edge efficiency (ϵ_E) as the fraction of true edges being selected and the edge purity (p_E) as the fraction of true edges in the selected edges. Figure 6(a) shows the edge efficiency and edge purity distribution as a function of edge score cuts and Figure 6(b) shows the ROC curve built from ϵ_E and p_E as defined above. The AUC for the Interaction GNN is 0.9998.

Figure 6: Model evaluation: ϵ_E and p_E as a function of edge score cut (*left*), ROC with AUC > 0.9998 (*right*)

3.4 Track Formation

Track formation is to create a list of hits, also known as *track candidates*, from the edge scores predicted by the interaction GNN. To that end, we use the *connected component* algorithm in the Graph theory [11]. We first remove edges with scores less than 0.25 and then find *weakly connected components* in the graph. Each found component is a track candidate.

4 Results

We define the Track Efficiency (ϵ_{phys} , $\epsilon_{\text{tech.}}$), Track Purity, and Fake Rate to evaluate the performance of the track finding pipeline. These metrics are defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}\epsilon_{\text{phys}} &= \frac{N_{\text{particles}}(\text{selected, matched})}{N_{\text{particles}}(\text{selected})} \\ \epsilon_{\text{tech.}} &= \frac{N_{\text{particles}}(\text{selected, reconstructable, matched})}{N_{\text{particles}}(\text{selected, reconstructable})} \\ \text{Purity} &= \frac{N_{\text{reco_tracks}}(\text{selected, matched})}{N_{\text{reco_tracks}}(\text{selected})} \equiv 1 - \text{Fake Rate}\end{aligned}\tag{1}$$

where $N_{\text{particles}}(\text{selected})$ is the number of particles generated within the STT acceptance, and $N_{\text{particles}}(\text{selected, reconstructable})$ is the number of generated particles that leave at least 4 hits in the detector, namely the reconstructable generated particles. Generated particles are reconstructed if they can be matched [†] to at least one reconstructed track. Similarly, $N_{\text{reco_tracks}}(\text{selected})$ is the number of reconstructed tracks containing at least 4 hits. The fake rate is defined as the fraction of reconstructed tracks not matching any particle tracks, and the duplication rate is defined as the rate at which a particle track is matched to more than one reconstructed track.

A test dataset with 5000 events is used for the evaluation. The overall ϵ_{phys} is 94.6% with a fake rate of 0.423% and a duplication rate of 16.6%. Figure 7(a) shows the ϵ_{phys} and $\epsilon_{\text{tech.}}$ over different p_T values. It is expected that the $\epsilon_{\text{tech.}}$ will be slightly greater than the ϵ_{phys} due to the inefficiency of the detector. Figure 7(b) shows the number of generated, reconstructable and matched events at various p_T values.

Figure 7: Track evaluation: (left) Track efficiency vs. p_T , (right) Number of generated, reconstructable and matched tracks at various p_T values.

The inefficiency and the high duplication rate are caused by crossing or overlapping tracks. For events consisting of well-separated tracks in an event, the ϵ_{phys} is 97.6% with a fake rate of 0.220% and a duplication rate of 7.92%. The remaining efficiency loss, in some cases, is caused by extremely low p_T tracks where a single track is broken into multiple sub-tracks, leading to low efficiency and a high duplication rate. Further investigation reveals that our track labelling method fails to assign shared hits to different tracks properly.

[†]the matching criteria is that the number of hits shared by the particle track and reconstructed track is larger than 50% of the number of hits of the particle track and larger than 50% of the number of hits of the reconstructed track. A particle track is formed by a list of hits created by the particle.

5 Conclusions

The PANDA experiment will be a unique facility to study strong interactions. We presented a GDL-based track reconstruction pipeline for the PANDA experiment. The pipeline achieves high reconstruction efficiencies at a low rate of fake tracks. However, the rate of duplicate tracks is high due to shared hits between tracks. A more robust track labelling algorithm will be investigated.

In the future, we would like to compare the GNN-based pipeline with other track reconstruction algorithms currently under development at PANDA and test the pipeline with different physics processes. We will also test the robustness of the pipeline and add the track parameter estimation.

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Tracking on GPU at LHCb's fully software trigger

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ABSTRACT

The LHCb experiment will use a fully software-based trigger to collect data from 2022 on, at an event rate of 30 MHz. During the first stage of the High-Level Trigger (HLT1), a partial track reconstruction, using efficient parallelisation techniques on GPU cards, is performed. This stage will reduce the event rate by around a factor 30. Reconstructing tracks at 30 MHz represents a challenge which needs to be faced with very performant tracking algorithms. These proceedings focus on reconstruction and performance aspects of HLT1, giving particular attention to the algorithms reconstructing particles traversing the whole LHCb detector.

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1 Introduction

The LHCb detector is a single-arm forward spectrometer installed at the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) and specialized to study heavy flavour physics [1, 2]. During Run 1 and 2 of the LHC, the experiment collected 9 fb^{-1} of data. However, many crucial studies are still statistically limited and require an increased amount of data together with an improved detector performance, to achieve uncertainties comparable to the associated theory. LHCb is undergoing a major upgrade during the Long Shutdown 2 in order to collect 50 fb^{-1} by 2033 (Run 3 and 4) [3]. To achieve this, the instantaneous luminosity will be increased by a factor 5 compared to Run2, reaching $2 \cdot 10^{33} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

To sustain the experimental challenges of the increased luminosity, higher granularity and more radiation tolerant sub-detectors are needed, together with new front-end and readout electronics. A sketch of the upgraded LHCb detector is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Side view of the LHCb upgraded detector.

In particular, all tracking sub-detectors underwent to major upgrades and here are described:

- The Vertex Locator (VELO), a sub-system located around the proton-proton collision point and devoted to precisely measuring primary and secondary vertices, is composed of 26 tracking layers based on $50 \times 50 \mu\text{m}^2$ pixel technology.
- The Upstream Tracker (UT), a sub-detector before the dipole magnet designed to reconstruct long-lived particles decaying after the VELO, is composed of 4 layers of silicon strips.
- The Scintillating Fiber tracker (SciFi), located after the magnet to provide measurements of particle momenta, is constructed of 12 scintillating fiber layers divided into 3 stations.

The Run 2 triggering scheme is a major limiting factor to exploit the $2 \cdot 10^{33} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ luminosity upgrade. As shown in Figure 2, the trigger yield for many hadronic channels was already saturating with Run 2 conditions ($4 \cdot 10^{33} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$).

This limitation is mainly caused by the LHCb's first level trigger (L0) implemented in hardware, which requires minimum energy depositions in the calorimeter to trigger on hadrons. To resolve this limitation, events will be selected by a fully software-based trigger during the upcoming data taking. Removing the L0 trigger will increase the hadronic channels' triggering efficiency by a factor of 2 for beauty hadron decays and typically larger factors for charm and light-hadron decays with respect to Run 2.

The software-based High Level Trigger (HLT) will perform the event reconstruction at the 30 MHz non-empty bunches collisions the LHC. The full LHCb data flow is presented in Figure 3.

Raw detectors' information is sent to a custom data processing center, where FPGA cards receive data at an average of 5 TB/s. Then, the Event Builder (EB) CPU servers use this information to produce packets of events that can be processed directly by the HLT. The first High Level Trigger (HLT1) reduces the 30 MHz

Figure 2: Run2 trigger yield dependence on instantaneous luminosity. [5] Various decays are identified by different colors. Hadronic trigger yields saturate when increasing the luminosity.

input rate to 1 MHz selecting interesting events by partially reconstructing them [4]. Graphical Processing Units (GPUs) are ideal for this purpose, as the reconstruction can be parallelised at the event level and further at the track level. Moreover GPUs can be added to each EB server with zero extra overhead costs.

A real-time alignment and calibration is then performed inside a buffer before processing events with the second High Level Trigger (HLT2). HLT2 performs a full event reconstruction on CPUs, reducing the rate from 1 MHz down to around 50 kHz. HLT2 selected events will be then processed offline to create final samples to be analysed.

Figure 3: LHCb upgrade dataflow focusing on the real-time aspects. [7]

2 Reconstruction on GPUs

The Allen project takes care of the HLT1 reconstruction on GPUs at LHCb. Charged particle reconstruction is performed down to a momentum threshold of 3 GeV. For LHCb's physics purposes, different types of tracks must be reconstructed (see Figure 4):

- VELO tracks leaving hits only in the VELO subdetector,
- Upstream tracks which are bent out of the magnet after the UT,
- Long tracks crossing all tracking subdetectors. These tracks are very important for LHCb as they provide the best particle momentum measurement,

- Downstream tracks produced by long lived particles and crossing only UT and SciFi subdetectors,
- T-tracks leaving hits only on the SciFi.

Reconstruction of downstream and T-tracks in HLT1 is discussed in [6].

Figure 4: Types of tracks reconstructed by the LHCb experiment.

Allen features various algorithms to perform the event reconstruction, using input raw data from the LHCb’s subdetectors. The default sequence is presented in Figure 5 and composed of:

- A global event cut, which rejects the 10% of highest occupancy minimum bias events prior any processing, based on UT and SciFi raw data information,
- VELO reconstruction using the “Search by Triplet” algorithm, performing an optimized straight line fit [10],
- Primary vertex finding and fitting, extrapolating VELO tracks as straight lines to the beamline,
- VELO-UT tracking with the “CompassUT” algorithm [12], providing the first charge and momentum measurement and having therefore the first meaningful objects for physics selections,
- Forward reconstruction, extrapolating VeloUT tracks to the SciFi region using a B field’s parametrized trajectory,
- Parametrized Kalman filter to improve the estimate of certain physics variables, such as the impact parameter (IP),
- Muon identification, extrapolating the reconstructed forward tracks to find matching hits in the muon system,
- Calorimeter reconstruction to correctly identify electrons from corresponding hits in the calorimeter and recover their lost radiated energy with a Bremsstrahlung recovery algorithm,
- Secondary vertex finding from long-lived particles decay,
- Event selection with trigger lines to cover most of the LHCb physics programme.

2.1 Velo tracking

Reconstruction at LHCb’s HLT1 level starts from tracks leaving hits in the detector closest to the proton-proton collision point: the VELO. This tracking sub-detector is designed to reconstruct particles in the LHCb forward acceptance (10-300 mrad) and it is composed of 26 modules on each side of the beam pipe. In this first region (~ 1 meter), the effect of LHCb’s magnet field is negligible. Tracks are therefore expected

Figure 5: Schematic of HLT1 reconstruction flow at LHCb.

to be straight lines. The “Search by Triplet” algorithm [10] achieves optimal computational performance with a double parallelization, at both the event and track level.

As trajectories are expected to start close to the XY plane origin, tracks can be reconstructed selecting hits by ϕ (angle in the XY plane) and z . The algorithm can then be explained in 3 steps:

1. Track seeding operating on 3 consecutive modules, looking for hits inside ϕ windows,
2. Forwarding the search to next modules to complete the track (accepting maximum one consecutive missing module) ,
3. Repeat the seeding process on the leftover hits.

As shown in Figure 6, the track reconstruction efficiency is about 99 % in all ranges of momenta and transverse momenta.

Figure 6: Velo tracking efficiency as a function of momentum and transverse momentum (p_T). [9]

2.2 Primary Vertex finding

One of the physics requirement in HLT1 is to reconstruct all primary vertices (PVs) from proton-proton collisions. VELO tracks can be extrapolated as straight lines to the beamline, and PVs can be identified by looking at the z position of the intersection between the track and the beamline. Figure 7 (a) shows a histogram of all VELO tracks’ point of closest approach inside a single event (filling the histogram bins taking into account each track uncertainty from its covariance matrix). Peaks can be then isolated and fitted

using Gaussian density distributions. These density distributions take the uncertainty on the track states into account. The primary vertex reconstruction efficiency as a function of VELO tracks associated to each PV is presented in Figure 7 (b).

Figure 7: Primary vertex clustering (a) and efficiency as a function of number of associated tracks (b). [11]

2.3 Velo-UT tracking

The UT subdetector is composed of 4 silicon strip module planes. The first and last plane, labeled as X, are composed of vertical modules while the two middle planes, labeled as U and V, contains modules tilted by $+5^\circ$ and -5° respectively. By combining the information from the U/V and X layers, it is possible to determine the Y coordinates of the hits. The UT subdetector allows to reconstruct charged particles which decay after the VELO and low momentum tracks bending out of the magnetic field region, not reaching the SciFi. Moreover, it allows a first momentum and charge estimate. VELO-UT tracks, because of their still poor momentum resolution, are not mainly used for physics selections, but are rather inputs to the Forward algorithm.

VELO tracks are extrapolated to the UT planes taking into account the small magnetic field present in the region. Hits are searched in the planes assuming a minimum momentum which defines the search windows size. To perform the UT tracking, a 4-hit search is carried out following the VELO track extrapolation and allowing for one missing hit [12]. If more than one tracklet per VELO input track is found, a χ^2 fit is performed and the tracklet with the lowest χ^2 is selected. The algorithm is parallelized over input VELO tracks and also over tracklet candidates per input track. The reconstruction efficiency as a function of momentum and transverse momentum is shown in Figure 8.

2.4 Forward tracking

For the LHCb's physics purposes, HLT1 needs to be able to reconstruct long tracks with 500 MeV p_T requirement and a 3 GeV momentum requirement, and evaluate their momenta with a resolution better than 1 %. The SciFi tracker, located after the dipole magnet, allows the reconstruction of these long tracks thanks to its 12 scintillating fibers layers. They are divided into 3 T stations with 4 layers each, labeled as X-U-V-X. X layers are vertical while U and V layers are tilted by $\pm 5^\circ$, respectively, providing in combination also Y information to the hits.

The forward tracking algorithm takes as input previously reconstructed VELO-UT tracks and parallelizes their extrapolation inside the GPU. The input tracks have already a first momentum and charge estimate from the VELO-UT algorithm. A parametrization of the magnetic field is used to estimate their trajectories extrapolating them to each of the 12 layers of the SciFi. The size of the search windows is decided based on the first momentum estimate from the VELO-UT algorithm.

Figure 8: Velo-UT tracking efficiency as a function of momentum and transverse momentum (p_T).

First of all, a 3-hit tracklet search is performed either looking at the first X layer in each T-station (first seed) or the last X layer in each T-station (second seed). Performing combinations in only 2 seeds is found to be the optimal, balancing between physics and speed performances of the algorithm. To achieve a better throughput performance, the triplet search is performed using a maximum of 32 central hits inside the search window. A second level of parallelization is set on the triplet candidates. The χ^2 of trajectories can be evaluated at this stage to avoid processing triplets that are unambiguously wrong (with very high χ^2). Matching a VELO-UT track with 3 hits in the SciFi provides a well defined trajectory which can be determined by a 4 parameter equation [14].

Then, the triplet candidates are extended over the other 3 X layers and 6 U/V layers (using Y information from the VELO-UT slope) requiring a minimum of 9 hits.

As a final step, all remaining tracklets in combination with their respective VELO-UT input track are fitted and the candidate with the lowest χ^2 is selected. The reconstruction efficiency is shown in Figure 9 (a) and plateaus at 90 % for tracks with $p_T > 1$ GeV. The final candidate fit provides also the momentum estimate, shown in Figure 9 (b), which has a resolution below 1 %.

Figure 9: Forward tracking efficiency (a) as a function of transverse momentum (p_T) and track momentum resolution as a function of momentum (b).

2.5 Forward tracking without UT

For the beginning of the 2022 data taking, the Upstream Tracker is not yet available. Therefore, the forward tracking should be adapted to reconstruct tracks using only VELO and SciFi information. As mentioned in the previous sections, the UT provides a first momentum estimate and a charge measurement of particles.

This is very important to reduce the search windows size and, as a consequence, the number of triplet combinations. To perform the forward tracking using VELO tracks as input only, a minimum momentum is chosen to limit the search window size. For this algorithm, the focus is on long tracks with momentum greater than 5 GeV and transverse momentum greater than 1 GeV. Both charge assumptions are tested opening double-sided search windows in the X direction, as charged particles are bent by the dipole magnet only in the XZ plane (see Figure 10).

VELO input tracks are extrapolated as a straight lines to the SciFi layers to find a central point from which two search windows are opened, representing the two charge assumptions. A small 1 cm overlap between the two windows avoids to lose efficiency for very high momentum tracks.

Figure 10: Forward tracking without UT scheme. The double-sided search window strategy allows to test both charge particle assumptions.

Triplets are then formed with the same technique explained in section 2.4, combining hits in search windows with the same charge and seed assumptions. The next steps of the algorithm remain unchanged.

The goal of the algorithm is to keep physics efficiency and throughput comparable to the forward tracking “with UT”, considering the smaller subset of tracks of interest ($P > 5$ GeV and $p_T > 1$ GeV). This comparison of reconstruction efficiencies as a function of momentum and transverse momentum is shown in Figure 11. The throughput is going to be discussed in the next section 3. The greater number of triplet combinations causes an increase of the ghost rate compared to the forward tracking version with UT (see Figure 12).

Figure 11: Forward tracking efficiency (a) as a function of momentum and (b) transverse momentum (p_T).

Figure 12: Forward tracking ghost rate (a) as a function of momentum and (b) transverse momentum (p_T).

Figure 13: Forward tracking momentum resolution as a function of momentum.

2.6 Kalman fit

Performing a Kalman fit on the reconstructed tracks improves the estimate of important physical parameters, as momentum and track's impact parameter. LHCb's nominal Kalman filter uses a Runge-Kutta extrapolator with detailed detector description to precisely estimate noise due to multiple scattering and energy loss. To increase throughput and limit memory overhead, these calculations can be replaced by parametrizations. The default HLT1 Kalman fit features a VELO-only parametrization, performing a backward VELO track fit using the momentum estimate from the forward tracking. The impact parameter resolution and χ^2 for various implementations of the Kalman fit are shown in Figure 14.

3 Throughput

Throughput is a crucial topic when discussing the HLT1 performance. The first high level trigger at LHCb needs to take care of an 30 MHz input rate, which must be reduced by a factor 30 to proceed to HLT2. The Allen throughput per different CPU or GPU cards is presented in Figure 15. The chart shows performances with the default "with UT" sequence and a sequence where no UT information is used (i.e. no VELO-UT tracking and Forward tracking with no UT). The NVIDIA RTX A5000 was chosen as the default GPU card for data taking. The results are comparable between the "with UT" and "no UT" sequences, keeping in mind that the "no UT" sequence only reconstruct a subset of all long tracks ($P > 5 \text{ GeV}$ and $p_T > 1 \text{ GeV}$). These results are very promising as, considering a single GPU throughput of around 170 kHz for the A5000

Figure 14: Impact parameter resolution and χ^2 for different implementations of the Kalman fit at HLT1. The default solution is shown in black and features a Velo-only Kalman fit taking the momentum estimate from the forward tracking. [4]

card, about 175 GPUs are needed to process the 30 MHz input rate. LHCb has 500 GPU slots available, which leaves a good amount of space for future improvements of the whole system. Allen in the first days of Run 3 is presented in Ref. [15].

Figure 15: HLT1 throughput comparison between full sequence and sequence without UT information.

4 Conclusions

The goal of LHCb's HLT1 is to reconstruct events at the LHC inelastic rate of 30 MHz. GPU technology helps performing this task by parallelizing the reconstruction over single independent events and over tracks. These proceedings focused on presenting the HLT1 tracking algorithms together with their performances. A customized algorithm presented for the first time in this document, allows performing forward tracking without UT information. Around 175 GPUs are needed to take care of the LHC input collision rate and reduce it by a factor 30 for the next steps of the data flow. All the aforementioned characteristics allow HLT1 to be ready to face the next LHCb's data taking with good expected physics performance.

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Fast and flexible data structures for the LHCb Run 3 software trigger

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ABSTRACT

Starting in 2022, the upgraded LHCb detector will collect data with a pure software trigger. In its first stage, reducing the rate from 30MHz to about 1MHz, GPUs are used to reconstruct and trigger on B and D meson topologies and high- p_T objects in the event. In its second stage, a CPU farm is used to reconstruct the full event and perform candidate selections, which are persisted for offline use with an output rate of about 10 GB/s. Fast data processing, flexible and custom-designed data structures tailored for SIMD architectures and efficient storage of the intermediate data at various steps of the processing pipeline onto persistent media, e.g. tapes, is essential to guarantee the full physics program of LHCb. In these proceedings, we will present the event model and data persistency developments for the trigger of LHCb in Run 3. Particular emphasize will be given to the novel software-design aspects with respect to the Run 1+2 data taking, the performance improvements which can be achieved and the experience of restructuring a major part of the reconstruction software in a large HEP experiment.

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1 The LHCb upgrade

In the last years, the LHCb detector[1] has been upgraded to run at a five times higher instantaneous luminosity (\mathcal{L}) than during Run 1+2 of the LHC, corresponding to $\mathcal{L} = 2 \cdot 10^{33} \text{ cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$. All tracking detectors and most of the readout electronics of the subdetectors have been replaced[2, 3, 4]. The change in hardware is also reflected by a change in the trigger strategy: for Run 3, starting in 2022, LHCb will use a pure software trigger, processing events at the 30 MHz non-empty bunch-crossing rate[5]. The first stage of the software trigger, HLT1, uses a set of GPU cards to perform a partial event reconstruction[6, 7, 8]. HLT2, the second stage of the software trigger, employs a farm of CPU servers to fully reconstruct the event with offline quality and perform an event selection, given an input rate of about 1 MHz and an output data rate of about 10 GB/s[9, 10].

In order to cope with the high data rate and the throughput requirements, the HLT2 event model was rewritten to use modern software paradigms such as SIMD (single instruction, multiple data) instructions. Its different building blocks and the performance will be explained in the following sections.

2 Introduction to the LHCb event model

The LHCb event model consists of all classes, implemented in C++, that represent the data flow from the detector raw banks to the charged and neutral particles used for data analysis. It is used to pass information between the algorithms in the reconstruction chain and to consistently write and read information from and to files. In Run 1+2 of the LHC, the LHCb event model used so-called “keyed containers” where every object in a container is identified by a key. These containers were implemented as array of structures (AOS) leading to slow data access in parallel-processing environments. Additionally, the keyed containers held pointers to objects they contained, making memory allocation and de-allocation slow.

For Run 3 of the LHC, the pure software trigger of LHCb required a redesign of the event model to reach the desired throughput. The new model stores the data in an Struct-of-Arrays (SOA) layout to be able to take advantage of SIMD (single input, multiple data) instructions on CPUs. The memory layout of AOS and SOA structures can be seen in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: A comparison of AOS and SOA layouts. Taken from Ref. [11].

While developing the new event model, several key points for the event reconstruction, but also for the analysis of particle decays, have been taken into account. They include having flexible data structures that can be grown and shrunk at run time using dynamic memory allocation, but also the possibility of traversing decay trees for the analysis of multi-staged particle decays. In order to reach a high computational speed, the model needs to allow easy vectorisation[12, 13, 14, 15]. At the same time, the new model needs to be compatible with the old event model also during the development phase to not break the workflow of the full reconstruction sequence and for quality assurance.

3 SOA collections

An SOA collection is a dynamically-resizeable collection of arrays in an SOA layout. Each array or field is represented by a tag which carries all the information about the field: its type, its packed representation for offline storage, etc... For example, a simple track* collection can be created with:

```
// Define tags:
struct Momentum : float_field {};
struct Index : int_field {};
struct LHCbID : lhcbid_field {};
struct Hits : vector_field<struct_field<Index, LHCbID>> {};

// Define collection:
struct Tracks :
    SOACollection <Tracks, Momentum, Hits>{};
```

with `Momentum` the absolute momentum of the track, `LHCbID` a unique identifier for a charged cluster on a track, `Index` the index of the LHCbID on the track and `Hits` a class representing the collection of charged clusters on the track. The design goal of SOA collections is to provide a user friendly structure, replacing an AOS structure such as `std::vector<Track>`, that allows for efficient vectorization.

Access to the individual tags is provided via proxies, where the specific SIMD[†] or scalar backends can be chosen at compile time, with an automated detection of the largest vector width available on the specific architecture. A proxy therefore represents a chunk of N objects in the collection where one object, e.g. a track, is a slice through the collection.

Elements to the collection can be easily added to the end, similarly to a `std::vector`, with the possibility of masking some elements, i.e. not actually adding them. This allows for selecting some objects while discarding others in parallel, e.g. when applying track quality or momentum requirements.

```
// Push N elements to the end of tracks, masking some
// Set the momentum of the track
auto proxy = tracks.emplace_back <simd>(mask);
proxy.field<Momentum>().set(momentum);

// Iterate over tracks N elements at a time
for (const auto& proxy : tracks.simd())
    auto momentum = proxy.get<Momentum>();
```

The same operations in scalar:

```
// Push 1 element to the end of tracks, possibly masking it
// Set the momentum of the track
auto proxy = tracks.emplace_back <scalar>(mask);
proxy.field<Momentum>().set(momentum);

// Iterate over tracks one at a time
for (const auto& proxy : tracks.scalar())
    auto momentum = proxy.get<Momentum>();
```

*A track represents the trajectory of a charged particle.

[†]SIMD is used in the following for all architectures which provide a vector width larger than 1.

4 Connecting SOA Collections

4.1 Zipping

In the transient event store (TES)[16], which is used to pass objects from one algorithm to the next, data objects need to be constant to allow safe memory allocation for multi-threading. However during the event reconstruction, more information can become available for some objects which are already in the TES. For example, after tracks are reconstructed, particle identification (PID) algorithms are executed, providing additional information for these tracks. Instead of making a copy of the objects in the TES, two methods can be used to connect the new information to the original object. The first is using ‘zipping’, which is similar to python `zip()`. A zip is a set of SOA collections of the same size that can be iterated as one and carries the information on how to iterate and access the collection, i.e. the actual SIMD backend and the proxy behaviour. An example of a possible zip between tracks and PID information can be seen in Fig. 2. Zips only keep pointers to existing containers and do not own any memory. An (example) zip with tracks and PIDs can be created with and iterated over with:

```
auto zipped = make_zip<simd>(tracks, PIDs);
for (const auto& zipproxy : zipped).simd() {
    auto momentum = zipproxy.get<Momentum>(); // from tracks
    auto pid = zipproxy.get<pid>(); // from PIDs
}
```

The fact that the code for looping over an SOACollection or a zip of SOACollections is identical leads to increased code flexibility.

Figure 2: An example zip combining track, particle ID and RICH PID to a charged particle. Taken from Ref. [17].

4.2 Relation tables

Zipping only works if both SOA collections have the same size and there exists a one-to-one correspondence between the individual entries in the SOA collections. However, there are situations where this is not the case, i.e. two tracks could both point to the same calorimeter cluster.

The second method to add information to an existing object are therefore ‘relations’. Relations connect elements in a collection to something else, which can be another collection. An additional weight information can be added to each relation. SOA Relations are SOA Collections representing relations between two SOA Collections. For example a relation can be used between particles and their primary vertices with:

```

struct TracksPVsRelWithWeight:
    RelationTable2D<Tracks, PVs, Weight>{};
TracksPVsRelWithWeight table {tracks, pvs};
auto proxy = table.emplace_back<simd>();
proxy.set(tracks.indices(), pvs.indices(), weight);

```

5 SIMD Wrappers

The efficient use of SIMD instructions relies on using “intrinsic” for vector operations, which depend on the architecture and instruction set used (x86, ARM; SSE, AVX). In order to allow for a consistent use of vector operations, an easy switching between the backends and a more familiar look-and-feel similar to the scalar instructions formerly used in the LHCb code, wrapper classes for commonly used intrinsics, called `SIMDWrapper` were introduced at LHCb[18]. The instruction set is fixed at compile time, by selecting an architecture using compiler flags and target, to allow the compiler to do more optimizations. Given that changing the architecture during runtime is unlikely, this limitation does not have a negative impact for the LHCb software. The wrapper is fully integrated into the LHCb software and templated when possible to have only one implementation for all backends. Also common math functions and matrix operations are defined for all architectures to allow easy switching from one to another. An example for the function to find the minimum is given below:

```

// scalar
scalar::float_v min( scalar::float_v lhs, scalar::float_v rhs ) {
    return std::min( lhs.data, rhs.data );
}
// neon
neon::float_v min( neon::float_v lhs, neon::float_v rhs ) {
    return vminq_f32( lhs, rhs );
}
// avx
avx::float_v min( avx::float_v lhs, avx::float_v rhs ) {
    return _mm256_min_ps( lhs, rhs );
}

```

with `scalar::float_v` a float with vector width one, `neon::float_v` a float on the ARM architecture, `vminq_f32` the function to find the minimum between two ARM float numbers, `avx::float_v` a float in the AVX instruction set and `_mm256_min_ps` the function to find the minimum between two AVX float numbers.

6 Throughput Oriented (ThOr) selections

In Run 2, the event reconstruction at LHCb was about 70% and the selections were about 30% of the time spent in HLT2. This is expected to be similar in Run 3. Currently, more than 1000 exclusive HLT2 lines are being tested, each performing selections (cuts, vertex fitting, combinations etc...) on basic particles. In order to benefit from the speed improvement provided by SIMD instructions and the usage of SOA collections also in selections, a new framework was developed simultaneously for the old and the new SOA-based event models.

In order to select interesting decays in trigger lines, functors (i.e. function objects) are used. The so-called Throughput Oriented (ThOr) functors, are designed to be agnostic about the input and output type to be flexible on what they operate on. A significant gain in speed is achieved when using SIMD instructions on SOA containers compared to the old implementation as seen in Table 1. Additional speed is gained by using a functor cache instead of Just-In-Time compilation: This means that functors, which are defined in `python`, are compiled into a cache during the build process to be then used directly in the application without further interpretation. To simplify user experience, functors are templated and are using `SIMDwrappers`, so the code is the same for every architecture and no specialization is needed at the functor level.

Implementation	$D^+ \rightarrow K^+\pi^+\pi^-$ execution time
CombineParticles	256 μ s
NBodyDecays	77.1 μ s
ThorParticleCombiner	38.8 μ s
ThOrCombiner Scalar	10.2 μ s
ThOrCombiner SSE	7.5 μ s
ThOrCombiner AVX2	6.9 μ s

Table 1: A benchmark comparing the timing of the reconstruction of a $D^+ \rightarrow K^+\pi^+\pi^-$ particle decay, using different algorithms to perform the particle combination. CombineParticles and NBodyDecays use the legacy framework from Run 1+2; ThorParticleCombiner uses functors, but still the old data structures; ThOrCombiner uses SOA structures with different vector widths. Taken from Ref. [17].

7 Persistency

The final step of the event reconstruction and the selection of candidates is the persistency of the data for future use. In the AOS event model, this is done in two steps: filtering what needs to be persisted and creating persistent representations i.e., conveying the data to more basic data structures. The SOA collections are already mostly in a format that is ready to be persisted so the second step is simpler. While creating the collection, each tag can be customized for how and if it is persisted and versioning can be introduced. For the example below, one field is defined to be packed as float, one field is not to be persisted at all, and one field is to be persisted only for the newest versions of the collection.

```
// Define tags :
struct Momentum : float_field {
using packer_t = SOAPackFloatAs <short,
                                std::ratio<1, 100 > >;
};
struct Unwanted : int_field {
    using packer_t = SOADontPack ;
};
struct OpsIForgotThisField : int_field {
using packer_t =
    SOAPackIfVersionNewerOrEqual<1, SOAPackNumeric <int>>;
};
// Define collection :
struct Tracks : SOACollection<Tracks,Momentum,
                             Unwanted, OpsIForgotThisField> {};
```

8 Throughput improvements in the HLT1 prototype sequence

A prototype for the HLT1 trigger was implemented on CPU in parallel to the GPU prototype[19]. It featured most of the improvements explained in these proceedings, most importantly the SOA Collection and a widespread use of SIMD instructions. The HLT2 trigger uses same event model as the HLT1 and benefits from the same improvements mentioned in these proceedings.

In order to test the impact of using SIMD instructions compared to scalar instructions, the sequence was once run with the AVX2 instruction set, and once with scalar instructions, while keeping the event model the same. The throughput was about twice when using vector instructions compared to scalar instructions.

A historical overview over the improvements achieved using the new event model, using SIMD instructions and having improved reconstruction algorithms can be seen in Fig. 3. It shows that thanks to a concentrated

effort on all three points, the throughput could be improved by about a factor 4, without compromising the reconstruction of physics quantities.

9 Conclusions

For Run 3 of the LHC, the LHCb collaboration implemented a new event model for the second stage of the software trigger, HLT2, using an SOA layout, native usage of SIMD instructions and more flexibility. This results in an increased throughput and allows to run more than 1000 trigger lines with a full offline-quality reconstruction, without the need for any post-processing. This event model therefore is well suited for the coming decade of data taking of the LHCb experiment.

Figure 3: Evolution of the upgrade LHCb HLT1 throughput of the CPU prototype between December 2018 and April 2020. The period between August 2019 and February 2020 has been cut out as there were little changes to the throughput. More details about the indicated optimizations can be found in Ref. [20].

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1 Real-time alignment procedure at the LHCb experiment for Run 3

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6 ABSTRACT

7 The LHCb detector at the LHC is a general purpose detector in the forward
8 region with a focus on studying decays of c- and b-hadrons. For Run 3 of the
9 LHC, LHCb will take data at an instantaneous luminosity of $2 \times 10^{33} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

10 To cope with the harsher data taking conditions, LHCb will deploy a purely
11 software based trigger with a 30 MHz input rate. The software trigger at LHCb
12 is composed of two stages: in the first stage the selection is based on a partial
13 event reconstruction, while in the second stage a full event reconstruction is used.
14 This gives room to perform a real-time alignment and calibration after the first
15 trigger stage, allowing to have the most precise detector alignment in the second
16 stage of the trigger. The framework and the procedure for a real-time alignment
17 of the LHCb detector in Run 3 are discussed from both the technical and
18 operational point of view. Specific challenges of this strategy and foreseen
19 performance are presented.

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1 Introduction

The LHCb Run 3 detector [1], currently being commissioned to take data during Run 3 of the Large Hadron Collider (LHC), is a general-purpose detector in the forward direction. The LHCb Run 3 detector employs a purely software-based trigger processing events at the non-empty proton-proton collision rate of 30 MHz. During Run 2, an alignment and calibration procedure in real-time has been pioneered [2]. This approach is critical for Run 3, as it is necessary for pure selections, which reduce the final output bandwidth of the trigger. In addition, having the most precise alignment available at the trigger stage ensures a fully consistent data processing chain [3].

The tracking system of the LHCb Run 3 detector providing a measurement of the momentum of charged particles consists of the Vertex Locator (VELO) [4] around the interaction region, the Upstream Tracker (UT) before, and the Scintillating Fibre tracker (SciFi) [5] after the magnet. The proton-proton interactions points (PVs) are reconstructed using tracks in the VELO. The muon system at the end of the detector reconstructs and identifies muons. Particle identification is provided by two ring-imaging Cherenkov detectors (RICH1 and RICH2) and the electronic and hadronic calorimeters (ECAL and HCAL).

2 Alignment tasks and performance

The alignment procedure consists of aligning the tracking system and the RICH mirrors. The alignment of the tracking detectors (VELO, UT, SciFi, Muon) is performed using reconstructed tracks by minimizing the χ^2 of all tracks with respect to the alignment parameters α , with

$$\begin{aligned}\chi^2 &= r^T V^{-1} r \\ r &= m - h(x, \alpha),\end{aligned}\tag{1}$$

where r are the residuals of the tracks defined as the difference between measurements m and the track model h , which depends on the track parameters x and the alignment parameters α , and V is the measurement covariance matrix. The alignment parameters describe the three translation (T_x, T_y, T_z) and three rotation (R_x, R_y, R_z) degrees of freedom of each alignable detector element.

The minimization is performed in an iterative procedure using the Newton–Raphson method by calculating the first and second derivatives of χ^2 with respect to the alignment parameters α . A new set of alignment parameters α_1 is obtained by

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{d\chi^2}{d\alpha} &= 2 \sum_{tracks} \frac{dr^T}{d\alpha} V^{-1} r, \\ \frac{d^2\chi^2}{d\alpha^2} &= 2 \sum_{tracks} \frac{dr^T}{d\alpha} V^{-1} R V^{-1} \frac{dr}{d\alpha}, \\ \alpha_1 &= \alpha_0 - \left(\frac{d^2\chi^2}{d\alpha^2} \right)^{-1} \bigg|_{\alpha_0} \frac{d\chi^2}{d\alpha} \bigg|_{\alpha_0},\end{aligned}\tag{2}$$

where α_0 are the initial alignment parameters and R is the covariance matrix of the residuals. The convergence criterion is defined by $\Delta\chi^2 < 25$ for each mode and $\frac{\Delta\chi_{tot}^2}{ndof} < 4$ for the total change in χ^2 and total number of degrees of freedom $ndof$, where the change in χ^2 can be calculated from the difference in alignment parameters

$$\Delta\chi^2 = -\Delta\alpha^T Cov(\alpha)^{-1} \Delta\alpha.\tag{3}$$

This procedure uses the same track states obtained from a Kalman filter as are used in the track reconstruction, ensuring consistency between alignment and reconstruction [6]. Further, it allows to add vertex and mass constraints [7] to improve the alignment quality.

The typical samples used for the tracker alignment during Run 2 consisted of 50000 minimum bias events for the VELO alignment, where proton-proton collisions as well as proton-gas interactions were used. The

Figure 1: Difference between x positions of the reconstructed primary vertices reconstructed with tracks in each VELO half [8].

57 sample used for the downstream tracking system was around 70000 $\mathcal{D}^0 \rightarrow K\pi$ decays and around 200000
 58 $J/\psi \rightarrow \mu^+\mu^-$ decays for the muon system alignment, which are expected to be collected within minutes and
 59 hours respectively in Run 3.

60 VELO alignment

61 The alignment of the VELO is of particular importance, as it is moved from a safe position while the LHC
 62 beams are injected (29 mm distance from the beamline), to a distance of 5.1 mm to the beamline when stable
 63 beams are declared.

64 To check the quality of the VELO alignment, the difference of the position of reconstructed PVs using
 65 only tracks in the left and right VELO halves can be used. A distribution not centered around zero would
 66 indicate a relative misalignment of the two VELO halves. The difference in x with a large initial misalignment
 67 and after the alignment procedure has converged, obtained from simulation, is shown in Fig 1.

68 To evaluate the precision of the VELO alignment, studies on simulated samples of a perfectly aligned
 69 detector are performed. A random initial misalignment is generated, reflecting the expected misalignment at
 70 the beginning of data-taking estimated by the detector survey accuracy, and the iterative alignment procedure
 71 is performed until it has converged. By repeating this with independent sets of initial misalignments, the
 72 final values of the alignment parameters can be studied. The bias and precision of the procedure can be
 73 estimated by the mean and width of the residual misalignment for each alignment parameter. The results
 74 of this study for the x -translation degree of freedom of the modules of the left VELO half are shown in
 75 Fig. 2. The initial misalignment, drawn from a Gaussian distribution with zero mean and a width of $5\ \mu\text{m}$, is
 76 compensated for by the alignment procedure, which is seen to be unbiased and to have a precision of about
 77 $1\ \mu\text{m}$, similar to what was achieved in Run 2 [9].

78 SciFi alignment

79 The alignment of the SciFi is essential to achieve the best-possible momentum resolution of charged-particle
 80 tracks. The first studies of the expected accuracy of the SciFi alignment are performed by adding a random
 81 input misalignment for the T_x degree of freedom to each SciFi module before executing the alignment
 82 procedure. The input misalignments are drawn from a Gaussian distribution with mean zero and a width
 83 of $100\ \mu\text{m}$. The input and residual misalignments after running the alignment procedure are shown in
 84 Fig. 3. The alignment can compensate for the input misalignments, reducing the standard deviation of the
 85 alignment parameters to $50\ \mu\text{m}$. This presents one of the first studies of the accuracy of the SciFi alignment.
 86 It is expected to further be improved by using a larger sample size and adding additional constraints in
 87 the alignment procedure. In particular, employing mass constraints, for example by using the abundant

Figure 2: The input (left) and residual (right) misalignments for the T_x degree of freedom of the modules of the left VELO half [10]. Each entry corresponds to a toy with a randomly generated input misalignment and a residual misalignment after the alignment procedure has converged.

Figure 3: The input x-translation misalignment for the SciFi modules (left) and the residual misalignment (right) after running the alignment procedure [10].

88 $D^0 \rightarrow K\pi$ and $J/\psi \rightarrow \mu^+\mu^-$ decays, can improve the quality of the SciFi alignment.

89 RICH mirror alignment

90 The RICH mirror alignment is performed by creating histograms of the difference ($\Delta\theta_C$) of each detected
 91 photon's reconstructed Cherenkov angle and its expected Cherenkov angle, inferred from the intersection
 92 point of the charged particle with the RICH material and its measured momentum, in bins of the azimuthal
 93 angle (ϕ) about the projected track position on the photodetector plane. By fitting the $\Delta\theta_C$ distribution
 94 and correcting for deviations of its mean value from zero in each ϕ bin, the RICH mirrors can be aligned.
 95 An example of a distribution before and after the mirror are alignment is shown in Fig .4.

96 3 Real-time alignment and calibration

97 The real-time alignment and calibration is performed at the beginning of each LHC fill. The software trigger
 98 consist of two stages (HLT1 and HLT2) [11]. The first stage HLT1 employs a partial event reconstruction.
 99 Dedicated trigger lines are used to select events, which serve as input sample for the alignment procedure.
 100 Events selected by HLT1 are stored on a buffer. This allows the collection of enough events and gives
 101 enough time for the alignment and calibration procedure to run before HLT2 is executed. The HLT2

Figure 4: $\Delta\theta_C$ plotted as a function of the azimuthal angle ϕ for one side of the RICH 2 detector. The left-hand plot is prior to alignment, and shows a dependency of the angle θ_C on the angle ϕ . The right-hand plot is after the alignment correction, and $\Delta\theta_C$ is uniform in ϕ [12].

Figure 5: Real-time alignment and calibration tasks for Run 3, executed for each fill. The ordering from left to right indicates the expected amount of time each task takes, from shortest to longest.

102 performs a full event reconstruction including also particle identification information to make the final
 103 decision which events to keep. In this way, HLT2 can use the most recent and most precise alignment and
 104 calibration constants to achieve a reconstruction and selection performance with the best precision. This
 105 makes re-running the reconstruction offline unnecessary and results in cleaner selections with less background
 106 contributions, reducing the output bandwidth of HLT2. As the alignment of the tracking detectors can be
 107 executed within a short amount of time (order of minutes), their updated constants are also propagated to
 108 HLT1.

109 The foreseen real-time alignment and calibration tasks are illustrated in Fig. 5. The tracking system
 110 and the RICH mirrors are aligned using the procedure described in the previous section, the calibration is
 111 described below. After the alignment procedure has converged, it is checked if an update is necessary by
 112 comparing the previous and updated constants. If the differences are not significant, the old constants are
 113 kept to avoid changing the constants too often due to statistical fluctuations. For illustration, the variation
 114 of the x - and y -translation constants for the VELO halves during the 2018 data-taking period is shown in
 115 Fig. 6. The VELO is expected to have frequent updates due to the movement during the closing procedure
 116 at the start of each fill.

117 To perform the tracking alignment on the event-filter farm, where the HLT2 processes are executed, and to
 118 achieve better timing performance, the execution of the alignment procedure is split into two parts - *Analyzer*
 119 and *Iterator*. The Analyzer reads the current alignment constants, reconstructs tracks and calculates the
 120 derivatives from Eq. 2 and saves them to a binary file. Since the event processing is independent, the

Figure 6: Stability of the translation along the x-axis (T_x) and along the y-axis (T_y) alignment constants of the VELO halves during 2018 data taking. Each point is obtained running the real-time alignment procedure and shows the difference between the initial and updated alignment constants [14].

121 Analyzer can be split up over multiple processes and threads. Once the Analyzer processes have finished,
 122 the Iterator collects the derivative files and performs the minimization step. New constants are written out
 123 and an update is triggered if necessary. The RICH alignment is organized in a similar way.

124 For Run 3, the Analyzer can utilize the multi-threaded reconstruction. This has the advantage that the
 125 alignment can be executed using fewer nodes of the event-filter farm. For each node in the event-builder
 126 farm (163 in total), there will be one node on the event-filter farm prioritizing the Analyzer tasks. This will
 127 make the distribution of the input data over the Analyzer nodes easier, as one event-builder node provides
 128 its collected sample to one Analyzer node. Due to the improvements in reconstruction throughput from
 129 multi-threading, it is expected that the alignment will run on a similar time-scale as in Run 2, even though
 130 fewer nodes are employed.

131 The alignment task is implemented as finite-state machine steered by the central Run Control. A scheme
 132 of the workflow is shown in Fig. 7. At the start, both Analyzer and Iterator processes are launched and the
 133 Analyzers begin with the reconstruction, while the Iterator is idling. Once the reconstruction and writing of
 134 the files with the derivatives is completed, the Iterator receives a signal to collect the files and to perform the
 135 minimization. Then it checks for convergence and triggers the continuation or completion of the alignment
 136 procedure. Once convergence is achieved, the new constants are compared with the initial ones. If the
 137 difference between them is significant, the updated constants are added to a database to be picked up by
 138 HLT2 (and HLT1 in case of the constants of the tracking system). The limits, which trigger an update,
 139 need to be carefully chosen to avoid too many updates from statistical fluctuations while still being sensitive
 140 to small misalignments. The alignment of the tracking system is expected to be completed within minutes.
 141 The RICH mirror alignment, which is not necessary for HLT1, can take more time, in the order of hours.
 142 Updates to the alignment constants of the muon stations are expected to be rare and only to be necessary
 143 after a technical intervention.

144 The real-time calibration consists of evaluating the refractive index that depends on the RICH tempera-
 145 ture and gas pressure, which is evaluated on a per run basis*, and an absolute calibration of the ECAL high
 146 voltage, which was updated once per month during Run 2. For the ECAL, the calibration is performed by
 147 analyzing the $\pi^0 \rightarrow \gamma\gamma$ decay mass distribution in each calorimeter cell. From the shift of the π^0 mass peak
 148 from the known position the needed adjustment of the high voltage to compensate the aging of the detector
 149 can be estimated. This allows to optimize the calorimeter performance, as illustrated in Fig. 8 for Run 2
 150 data, and its stability over time.

*a LHCb run corresponds to up to an hour of data-taking

Figure 7: Illustration of the Analyzer and Iterator processes for the tracker alignment steered by the Run Control.

Figure 8: Invariant mass distribution for $\pi^0 \rightarrow \gamma\gamma$ candidates upon which the fine calibration algorithm is applied in Run 2. The red curve corresponds to the distribution before applying the method, while the blue curve is the final one. Values in the red (blue) box are the mean and sigma of the signal peak distribution in MeV/c² before (after) applying the fine calibration method [13].

4 Conclusions

During Run 2, a fully automated real-time alignment and calibration procedure was pioneered by the LHCb collaboration. This approach is essential for Run 3, where the trigger is purely software-based, to achieve the best possible physics performance of the experiment. The alignment procedure profits from the gains in reconstruction throughput achieved for HLT2, especially from multi-threading, ensuring that it can be executed in a timely manner. The system is currently being built up and will be tuned over time with feedback from taking real data.

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Track reconstruction at the LUXE experiment using quantum algorithms

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ABSTRACT

LUXE (Laser Und XFEL Experiment) is a proposed experiment at DESY which will study Quantum Electrodynamics (QED) in the strong-field regime, where QED becomes non-perturbative. Measuring the rate of created electron-positron pairs using a silicon pixel tracking detector is an essential ingredient to study this regime. Precision tracking of positrons traversing the four layers of the tracking detector becomes very challenging at high laser intensities due to the high rates, which can be computationally expensive for classical computers. In this work, we update our previous study of the potential of using quantum computing to reconstruct positron tracks. The reconstruction task is formulated as a quadratic unconstrained binary optimisation and is solved using simulated quantum computers and a hybrid quantum-classical algorithm, namely the variational quantum eigensolver. Different ansatz circuits and optimisers are studied. The results are discussed and compared with classical track reconstruction algorithms using a graph neural network and a combinatorial Kalman filter.

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1 Introduction

In this work, we present an update of our previous study of track reconstruction with quantum algorithms [1] at LUXE. LUXE [2] is a planned experiment at DESY in Hamburg to study the transition far into the strong-field regime of QED, where QED becomes non-perturbative. The classical non-linearity parameter,

$$\xi = \frac{m_e \mathcal{E}_L}{\omega_L \mathcal{E}_{cr}}, \quad (1)$$

where m_e is the electron mass, ω_L is the laser frequency, \mathcal{E}_L is the instantaneous laser field strength, and $\mathcal{E}_{cr} = m_e^2 c^3 / e \hbar$ is the critical field strength, known as the Schwinger limit, is used to demarcate the regime of strong-field QED in particle-laser and photon-laser interactions ($\xi \gg 1$).

To study the phenomena occurring in these interactions, a key measurement is the number of positrons generated from the Breit-Wheeler process with respect to the parameter ξ . The number of expected positrons ranges from less than 10^{-4} up to 10^6 . Both a low background rate ($< 10^{-3}$) at low ξ and a good linearity of the number of reconstructed tracks as a function of ξ are essential. For this challenging task, we explore the potential of using quantum computing for track reconstruction. Other quantum computing algorithms studied for charged particle tracking can be found in Ref. [3] and references therein.

In Fig. 1, the number of expected positrons as a function of ξ is shown for laser-photon interactions. For $\xi \gtrsim 1$, the difference between the predictions of non-perturbative and perturbative QED with respect to the number of created positrons is expected to become measurable.

Figure 1: Number of positrons per laser-photon interaction, normalised to a given laser spot size (w_0) as a function of the classical non-linearity parameter ξ for ten days of data acquisition (N_{day}), assuming a background rate of 0.01 (N_{BG}) per interaction. Predictions for full QED and purely perturbative QED are added. Error bars are dominated by statistical uncertainties. The correlated uncertainty of about 40%, as highlighted in the lower panel, arises from a 5% uncertainty on the laser intensity. Figure recreated from [2].

Positron tracks are reconstructed from energy deposits on four consecutive pixel detector layers. There is no electromagnetic field within the detector system. A brief overview of the underlying physical processes and the experimental setup is given in sections 1 and 2 of Ref. [1].

2 Data sets and selection

In this study, simulated data is used. Signal interactions at the interaction point (IP) are generated with PTARMIGAN [4], a custom Monte Carlo event generator. Positrons stemming from PTARMIGAN are propagated through a dipole magnet and through the positron tracking system using a simplified simulation. In the simplified simulation, parameters such as position and resolution of detector layers, as well as the scattering processes can be tuned to explore the impact on the reconstruction algorithm. In this study, a simplified detector geometry is used, namely four non-overlapping layers.

The used simulated data predicts future measurements of the phase-0 of LUXE for the e-laser setup for $\xi \in \{4, 5, 7\}$, which corresponds to between 2,000 and 70,000 expected positrons. The 500 particles per laser-beam interaction closest to the beamline are considered for the track reconstruction task in order to equalise the size of all used data sets. The track density increases with ξ , thus increasing the complexity of the track reconstruction task.

Our starting point for track reconstruction is either doublets or triplets of energy deposits (hits). Doublets are two connected hits from strictly consecutive layers, while triplets are composed of two doublets with one shared hit. Triplets consist of three hits from strictly consecutive layers. With respect to the beamline, an angle-based pre-selection procedure is applied to the doublets based on the experiment geometry. Triplets are formed if the angles between two doublets with one shared hit do not exceed a threshold value. In this procedure, the combinatorial triplet candidates are reduced without lowering the efficiency.

3 Methodology

Classical tracking

As a benchmark, a classical tracking approach with a combinatorial Kalman filter (CKF) technique is used. For this, a reconstruction software based on A Common Tracking Software (ACTS) toolkit [5] is employed. Triplets are used as seeds to find an initial estimate of the track parameters. This initial estimate is updated by scanning for matching hit candidates, and the measurement search is performed at the same time. Eventually, after the track finding and fitting is completed, an ambiguity-solving step is applied to remove tracks with shared hits.

Graph neural network

Another method explored in this work is the use of a graph neural network (GNN) [6, 7]. Here, hits are represented as nodes. Edges are connections between these nodes, forming doublet-like structures, called segments, and are only kept if they satisfy the pre-selection criteria. The GNN consists of an alternating EdgeNetwork and NodeNetwork and is trained on weighted examples to optimise the edge connections, thus learning which segments should be chosen to be a part of track candidates. We note that there is also a hybrid quantum-classical version of the GNN-based tracking [8], which is not examined here but could be studied in future work.

Quantum algorithm

In the quantum computing part, only triplet-level information is used for the pattern recognition task. Triplets are encoded as binary variables. A decision is then made on which triplets to keep or to discard in the subsequent track reconstruction process. An objective function is defined, called Quadratic Unconstrained Binary Optimisation (QUBO), as proposed in Ref. [9]. The goal is to minimise this objective function,

$$O = \sum_i^N \sum_{j < i} b_{ij} T_i T_j + \sum_{i=1}^N a_i T_i, \quad T_i, T_j \in \{0, 1\}, \quad (2)$$

where T_i and T_j represent triplets at the positions i and j of a possible solution vector, and a_i and b_{ij} are the QUBO coefficients.

In Eq. (2), the quadratic term describes the relation between triplets, which is quantified by the parameter b_{ij} . This parameter has a negative value if the triplets form a track candidate, a positive value if they are in conflict, and a zero value if they do not share a hit. The parameter a_i evaluates a triplet based on the angle between the two doublets that make up the triplet. In this work, we discard the linear term and focus entirely on the quadratic term.

We map the QUBO onto an Ising Hamiltonian, in order to solve it using a simulated quantum device. Finding the ground state of the Ising Hamiltonian is equivalent to minimising the QUBO and thus to finding an optimal solution to the track reconstruction task. The Ising Hamiltonian,

$$\mathcal{H} = - \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{m < n} \bar{b}_{nm} \sigma_n^x \sigma_m^x - \sum_{n=1}^N \bar{a}_n \sigma_n^x, \quad (3)$$

is solved using the Variational Quantum Eigensolver (VQE), a hybrid quantum-classical algorithm. For this task, the Qiskit [10] toolkit is employed. As a benchmark for the VQE, an analytical solution can be obtained by using the Numpy Eigensolver for small QUBOs. We use an ideal, noiseless simulation for VQE. For the optimiser, the Nakanishi-Fujii-Todo (NFT) [11] algorithm is selected.

We have improved the hyperparameters of the VQE to boost the performance compared to our previous results [1]. After comparing the results of NFT and Constrained Optimisation by Linear Approximation (COBYLA), we decided to use NFT because it performs better. The quantum circuit following Qiskit's *TwoLocal* ansatz scheme is altered from a circular entanglement scheme to a linear entanglement scheme, and the circuit depth is increased to three. The quantum circuit is shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Variational quantum circuit layout. The *TwoLocal* ansatz is used with three repetitions of R_Y and CNOT gates and an additional final rotation layer. For simplicity, only a four qubit system is shown.

To solve the QUBO, an initial guess of the solution is made, in the form of a string representation of the set of triplets, assuming values $\{0, 1\}$. For solving the QUBO in one step, the number of available qubits for the computation has to be at least the same as the number of triplets participating in the QUBO. For 500 tracks we get approximately 1500 to 3000 triplets, depending on ξ and on the parameters of our pre-selection. Since sizes of quantum devices of this magnitude are not available and simulating huge devices is computationally infeasible, the problem has to be broken down into smaller parts, called sub-QUBOs, which are solved sequentially in each iteration. A sub-QUBO size of seven is chosen. The order of triplets used in the sub-QUBO process is determined by their impact on the Hamiltonian energy. This impact is defined as the absolute difference between the original objective function and the objective function after flipping the binary representation of the triplet in the QUBO, i.e., for each triplet, the state of the triplet is flipped and the objective function is recomputed. The triplets are then ordered by their impact, from lowest to highest, and partitioned into size-7 sub-QUBOs. All the resulting sub-QUBOs are then solved sequentially. These steps are repeated until a stable solution is found. A sketch of the QUBO solving process with a focus on the sub-QUBO routine is shown in Fig. 3.

4 Results

Comparing the performance of the different track reconstruction methods is done on track level. Results are averaged over 10 bunch crossings for each ξ . Efficiency and fake rate are used as metrics. A track is defined

Figure 3: Sketch of the QUBO solving approach with focus on the sub-QUBO routine [1].

as a set of four hits of consecutive layers, which is either obtained by combining doublets and triplets into quadruplets or is found directly with the classical CKF-based tracking method. A matched track stems from exactly one particle, fake tracks from multiple particles.

The efficiency and fake rate are defined as

$$\text{Efficiency} = \frac{N_{\text{matched tracks}}}{N_{\text{generated tracks}}} \quad \text{and} \quad \text{Fake rate} = \frac{N_{\text{fake tracks}}}{N_{\text{reconstructed tracks}}}. \quad (4)$$

In Fig. 4, the efficiency and fake rate for 500 tracks are displayed as a function of the classical non-linearity parameter ξ . Conventional CKF-based tracking is used as a benchmark for efficiency and fake rate, and is compared to GNN-based tracking and VQE. The Eigensolver results are added as a benchmark for the VQE approach for a sub-QUBO size of seven.

Figure 4: Efficiency (left) and fake rate (right) as a function of ξ .

The CKF-based tracking efficiency decreases with ξ but is still performant at the highest shown track density at $\xi = 7$. The GNN-based tracking shows similar, but slightly worse performance than the CKF-based tracking. The VQE and Eigensolver deteriorate strongly at high ξ values while being comparable with CKF-based tracking and GNN at $\xi = 4$. While the performance of the GNN is known to be improved by using more training examples, the VQE performance is likely limited by the set of the QUBO parameters

a_i and b_{ij} as well as by the size of the sub-QUBOs, therefore both approaches can be further optimised. To investigate the impact of the sub-QUBO size on the performance, only the Eigensolver is used, because simulating VQE for a higher number of qubits is computationally intensive. In Fig. 5, the results for both sub-QUBO sizes is shown. Increasing the size of the sub-QUBOs from 7 to 16 does not yield an improvement in efficiency. However, the statistical uncertainty for sub-QUBO size of 16 is much smaller.

Figure 5: Efficiency (left) and fake rate (right) for 500 tracks as a function of ξ for sub-QUBO sizes 7 (Q7) and 16 (Q16).

Using customised entanglement structures may increase the performance of the VQE on the sub-QUBO level. Four different entanglement structures are compared in Fig. 6. Linear entanglement is shown in Fig. 2. circular entanglement, as used in our previous study in Ref. [1], has an additional CNOT gate, connecting the last to the first qubit. Full entanglement refers to each qubit being entangled with every other qubit. A Hamiltonian driven approach is used if qubits are only connected via a CNOT gate, i.e., if they represent triplets, which actually have a shared hit and thus an immediate connection. The Eigensolver result is an upper limit for the performance of the VQE based solving. The Hamiltonian driven entanglement shows a performance similar to the Eigensolver at low ξ , and on average, exceeds the Eigensolver performance at $\xi = 7$. This is due to the large uncertainty of the Eigensolver result for $\xi = 7$ in combination with a better random initial guess, since it is not possible for the VQE approach to achieve better efficiencies than the Eigensolver. Linear and full entanglement perform slightly worse, whereas circular entanglement shows significantly lower efficiency and higher fake rate.

Figure 6: Efficiency (left) and fake rate (right) as a function of ξ . The Eigensolver result is the upper limit of what can be achieved by employing VQE and using the sub-QUBO subroutine approach.

5 Conclusions

In this work, we updated our previous results [1] of studying a hybrid quantum-classical algorithm for track reconstruction in the LUXE experiment, as well as a GNN-based tracking approach. As a benchmark, conventional CKF-based tracking is used. With the current version, the quantum approach is less performant than GNN-based and conventional tracking, but we identified several clues for optimisation on the quantum side as well as on the classical side, which will be further investigated in the future. Especially the optimisation of the sub-QUBO routine is a strong candidate for a major improvement.

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Allen in the first days of Run 3

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ABSTRACT

The LHCb collaboration recently began commissioning an upgraded detector that will be read out at the full 30 MHz LHC event rate. Events will be reconstructed and selected in real time using a GPU-based software trigger called Allen. In this talk, I'll present the status of Allen and discuss how it is evolving as Run 3 begins. In particular, I'll focus on the process of preparing Allen to confront real data and discuss our experiences operating a GPU-based trigger in the early days of Run 3.

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1 Introduction

The primary goal of the LHCb experiment is to study decays of hadrons containing charm and bottom quarks. Figure 1 shows event rates for various Standard Model production processes at the LHC experiments in Run 3. The trigger systems of the ATLAS and CMS experiments are primarily designed to select high-energy signatures of relatively rare processes. These signatures, which include calorimeter clusters with high transverse energy (E_T) and high-momentum muon tracks, can be efficiently identified and selected using hardware-level information from single subdetector subsystems. In contrast, the b and c hadrons studied at LHCb will be produced at rates of $\mathcal{O}(1 \text{ MHz})$. Furthermore, heavy flavor hadrons decay to final-state particles with momenta similar to those of particles from the underlying event. The signature of a heavy flavor hadron decay is a decay vertex (secondary vertex) displaced from the pp collision (primary vertex). Reconstructing a displaced secondary vertex requires global information from LHCb's full charged particle tracking system. As a result, heavy flavor hadrons cannot be efficiently selected using hardware-level triggers. This is demonstrated in Figure 2, which shows the projected performance of an emulated hardware trigger at LHCb in Run 3. At a throughput of 1 MHz, hadronic b -hadron decays are selected with about 10% efficiency, while hadronic c -hadron decays are selected with about 5% efficiency. To solve this challenge, the LHCb collaboration is analyzing the full LHC event rate in real time using a software trigger.

Figure 1: Event rate estimates for various Standard Model processes at the LHC in Run 3 [1].

Figure 2: Selection performance of a hypothetical Run 3 low-level trigger that selects events based on the presence of a single high- E_T HCAL cluster [2].

The LHCb software trigger is split into two stages called “HLT1” and “HLT2”. Data is read out from the detector at an event rate of about 30 MHz and passed to HLT1. HLT1 selects events at a rate of about 1 MHz, which are then passed on for further processing. The LHCb HLT1 has been implemented on GPUs in the Allen software package [3, 4]. Allen is the first complete high-throughput GPU trigger for a high-energy physics experiment. In this contribution, I’ll show how Allen has evolved from a prototype to an operational software trigger over the last two years. I’ll also present some of Allen’s new features and discuss how the Allen team is approaching the challenges of collecting real data as Run 3 begins.

2 The Allen Project

Allen is LHCb’s GPU-based first level software trigger. Named for Frances E. Allen, Allen is available as both a standalone application and as part of the LHCb software stack. Allen can be built for CPUs and GPUs. Both NVIDIA and AMD GPUs are supported using the CUDA and HIP frameworks, respectively.

Allen was originally designed to perform a partial reconstruction of charged particles in HLT1 as described in Ref. [2]. The upgraded LHCb detector is shown in Figure 3 with the subdetectors used in the baseline reconstruction sequence highlighted. Allen must decode data from the Vertex Locator (VELO) [5], Upstream Tracker (UT) [6], Scintillating Fibre (SciFi) [6], and Muon [7] detectors and cluster this data into hits. VELO hits are used to create tracks using the Search by Triplet algorithm [8]. VELO tracks are then propagated to the UT and VELO-UT tracks are constructed using the Compass algorithm [9]. VELO-UT tracks are then extrapolated to the SciFi and are used to define windows to search for SciFi tracks. Reconstructed VELO-UT-SciFi tracks are then extrapolated to the Muon detector stations, which are used to identify muons [10]. The VELO segments of reconstructed tracks are fit using a parameterized Kalman filter [3] and are used to reconstruct secondary vertices. Events are selected based on the properties of tracks and secondary vertices. In addition, Allen also decodes and reconstructs data from the electromagnetic calorimeter (ECAL).

Figure 3: The upgraded LHCb detector. The detector systems used in the baseline HLT1 reconstruction sequence described in Ref. [2] are highlighted in color.

The Run 3 LHCb data acquisition pipeline is shown in Figure 4. The Allen implementation of HLT1 will run on GPUs placed on Event Builder nodes, resulting in a large decrease of data volume transferred between the Event Builder nodes and the CPU farm where HLT2 runs. Furthermore, GPUs can provide more computing power per unit cost than CPUs. Consequently, a GPU-based HLT1 offers many opportunities for cost savings [13]. In addition, Allen is fast enough to allow for additional features to be added to the

HLT1 reconstruction sequence. Because of these cost savings and the potential to expand LHCb’s physics program, the LHCb collaboration adopted Allen as its first level software trigger for Run 3.

Figure 4: Sketch of the LHCb data acquisition system for Run 3, including the GPU-based HLT1 [11]. All numbers related to the dataflow are taken from Refs. [2] and [12].

3 New features in Allen

Many LHCb analyses require reconstructing and identifying electrons. Electrons are identified using the ECAL, which was not used in HLT1 in Runs 1 and 2. ECAL reconstruction has now been implemented in Allen. This includes decoding data from the ECAL, clustering ECAL cells, and matching ECAL clusters to charged tracks. In addition, VELO track trajectories are used to match electron candidates to ECAL clusters produced by bremsstrahlung radiation. ECAL reconstruction will improve Allen’s ability to select final states including electrons and photons such as those used in studies of lepton flavor universality [14] and direct searches for new particles [15, 16].

Most events selected by Allen are selected using inclusive one- and two-track selection algorithms based on neural network (NN) classifiers. These inclusive NNs are trained using simulated heavy flavor decays to select displaced and high-momentum tracks and secondary vertices. Very little training signal is available at large decay times, and backgrounds can be produced by particles interacting with the detector material. As a result, NN performance tends to suffer for particles with large decay times, as shown in Figure 5. To overcome this limitation, methods have been developed to constrain classifiers to produce monotonically increasing responses in a given set of variables [17]. In addition, detector conditions may fluctuate during data taking. In Runs 1 and 2, LHCb accounted for this by discretizing variables used as inputs to selection algorithms [18]. A similar effect can be achieved by limiting the gradient of the classifier response. This has been implemented in so-called “Lipschitz NNs” [17]. The performance of an unconstrained NN is compared to a monotonic BDT and a monotonic Lipschitz NN in Figure 5. The one- and two-track inclusive selections in Allen now both use monotonic Lipschitz NNs.

When Allen was adopted for use in Run 3 in 2020, it had achieved throughput of about 70 kHz on a GeForce RTX 2080 Ti GPU [3]. Allen has achieved dramatic speedups since then, which are due to detailed profiling of GPU occupancy and improvements in compiler configuration. Figure 6 shows updated throughput measurements. When the new features discussed above are included, Allen has still achieved speedups of around 50% on the same card since 2020.

Figure 5: Selection efficiency as a function of decay time for (left) an example unconstrained NN, (middle) a boosted decision tree classifier constrained to have a monotonically increasing performance as a function of decay time, and (right) a NN constrained to have a monotonic response and to satisfy a Lipschitz condition that limits the magnitude of its gradient. From Ref. [17]

Figure 6: Allen throughput on various GPUs and CPUs.

4 Early data taking challenges

The entire LHCb tracking system has been replaced for Run 3. The UT is not expected to be in place until December. The UT provides a charge determination and an initial momentum estimate for charged tracks that can be used to define search windows for hits in the SciFi. Reconstructing tracks without the UT required the development of new tracking algorithms. Two such algorithms have been implemented in Allen and are described in Ref. [19].

In addition to pp collisions, LHCb will simultaneously record data in fixed target mode using the System for Measuring the Overlap with Gas (SMOG) [20]. Figure 7 shows the VELO tracking efficiency as a function of the primary vertex position along the beam axis. Allen is able to simultaneously reconstruct pp and p-gas events with negligible loss of performance.

Allen will also be used to collect PbPb data in November, 2022. Figure 8 shows the LHCb tracking efficiency for charged particles traversing both the VELO and SciFi detectors as a function of the number

Figure 7: VELO tracking efficiency as a function of primary vertex z position for various pp and SMOG2 data-taking scenarios [21]. The pp interaction region is centered at $z = 0$, while the SMOG2 cell is centered near $z = -400$ mm.

of hits in the SciFi detector. In the high-occupancy environment of PbPb collisions, the SciFi detector will saturate, leading to poor tracking performance. As a result, Allen will need to use a new trigger strategy for PbPb data taking, which is currently under development.

Figure 8: SciFi track reconstruction efficiency as a function of the number of hits in the SciFi for reconstructible tracks [21].

5 First data

Allen has been fully integrated into the LHCb data acquisition system using RTX A5000 GPUs and was used to collect cosmic ray data based on ECAL activity beginning in May. Since the end of May, Allen has been used to select pp collisions data. A histogram of selected bunch crossing IDs from pp collisions is shown in Figure 9. The histogram shows sharp peaks corresponding to filled LHC bunches. This demonstrates

that Allen is successfully selecting real pp collisions. Since early July, Allen has processed data from $\sqrt{s} = 13.6$ TeV pp collisions. To date, Allen has processed pp collisions at an event rate of about 27 MHz. Figure 10 shows the Allen selection rate for events with at least one ECAL cluster with E_T of at least 400 MeV.

Figure 9: Histogram of bunch crossing IDs selected by Allen based on ECAL activity in $\sqrt{s} = 900$ pp collisions.

Figure 10: Allen selection rate of $\sqrt{s} = 13.6$ TeV pp events with a single ECAL cluster with $E_T > 400$ MeV. The horizontal axis shows elapsed time in seconds, and the vertical axis shows the selection rate in Hz.

6 Conclusions

Since its adoption as the official LHCb HLT1 software implementation, Allen has grown from a prototype to a fully functional software trigger system. In the meantime, Allen's throughput has increased even as additional features have been added. The LHC just began producing pp collisions at the nominal center-of-mass energy of 13.6 TeV in July, so the challenges and excitement of operating a fully GPU-based software trigger are just beginning.

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Expanding Physics Reach with Unused Tracks in LHCb

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ABSTRACT

The physics reach of the LHCb detector can be extended by reconstructing particles with a long lifetime that decay in the magnet region, using only tracks from downstream of the dipole magnet. This allows for electromagnetic dipole moment measurements, and increases the reach of undiscovered long-lived particle searches. However, using tracks to reconstruct particles decaying in this region is challenging, particularly due to the increased combinatorics and reduced momentum and vertex resolutions, which is why it has not been done until now.

New approaches have been developed to meet the challenges and prepare for physics analysis from these previously unused tracks. These proceedings present the feasibility demonstration studies using Run-2 data, as well as discussing new developments to expand these techniques to fully exploit the dataset to be acquired during Run-3.

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1 Introduction

These proceedings describe the reconstruction of particles in LHCb, using tracks comprised exclusively of hits from after the dipole magnet. This expands the physics reach of the detector by enabling new kinds of measurements, such as electromagnetic dipole moments and beyond the Standard Model (BSM) long-lived particle (LLP) searches over significantly longer distances. This endeavor presents certain reconstruction challenges, primarily due to reduced momentum resolution, as well as extrapolation over large distances to arbitrary locations through a strong inhomogeneous magnetic field. The approaches to these challenges are described below. An overview of the different track types defined in LHCb is described in Sec. 2, the physics motivation is described in Sec. 3, the feasibility studies are presented in Sec. 4, the prospects for Run-3 are briefly described in Sec. 5 and a summary is presented in Sec. 6.

2 LHCb tracks

The tracking system of LHCb [1] is comprised of three subdetectors and a dipole magnet. Tracks are reconstructed from segments in the different subdetectors, and are categorised according to the location of hits. The categories are summarised below:

Velo tracks are comprised exclusively of hits in the VELO (VERTex LOCator) subdetector around the interaction point.

Upstream tracks are comprised of hits in the VELO and the TT (UT from Run-3), named as such because the TT (UT) is located upstream of the magnet.

Downstream tracks are comprised of hits in the TT (UT) and tracking stations T1-T3 (SciFi from Run-3), named as such because T1-T3 (SciFi) are located downstream of the magnet.

Long tracks are comprised of hits in at least the VELO and T1-T3.

T tracks are comprised only of hits in T1-T3 (SciFi), i.e. from hits downstream of the magnet.

Long and Downstream tracks are better measured since they have more hits and traverse the entire magnet, which provides superior momentum resolution. Long tracks have a typical momentum resolution σ_p/p less than 1% [2], whereas for T tracks it is around 25%. For this reason, the LHCb physics programme focuses almost entirely on Long and Downstream tracks. However, this limits the maximum decay length of a particle to around 2 m from the interaction point. It is possible to reconstruct particles from T tracks, extending the maximum decay length up to ~ 7.6 m.

3 Motivation

LHCb is designed and optimised to study particles decaying upstream of the dipole magnet after a few picoseconds. The reconstruction of particles decaying beyond this region has two key physics motivations: dipole moment measurements and the undiscovered long-lived particle (LLP) searches. These are summarised below.

3.1 Electromagnetic dipole moment measurements

Electric and magnetic dipole moments (EDM and MDM respectively) can be measured by exploiting the spin precession of particles that pass through the dipole magnet before decaying. As proposed in [3], this requires a source of polarised particles not aligned with the magnetic field and sufficient reconstruction of decays after the magnet. An example is shown in Fig. 1.

The SM predicts minuscule EDMs. Therefore, enhanced EDMs would be indicative of BSM physics in the form of new sources of CP-violation. By reconstructing particles that decay as they pass through the magnet in LHCb, experimental EDM limits will be greatly improved. For example, the EDM of the Λ baryon

Figure 1: The spin precession of a Λ that originates in $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi\Lambda$, and decays downstream of the magnet.

was last measured some 40 years ago [4]. With the full Run-4 dataset, this limit can be surpassed by between one and two orders of magnitude using the method proposed in [3]. Furthermore, a measurement comparing the MDMs of Λ and $\bar{\Lambda}$ will provide a direct test of CPT symmetry.

3.2 Undiscovered long-lived particle searches

Long-lived particles are present in nearly every beyond the Standard Model (BSM) theory, though none have been discovered so far. LHCb is particularly well suited to search for LLPs produced in the decays of b- and c-hadrons, as well as decays to hadronic signatures, such as pions and kaons, that would benefit from particle identification. Thus far, searches in LHCb have only included Long tracks, meaning they are limited by the size of the VELO subdetector around the beamspot with a decay length $c\tau \lesssim 30$ cm. Analyses using T tracks extend the maximum allowed decay length to ~ 7.6 m, corresponding to lifetimes of up to a few nanoseconds.

4 Feasibility

A study has been performed to demonstrate the feasibility of analyses including T tracks. This tests the suitability of existing LHCb tools and identifies challenges in the approach that would affect a full physics analysis. The goal of the feasibility study is to accurately determine the vertex positions and invariant mass peaks in the $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi\Lambda$ and $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0$ channels, using the dataset collected in Run-2 corresponding to 6 fb^{-1} . The strategy is summarised as follows:

- Trigger on detached muon pair from $J/\psi \rightarrow \mu^+\mu^-$.
- Make a preselection based on kinematic variables.
- Use a boosted decision tree (BDT) classifier that includes kinematic, topological and fit quality variables.
- Veto the physical backgrounds, using both mass cuts and the Armenteros-Podolanski technique [6].
- Fit the invariant mass distributions in simulation and data, with the fit to data constrained by the fit to MC.

The BDT uses the `scikit-learn` histogrammed-BDT model [5]. It is trained on 43,000 simulated signal events, and 6 million background events reconstructed from data. The training is performed on 90% of the sample, and the remaining 10% is used to assess performance. The operating point is set applying a

threshold of 0.366 to the BDT response, with the value determined by the optimal signal to background significance.

The primary challenge of reconstruction with T tracks is the reduced momentum resolution due to lower magnetic field downstream of the magnet, as this affects the mass resolution and vertex reconstruction. The other key challenge is the extrapolation of the tracks to arbitrary locations through the strong, inhomogeneous magnetic field of LHCb's dipole magnet. With no exact analytic solution, a 5th order Runge-Kutta method must be used to numerically approximate the trajectory.

4.1 Particle Identification

Figure 2: The invariant mass distributions of (left) $\Lambda \rightarrow p\pi^-$ and (right) $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi\Lambda$.

$B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0$ is a physical background to $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi\Lambda$ decays. A worse momentum resolution implies a worse mass resolution. Thus, there is little separation in the mass distributions of $\Lambda \rightarrow p\pi^-$ and $K_S \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-$, shown in Fig. 2, so these decays cannot be distinguished by defining suitable regions of invariant mass. The effect is less severe in mass distributions of Λ_b^0 vs B^0 , so an acceptable mass veto can be applied. In LHCb, Particle Identification (PID) parameters are normally calculated with information from the two RICH subdetectors (upstream and downstream of the magnet) as well as the calorimeters and muon stations. PID parameters are not calculated for T tracks in Run-2 data since they were never used in analysis. The Armenteros-Podolanski technique can be employed instead to distinguish $\Lambda \rightarrow p\pi^-$ and $K_S \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-$ using kinematics, as shown in Fig. 3. The region between the Λ and $\bar{\Lambda}$ distributions can be vetoed to reduce the contribution from K_S^0 decays.

4.2 Momentum resolution

The relatively poor momentum resolution is improved by fitting the full decay tree with kinematic constraints imposed. The fit is performed using Decay Tree Fitter (DTF) [7]. It is constrained using the masses of the Λ and J/ψ . This improves the momentum resolution by a factor of 3 (2) for protons (pions) to around $\sigma(p)/p = 10\%$. For comparison, Long tracks tend to have a resolution less than 1% [2].

4.3 Efficiency

The effect of the different selection criteria on the overall efficiency is shown in Fig. 5. The greatest loss in efficiency is caused by the vertex fitting. Potential reasons for this are discussed below.

 Figure 3: Armenteros-Podolanski distributions for $\Lambda \rightarrow p\pi^-$ and $K_S \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-$ decays.

 Figure 4: Momentum resolution before and after applying DTF, for protons and pions, in $\Lambda \rightarrow p\pi^-$ decays.

4.4 Mass fits

Fig. 6 shows the invariant mass distributions of $\Lambda \rightarrow p\pi^-$ and $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi\Lambda$ candidates in data, after all selection criteria are applied. The signal distributions are well described by asymmetric and symmetric (respectively) double-tail Crystal Ball functions. The tail parameters of the symmetric distribution are fixed to values obtained from a fit to simulated $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi\Lambda$ events. The mass resolutions in data are measured to be 8 MeV and 41 MeV respectively. This demonstrates that it is possible to perform meaningful physics analysis by reconstructing particles from T tracks.

4.5 Ghost vertices

As shown in the figure, vertex reconstruction becomes more challenging the further the decay vertex is from the tracking stations. This is in part due to the low Q value in $\Lambda \rightarrow p\pi^-$ decays, meaning a small opening angle between the proton and pion. Therefore the tracks can cross twice within the resolution, which creates an additional “ghost” vertex that cannot be distinguished using standard vertex reconstruction. This ghost vertex can be partially identified by the horizontality, h , defined as:

$$h = \pm M_{\text{pol}} \hat{a}_y, \quad \vec{a} = \vec{p}_{p\pm} \times \vec{p}_{\pi\mp}$$

Figure 5: The efficiency is calculated with respect to particles reconstructible within LHCb. The effect of the different selection criteria on the is shown.

Figure 6: The fitted invariant mass distributions in data for (left) $\Lambda \rightarrow p\pi^-$ and (right) $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi\Lambda$.

Requiring events to have a positive horizontality removes most ghost vertices, thereby significantly improving the vertex bias. However this approach has a low efficiency of about 20%.

5 Run-3

LHCb's upgraded software trigger is versatile and adaptable, allowing for real time analysis of events. This framework is easily expanded to include the reconstruction of particles from T tracks in higher-level-trigger-2 (HLT2), which includes full event reconstruction. This means that PID information for T tracks, including RICH2 information, will now be calculated. Very preliminary studies indicate that this offers adequate distinction between protons and pions, shown in Fig. 7, and could thus be used for both online and offline analysis in future. The Kalman filtering of T tracks is being optimised, and a new vertex finder is being used that could offer improved reconstruction efficiency for T tracks.

There are several T track HLT2 lines in development for Run-3, starting with the two benchmark channels,

Figure 7: Very preliminary demonstration of the proton/pion discrimination in Run-3 simulation for T tracks with RICH2 information.

$\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi\Lambda$ and $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0$. There are plans to include T track BSM LLP lines, once the sensitivity of these channels has been determined.

6 Summary and outlook

The physics reach of LHCb can be extended by reconstructing particles decaying in the magnet region, as this would permit electric and magnetic dipole moment measurements as well as significantly extending the reach of BSM LLP searches. The feasibility of reconstructing such particles has been demonstrated here using Run-2 data. Work is being undertaken so that HLT2 lines are in place for Run-3 to take full advantage of this source of physics.

The next step in this approach is to mitigate the vertex reconstruction issues, and perform a full EDM measurement. The study of additional channels and sensitivity studies for BSM LLP searches is also underway.

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Reinforcement learning for charged-particle tracking

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ABSTRACT

The LHC is undergoing upgrades that will increase the nominal luminosity by at least a factor of five. This creates a computational challenge for the experiments' real time filter systems, particularly for their particle tracking algorithms. Reinforcement learning is introduced as a potential way to address this. It is shown that several reinforcement learning algorithms are able to learn to approximate hit positions given the previous hit associated with a candidate track. The reinforcement learning does not yet perform well enough to be a standalone solution, but it is shown that it may aid other methods such as graph neural networks.

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1 Introduction

The Large Hadron Collider [1] at CERN has brought several scientific discoveries since its inception in 2010, including the discovery of the Higgs boson. It is now being upgraded, and will continue its search for new physics, with a particular emphasis on rare processes and Higgs boson properties. The rate of collisions will increase by at least a factor of five compared to the original design value, and the average number of interactions per bunch crossing will increase from 50 to 200 [2]. Having these interactions simultaneous to the interaction of interest (pileup) poses a great computational challenge, particularly for the real time filter systems. At the CMS [3] experiment, a two tiered trigger system reduce the amount of data read to storage by around two orders of magnitude in an order of 100ms [4]. Even with a planned latency increase, current algorithms will fall short of the upgrade requirements. Particle tracking takes up the largest part of the triggering time budget, and scales particularly badly for high pileup scenarios [5].

1.1 Particle tracking

As charged particles traverse the detector, they leave energy deposits in silicon detector layers. These hits are connected to reconstruct the particle track, known as tracking. The track gives information about the momentum and charge of the particle, the proton-proton interaction point, and potential particle decay points. All of this contributes to the decision on whether to write the event to storage. The high level trigger at CMS uses a Kalman filter [6] method to reconstruct tracks. Given a hit in the detector, a prediction is made of where the track will go next. If a hit is found near this point, the track is updated with this hit. If several compatible hits are found, the track splits, so the different possibilities are explored. This has proven a very fast and accurate method for reconstructing tracks. With the updates of CMS, this is not the case anymore. At the current pileup, there are $O(10\ 000)$ hits in each event, which will scale to $O(100\ 000)$ with 200 pileup. There are many more compatible hits in each iteration of the Kalman filter [6], causing a combinatoric explosion [5], and sending tracking far over the trigger time budget. This could be addressed by e.g. accelerating the Kalman filter method, or by machine learning.

1.2 Accelerating particle tracking

Many projects have been launched to accelerate particle tracking. Some of the main analytical methods that have been explored are mkFit and Patatrack. The mkFit [5] project has parallelised the traditional tracking by parallelising over each event, sections of the detector, and seed tracks. There are plans to port this to GPUs. The Patatrack [7] collaboration swapped the Kalman filter for a line fit method, parallelised it and ported it to GPUs. Several machine learning approaches have also been investigated, but graph neural networks have shown the highest track reconstruction accuracy [8]. Hits act as nodes in a graph, and nearby hits are connected with edges. One can then use a graph neural network to predict whether the edges are false or true edges. This has shown a high accuracy, though building the graphs is time consuming [9].

All these projects have shown promising acceleration, but have not met timing requirements yet. One challenge is that they still retain the combinatorial nature of the problem. Reinforcement learning [10] could provide an approach that directly addresses the combinatorics. It offers a way to take advantage of previous experience and is easily parallelisable. If the accuracy is not adequate, it could still help build smaller graphs for the graph neural networks; potentially improving both latency and accuracy.

2 Reinforcement learning

Reinforcement learning (RL) relies on the reward hypothesis; any goal can be represented as a maximisation of the expected value of the cumulative sum of a reward signal. In other words, a problem is phrased as an agent acting in an environment that receives rewards based on its actions. This has had large successes in recent years, including AlphaGo, AlphaZero, and fusion plasma control [11, 12]. RL can be appropriate when a problem is intractable and the environment changes based on the action. Most often, RL also requires Markovian state; where the agent will go next depends only on the current state. The set of rules

that determine which actions an RL agent takes is called a policy. This can be deterministic, like a neural network, or stochastic, like sampling from a distribution. One can learn a policy by learning the parameters of e.g. a neural network or a Gaussian distribution. Most algorithms also have a value function that estimates the expected return given a state-action pair.

RL is divided into two main categories; model based and non-model based. Model based learning has a model of the environment, which is sample efficient, but relies on a good model of the environment. The second dividing element of RL methods is what they learn. One can learn a policy, a value function, or a model of the environment. When choosing a reinforcement learning method, it can be worth keeping in mind that non-model based methods have been explored more, and are often easier to implement [10]. Some of the methods that were used to explore RL for particle tracking are introduced below.

2.1 Policy gradient

Policy gradient algorithms [13] are some of the simplest RL algorithms and are often a logical starting point for a new reinforcement learning application. They aim to learn the parameters of a policy through gradient descent. For continuous action spaces, Gaussian policies are often used. Each agent state is associated with a Gaussian distribution, and actions will be sampled from this distribution. As the agent learns, the mean might shift, and the distribution will narrow as the policy learns the best action for that state. Policy gradients are considered to have good convergence properties, which is one reason they are often used as a first test for new reinforcement learning applications. A downside is that they often converge to local instead of global optima. Policy gradients are suitable for both continuous and discrete action spaces.

2.2 Deep Q-Network

Another relatively simple algorithm is deep Q-learning [14]. Q-learning tries to learn the quality of an action given a certain state. The simplest version of Q-learning simply tabulates the quality of all possible actions given all possible states. In many problems, the dimensionality is too big for all combinations to be explored. Instead, one can learn a function that calculates the quality of the possible actions given a certain state. This is most often done with deep neural networks, called deep Q-Networks (DQN) [15]. The neural network predicts the quality of each possible action given an input state. To avoid situations where a lot of similar states dominate the learning, previous experiences are stored in a buffer and replayed through the network. Methods that use neural networks to estimate qualities of actions usually always use another neural network called a target network. The Q-learning neural network uses the reward signal to calculate the estimated quality of an action, and performs supervised learning with this as a target. This quality can change depending on the samples, so the target changes. To avoid this, the weights of this network is copied to a target network. This only updates every N iterations to keep the learning stable. The action space for DQN must be discrete since one chooses actions from a discrete set of output nodes.

2.3 Deep deterministic policy gradient

Deep deterministic policy gradient (DDPG) [16] has been developed specifically to act as a RL method similar to DQN that can be used in continuous action spaces. It combines ideas from the two previous methods, and learns both a policy and a Q-function. This idea is called actor-critic since there is a policy (actor) and a critic (Q-function) that criticises the moves made by the policy. The policy can predict continuous states, and the critic will estimate the quality of the action. The policy will be guided by the critic as it updates. This can create a good, advanced model for continuous spaces, but has been known not to converge, even in simple environments [17].

3 Reinforcement learning for particle tracking

The tracking problem was recast as a reinforcement learning problem where an agent is given a state and predicts where the next hit will be. The state contains the current hit position, and to be Markovian, it also

needs track parameter estimates or information about the previous hits for the track candidate. The simplest Markovian state can for instance contain the current and previous hit positions. The two inner hits of each track were used as a seed to fill the track parameter or previous hit information. An illustration is shown in Fig. 1. Although this uses truth-level information, it does not make the scenario entirely unrealistic, since seeds are created at the low level trigger [4]. The hit positions were described by two dimensional coordinates; z and r , where r is $\sqrt{x^2 + y^2}$. The tracks are straight in this space when ignoring energy loss, making it much easier to learn than a three dimensional helix. The reward was defined by the negative distance between the predicted and true hit position. Each episode contained five hit predictions, so only tracks with a total of seven hits were used. To simplify the problem, only one hit per layer were considered. The TrackML dataset [18] was used. This is a dataset created to benchmark machine learning approaches for tracking. It uses a generic detector layout and an average pileup of 200, making it a reasonable reflection of the upgrade environment.

Figure 1: Visualisation of the tracking problem. A seed is created from the two inner hits. The next hit position is predicted using help from the previous hit, a seeded linear fit (a) (Section 3.1.2) or a module mapping (b) (Section 3.1.3). The reward is given after each hit prediction based on the distance between the actual hit and the predicted hit.

Ideally, this approach could be used standalone for tracking. If it does not achieve sufficient performance, it could instead be used to cut down the number of fake edges built in a graph neural network. To know how accurate the RL algorithm needs to be to do this, the distance between true hits and hits for built fake edges in a graph neural network was studied. This was done using the graph neural network implementation given in [9]. The results are shown in Fig. 2. It shows that if one has a RL agent that consistently predicts hit positions 10cm within the true hit, one would cut around half of the fake edges built for the graph. Within 20cm one would eliminate 25% of the fake edges. The resolution of the detector is on the order of micrometres [3], so a method that predicts within 10-20cm of the true hits would be very far away from performing tracking well on its own. Fig. 2 shows that it could still be used to build smaller and more accurate graphs for graph neural networks. It does not outperform a straight line fit, as is discussed in Section 3.1.2.

3.1 Policy gradient for tracking

A simple policy gradient algorithm was applied to the environment outlined above. A neural network using just two hidden layers with 64 neurons each was used. Since the aim is to accelerate tracking, it is important

Figure 2: Distance between the true track hit and fake edge hit for two minimum p_T points. The orange line illustrates the median and the box shows the interquartile range. The green points mark points that are outliers, i.e. a value higher than 1.5 times the interquartile range plus the third quartile.

to keep the neural network lightweight, so it does not take longer than traditional tracking. A lightweight approach also makes any potential GPU or FPGA acceleration easier. A Gaussian policy parameterised by a neural network was chosen. Many variations of state descriptions were explored, with some highlighted in the section below.

3.1.1 Inductive bias

Every machine learning model has inductive bias - something that makes it favour one model over another. This becomes especially important in reinforcement learning. If a human were to connect the dots in Fig. 1, it is likely they would immediately assume that hits would only be possible on detector layers, and given the physics of the problem, there would be a straight line from the seed. A RL agent does not have this intuition. Infusing the model with this inductive bias is therefore important to avoid extremely long training times or a lack of convergence.

Fig. 3 shows three different RL scenarios. If one predicts the position of the next hit, the algorithm does not appear to learn in a reasonable time frame. There is too much action space to explore to find good solutions. Since we know the next hit in the track will be close to the previous, predicting a change in position eliminates a lot of the action space, giving a jump in performance. One can go even further and assume that the change in coordinates is going to be similar to that of the last hit, and learn a correction to this assumption. This has a slight advantage early on, but it converges on the same solution as predicting a change in position. The black dashed line shows the accuracy when always assuming the same change in position as the seed without any RL. This illustrates that the RL learns valuable information in addition to the inductive bias it is given. A small increase in performance not shown in the graph was also seen by taking advantage of the symmetry in the z -axis. Projecting all tracks to the positive z -plane removes half the phase space, so the agent learns more easily. Tracks that cross the r -axis and are in both positive and negative z -space would be displaced tracks and are not considered in this study. The average return is the total reward for a track averaged over the past forty iterations. This converges around -100. Since five hits were predicted, this means that the hit predicted is consistently 20cm within the actual position. Consulting Fig. 2, this would cut down about 25% of the fake edges of a graph neural network. While it is an improvement, it is likely not enough to compensate for the extra time taken for the RL evaluation. To improve, more prior knowledge was considered.

Figure 3: Reward for tracks averaged over the past forty training iterations using a policy gradient environment with different inductive biases. The tracks have two seed hits and five hit predictions. The various lines shows what the policy was trying to predict. Always (dr, dz) corresponds to a non-RL scenario where one assumes the change in r and z are the same as in the seed for the entire track.

3.1.2 Linear fit

A disadvantage of the approach in Section 3.1.1 is that it allows hit predictions outside the detector layers. To address this and take advantage of how tracks form a straight line in the r-z space, a line fit was applied. A straight line fit was created from the seed, and intersection points with the detector layers were calculated. To see if this would be a viable method, it was first tried without any reinforcement learning. Since a potential goal was to reduce the number of fake edges in a graph neural network, the graph building outlined in [9] was used as a baseline. Implementing it with the linear fit, only hits that fell within ± 1.5 cm of the detector intersection points were connected. The graph neural network was then trained and evaluated. The results are shown in Fig. 4.

The linear fit shows a similar efficiency to the baseline graph neural network and a much higher purity. Since it showed promise, it was then combined with reinforcement learning. The baseline assumption was that the next hit would be where the next detector intersection is, and the reinforcement learning agent learnt a correction to this. This reduced the average episode return from -100 to around -60, so resulted in much more accurate hit predictions. Perhaps surprisingly, the reward when using just the linear approach and no machine learning was -30. This discrepancy is partially due to missing hits.

The corrections to the linear fit are generally quite small. When there are missing hits, all the predictions are offset by one, causing very low rewards for the remains of the episode. This hides what the reinforcement learning agent needs to learn. When only considering the inner tracker, and removing any tracks with missing hits, the average episode reward is around -1.5 for the linear fit, and -5 for the linear fit reinforcement learning. This would remove more than 75% of the fake edges in the graph building, and approaches the limit where RL might be considered as a standalone method. The reason the reward is lower when applying RL is that the corrections to the linear assumption are likely to be close to stochastic. Any pattern probably does not emerge until one also considers where the observed detector hits are.

Ideally, the reinforcement learning agent would know roughly where the next hit is and sample its next state from the compatible detector hits. Learning how to choose the best hit given a set of available hits is difficult because every event will look different. A simple way to account for hit information is to simply choose the hit that is closest to the hit prediction. Without using reinforcement learning, that brings the reward up to around -0.7 for the linear fit without machine learning. With RL, the reward is still around -5, since the agent is not aware of the hits before making its prediction. The linear fit approach therefore looks good as an analytical solution, but to benefit from reinforcement learning, one would need the RL agent to know the position of available detector hits before making its prediction. This could be done by for instance behaviour priors [19] or action masking [20].

3.1.3 Module mapping

The linear fit has the disadvantage of doing analytical calculations for every track. An alternative could be module mapping, which has been extensively explored as a way to reduce the number of edges in graph neural networks for particle tracking [21]. By iterating over tracks and storing which modules are adjacent, one can create a mapping of allowed module connections. This has shown very good results for reducing the number of fake edges, but could perhaps be put to even better use when combined with reinforcement learning. Other module mapping methods usually consider a sequence of two or three modules that are connected. These are stored in a mapping and any of the connections are allowed in the graph building. Inspired by the linear fitting in the approach above, one might consider that each module connection is likely to only occur for a certain line slope. By iterating over 10 000 tracks, a mapping was created with this in mind. The end result is a dictionary where one can look up a module, the current line parameters, and find all the connected modules that have been seen. Similarly to the linear fit, it was first tried with the graph building outlined in [9]. Only hits that conformed with the module mapping were connected. The results are shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 4: Efficiency (a) and purity (b) comparisons for graph neural networks using two analytical methods and a baseline. The efficiency is the ratio of edges that were correctly classified as true. The purity is the ratio of real to total edges in the graph. The linear fit and module map methods are described in Section 3.1.2 and Section 3.1.3 and show similar efficiency and consistently higher purity than the baseline graph neural network method.

The module mapping results are quite similar to the linear approach, with a slightly lower purity. The module mapping has not been combined with reinforcement learning yet. This is because it is a similar situation to the one outlined in Section 3.1.2. One could e.g. use the module mapping to learn a correction to assuming that the track would go to the average allowed module position. To benefit from RL, however, one would need to learn which hit to choose given a set of available hits.

3.2 DDPG and Q-learning

Since the policy gradient is a very simple reinforcement learning method, other approaches were also explored. DDPG is a more advanced method well suited for continuous spaces. It did not improve the accuracy compared to the policy gradient method. Some environments achieved similar performance, but many had lower performance and a much more unstable learning process. As described in [17], DDPG uses several neural networks, so these behaviours are known to occur. Learning in continuous environments can also be difficult, so a discrete approach was tried. Deep-Q learning was implemented to predict which module the track would propagate to given previous modules. This had very bad performance and did not seem to learn any valuable information. This is likely due to the somewhat arbitrary numbering of modules, making it

difficult to create a meaningful mathematical relation between them. There are many ways to deal with this in Deep-Q learning, but many of them require quite complex representation of the state. There might be some value to these discrete approaches, but the combinatorics of such problems make them a less attractive alternative.

4 Conclusion

Reinforcement learning for particle tracking has been explored. Using a simple policy gradient method, it was shown that an RL agent could learn to predict where the next hit would be with an accuracy of about ± 20 cm. This is quite a wide range, and would not be sufficient for RL to be a standalone method for tracking. If used in conjunction with graph neural networks, it could cut down about 25% of the fake edges built, but would likely not make up for the additional evaluation time and complexity. Linear fitting and module mapping were explored for use in reinforcement learning. Both showed promise, with the linear fit predicting consistently within 5cm of the true hit for a slightly simplified scenario. The linear fit performed better without any reinforcement learning than with it. To benefit further from reinforcement learning, the agent needs to know about the available detector hits before making a prediction. The linear fit without any machine learning was consistently accurate within less than a centimetre in a slightly simplified scenario, so it can be used as a benchmark for accuracy and latency for future work.

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Track Reconstruction at the Electron-Ion Collider

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ABSTRACT

During the past year, substantial progress has been made on the design of EPIC, which is the first detector for the Electron-Ion Collider (EIC). All detector variants proposed during this phase incorporated silicon trackers for charged particle tracking and vertex reconstruction. A simulation and reconstruction framework based on DD4hep + Gaudi + Acts + EDM4hep was developed by the ATHENA proposal collaboration to demonstrate a tracking performance consistent with the EIC physics requirements as defined in the Yellow Report. In this work, the ATHENA tracking system configuration, reconstruction studies with Acts, and plans to further advance this effort for EIC Project Detector 1 are discussed.

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1 Introduction

The Electron-Ion-Collider (EIC) will be a new experimental facility to study the structure and dynamics of quarks and gluons in nucleons and nuclei. The facility will be sited at Brookhaven National Laboratory on Long Island, New York, and the U.S. Department of Energy has granted Critical Decision 1 (CD-1) for the project. In March 2021, Brookhaven National Laboratory (BNL) and Thomas Jefferson National Accelerator Facility (JLab) together issued a call for Collaboration Proposals for Detectors at the EIC [1]. According to the proposal submission guidelines, the nominal concepts proposed for EIC Detector 1 were required to satisfy the needs of the science program laid out in the EIC Community White paper [2] and the NAS Science Assessment [3], recently worked out further in the form of reference detector concepts in the EIC Yellow Report [4] with the corresponding particle identification, calorimetry, tracking and vertexing resolutions. The collaboration proposals were furthermore required to provide paths towards the construction of such a detector by CD-4A, the start of EIC accelerator operations, currently anticipated in 2031. The proposals were also to address cost, schedule, and risk.

Three proto-collaborations – ATHENA [5], ECCE [6] and CORE [7] – were formed during the detector proposal stage. There are two possible experimental halls to accommodate EIC detectors on the six and eight o'clock locations of the RHIC ring, called IP6 and IP8 respectively. CORE's design focuses on the far-forward detectors making use of the possibility of secondary focusing at IP8. ATHENA and ECCE are both designed for IP6. The latter two detector concepts have many commonalities in their proposed tracking and vertexing subsystems. ECCE opted to re-use the 1.4 T solenoid magnet from the former BaBar experiment [8], while ATHENA proposed to build a new solenoidal magnet with a 3 T field strength. During the ATHENA proposal stage, a new simulation and reconstruction framework was developed featuring modern software created by the high energy physics community, including DD4hep [9], Gaudi [10], Acts [11] and EDM4hep [12]. These proceedings document some of the tracking simulation work for the ATHENA detector proposal including geometry and material description, digitization, track finding/reconstruction, and performance checks. Following the EIC Detector Proposal Advisory Panel [1] recommendation to use the ECCE concept as a reference design for EIC Detector 1, the three proto-collaborations have been merged to continue the development of Detector 1 from reference to baseline. DD4hep, Acts, and EDM4hep will continue to be used as important components of the future simulation framework, making the development and experience from ATHENA quite valuable.

2 Geometry and Material Description

DD4hep is a comprehensive toolkit that provides a complete detector description for simulation, reconstruction, and analysis. It converts an easy-to-use compact detector description file in XML format to a ROOT TGeo-based generic model for geometry construction and visualization, and interfaces with Geant4 to perform simulations. The full implementation and documentation of the ATHENA detector geometry can be found in the code repository [13]. A detailed description of the tracking system can be found in Ref. [14]. Starting from the all-silicon tracker conceptual design (see Ref. [15]) used in the EIC Yellow Report, ATHENA developed a hybrid tracking system with mixed technologies including Monolithic Active Pixel Sensors (MAPS) and Micro Pattern Gas Detector (MPGD) technology.

Figure 1 shows the ATHENA central tracking system with realistic modeling of service and mechanical support structures. The core of the system is a set of MAPS detectors: six silicon disks in the forward (hadron-going) direction, five in the backward (electron-going) direction, with a span along the beam direction of +165 cm and -145 cm respectively, and five layers of silicon central barrels that cover pseudo-rapidity $|\eta| < 1.1$. In the backward/forward direction, there are two large Gas Electron Multiplier (GEM) rings to increase the detection area at relatively low cost. In the forward direction, a large micro-Resistive Well (μ RWell) disk is placed behind the dual Ring Imaging Cherenkov (dRICH) detector at $z = 335$ cm to increase tracking accuracy at this location. The backward direction has fewer disks to minimize material that electrons scattered in this direction go through. Two micromegas barrels (each contains two layers of

micromegas detectors) are put outside of the silicon barrels to provide additional tracking hits in the central region. A Low Gain Avalanche Detector (LGAD) is also included in the proposed tracking system to provide additional position and fast timing information. That particular subsystem is, however, not fully integrated into the reconstruction study presented here.

Figure 1: Illustration of the ATHENA central tracker in DD4hep. The axes are shown with units in cm. Note that the proposed dRICH detector, located between $z = 190$ to 330 cm, as well as other non-tracking subsystems are not shown.

All tracking detectors are implemented with detailed geometry and material thickness in DD4hep for use in Geant4 simulation and reconstruction with Acts. Segmentation for each detector surface is defined in the same compact XML files following the proposed detector feature sizes and resolutions. Acts can convert geometry descriptions from DD4hep detector volumes to Acts surface representations. The material thickness, however, needs to be manually assigned to Acts surfaces of choice. A full tutorial of this material assignment process can be found in Ref. [16]. In general, one needs to use Acts utilities to convert the detailed geometry in DD4hep into volume and surface descriptions, then go through layer volume boundaries to decide surfaces that the material will be mapped onto, and decide on a binning. In this study, we chose the Acts approaching layers to be just inwards of the sensitive tracking surfaces of the proposed detector, which all served as Acts mapping surfaces. In the case of the dRICH, additional surfaces were defined. The detector materials were then mapped onto the nearest mapping surfaces in generating the Acts material map. Typically, 36 bins in ϕ and 100 bins in z and R were found to give good results. This process was repeated with different binnings until the result was found to be in good agreement with Geant4 material scans using the geantino, which is a chargeless, massless, completely non-interacting virtual particle *c.f.* Fig. 2. The resulting material map was then used as input to Acts during reconstruction.

3 Track Reconstruction

3.1 Simulation Process

DD4hep takes initial particle information from either HepMC3 files [17] or from a particle gun. The simulated event information, including Monte Carlo (MC) truth particles and hits from each detector volume, were stored in ROOT files and served as the input to the Gaudi-based reconstruction framework called Juggler [18]. By default, Juggler calls the Acts-based Combinatorial Kalman Filter (CKF) for track finding

Figure 2: Material scan from the Acts material map (black) and from a geantino scan (red) as X/X_0 (top panel) and their ratio (bottom panel) versus pseudo-rapidity.

and reconstruction. Acts uses a simplified surface-based detector geometry to achieve faster navigation and reduce CPU time. Hits from the tracking detectors first went through a digitization step where hit positions were assigned to cell centers in the detector local coordinate system using input from the actual segmentation specified in DD4hep. Threshold cuts on timing and energy deposits or other response characteristics can also be applied on the detector hits at this stage, as needed. The digitized tracking hits from the detailed 3D detector geometry were then transformed into measurements on the Acts surfaces to perform CKF. Finally the reconstructed trajectories from CKF were matched with the Monte Carlo truth information to identify the reconstructed particles.

The initial and reconstructed particles, as well as their trajectories and hit information, were saved following structures defined by a PODIO-based [19] event data model called EICd [20], based on EDM4hep. By default, the tracking information was stored at the location of the collision vertex, including uncertainties along R and Z , azimuthal (θ) and polar (ϕ) angles, and charge to momentum ratios. Alternatively, one can also project the trajectories to any given detector surface to obtain the corresponding quantities along the track including the path-length. This functionality was used for several detector studies. The collision vertex was chosen to be at the nominal collision point for most studies presented here and more studies with an actual vertex distribution and reconstruction are planned for the future.

3.2 Single Particle Track Performance

Single π^+ events were used in the track performance study presented here. Only one outgoing π^+ was generated per event with uniformly chosen polar angle ϕ at any given momentum p and azimuthal angle θ . The MC truth particle information was used to create seeds for CKF in this study while the realistic seed finding algorithm is still under development. An event was considered to be properly reconstructed if there existed at least one reconstructed track within 5% in $\delta p/p$, 0.005 rad in θ , 0.03 rad in ϕ , and 3 mm in DCA_τ with respect to the initially generated quantities. The resolution of a given tracking variable is extracted as the standard deviation of a Gaussian fit to its residuals $\frac{recon-init}{init}$, where a single Gaussian provided an adequate parametrization. When this was not the case, a Gaussian was fitted to a truncated range around the central peak to make the fitting robust against tails. Figure 3 shows the tracking efficiency, angular distribution, and momentum and angle resolutions from a sample of single π^+ events. This process was repeated for different bins in η and p . Results were compared with the Yellow Report design resolutions, as

well as benchmarked against two other reconstruction packages, Fun4All [21] and LDT [22], as part of the validation of the ATHENA design concept and the entire simulation framework.

During the ATHENA proposal period, a material map was generated and the single particle tracking studies were performed every time the tracking system configuration was changed as part of the optimization process. Figure 4 shows the $\delta p/p$ performance of the final detector version (with code name DeathValley) that is reported in the ATHENA proposal and compares the performance with the physics requirements from the Yellow Report. In general, the ATHENA design performances meet or exceed the physics requirements of the Yellow Report. The very backward (electron-going) direction forms an exception, where no known tracking technology can currently meet the physics requirements even in a 3 T magnetic field. In the ATHENA design, only five disks were proposed in this direction (and hence at most five tracking hits are available) in a carefully studied optimization of the trade offs between traversed material and detector hit points. In the case of high-energy electrons, the Yellow Report requirements on momentum resolution may be reached by combination of the tracking information with the energy measurement using the proposed precision electromagnetic calorimetry (nEcal) located downstream of the tracking disks.

Limitations of the tracking studies presented here include, for example, that they are based on single particles without taking background hits into account and without realistic seeding and vertex reconstruction. For the anticipated collision rate (< 1 MHz) at the EIC design luminosities and for the proposed kinematics (center-of-mass energy < 144 GeV), the multiplicities in deep inelastic scatterings tend to be less than 10 within the detector acceptance [15]. Beam-induced backgrounds will contribute further hits and can thus affect the performance of the tracking algorithm. Further study of these effects is planned. The simulated performance is, furthermore, known to benefit from truth seeding for $p_T < 1$ GeV/c. With the assumption that at least five hits will be needed for a realistic track reconstruction, a particle in the central barrel region $|\eta| < 1.1$ will need to reach the sagitta barrel layer at $R = 18$ cm to satisfy this need. This radius corresponds to a minimum p_T of approximately $0.3 \cdot 3T \cdot 0.18\text{m}/2 \approx 80$ MeV/c. However, due to multiple scattering, the resolution distributions for $p_T < 400$ MeV/c are known to have non-Gaussian tails that underline the need for further study including backgrounds and more realistic seeding.

Figure 3: Track reconstruction resolutions from a sample of 10,000 single π^+ events generated with $\eta = 0.4 - 0.6$ and momenta p between 2 and 2.5 GeV/c.

4 Conclusions

The ATHENA detector proto-collaboration developed a comprehensive simulation and reconstruction software framework for EIC. It integrates widely-used software from the modern high-energy (nuclear) physics community to achieve high performance at manageable maintenance and development effort. Charged-particle tracking and reconstruction have been demonstrated during the proposal stage in simulations. Many of the associated software efforts, including DD4hep and Acts-based or related development, are

being adopted by the collaboration that is being formed around the EIC project detector. In particular, the software and simulation working groups of the new collaboration are working closely with the Acts developers towards a realistic tracking solution for EIC and also address important remaining open questions in the detector baseline design.

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Figure 4: The simulated momentum resolution $\delta p/p$ versus momentum for different η ranges as green markers and orange fitted curves. The blue dashed curves show the physics requirements from the Yellow Report. The dotted-dashed curves in red indicate the size of the constant term in the energy resolution for the proposed electromagnetic calorimeter in the electron-going direction [4]; this term limits the resolution that can ultimately be reached at high momenta in this acceptance region.

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The tracking and measurement of the beam-related parameters at Belle II

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ABSTRACT

The tracking system of Belle II consists of a silicon vertex detector (VXD) and a cylindrical drift chamber (CDC), both operating in a magnetic field created by the main solenoid of 1.5 T and final focusing magnets. The experiment is taking data since 2019 with high-quality and stable tracking performance. We present the tracking-based calibration of the beam characteristics and their interaction region, which are critical for the many high-precision measurements in the physics program. We also discuss possible improvements in the silicon strip vertex detector track finding, exploiting Hough transformation instead of the current approach which is based on the trained MC patterns.

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1 Introduction

The Belle II experiment [1] belongs to the next generation of the B -factories and its main mission is to study the CP -violation in the $B\bar{B}$ system and rare decays of B mesons. Despite the name, Belle II also probes charmed particles, τ leptons, performs dark sector searches and serves in addition a broad physics program. The experiment is located at the SuperKEKB collider [2], which accelerates electrons to 7 GeV and positrons to 4 GeV, so that the centre-of-mass (CM) energy of the collisions is 10.58 GeV, corresponding to the $\Upsilon(4S)$ resonance mass. The $\Upsilon(4S)$ resonance decays almost exclusively to $B\bar{B}$. As the $\Upsilon(4S)$ mass is just slightly above the production threshold, the B mesons are nearly at rest in the CM frame. Asymmetric beam energies lead to a boost of the $B\bar{B}$ system, so that the lifetimes of the B mesons can be measured via the displaced vertices.

Up to now SuperKEKB has achieved a peak luminosity of $5 \times 10^{34} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ which is more than twice the record luminosity set by Belle [3], but still about 20 times smaller than the design luminosity.

High luminosity is achieved by a significant reduction of the vertical beam size ("nano beam" scheme) and by increasing the beam currents. Over the full lifespan SuperKEKB is expected to deliver an integrated luminosity of 50 ab^{-1} . So far before the Long Shutdown 1, which started in Summer 2022, the luminosity of 430 fb^{-1} have been recorded, which roughly corresponds to the total integrated luminosity recorded by BaBar. The data taking will continue in Fall 2023 after the upgrade.

The design of the Belle II experiment is motivated by the high instantaneous luminosity and the challenges that come with it. In addition it respects the asymmetry in energies of the colliding particles, i.e. the detector has better coverage in the forward region than in backward.

The tracking system (Fig. 1) is made up of three tracking detectors: the pixel detector (PXD) and the strip vertex detector (SVD), which are commonly summarized as the vertex detector (VXD), as well as the central drift chamber (CDC). The PXD is installed right outside the beam pipe and consists of two layers,

Figure 1: The Belle II vertex detector (VXD) (a) and the Central Drift Chamber (CDC) (b).

based on the DEPFET Pixel Technology [4]. Currently, the first layer of 16 modules is fully installed but only four modules from 24 modules of the second layer are mounted. One of the advantages of the DEPFET is a very low material budget of about 0.2% of a radiation length. The PXD allows for a very precise measurement of the impact parameter of tracks as the inner layer is installed at a radius of just about 1.4 cm and the pixel size is $50 \mu\text{m}$ in the azimuthal direction. The SVD encloses the PXD and consists of four layers of double-sided silicon strip detectors, which corresponds to a thickness of about 0.7% radiation lengths. It has an excellent hit time resolution of about 3 ns. This allows the SVD to provide robust tracking despite the background levels, also for standalone tracking. The outermost tracking detector is the CDC, which consists of 56 layers of wires grouped in alternating superlayers of axial and stereo wires. Stereo wires are skewed by an angle between 45.4 and 74 mrad in the positive and negative direction with respect to the axis of the beam and are necessary to determine the longitudinal position of tracks. Most importantly, the CDC provides a very high momentum resolution as it covers the major part of the tracking volume up to $l \times r = 2.3 \text{ m} \times 2.2 \text{ m}$.

2 Track finding

2.1 Overview

A detailed overview about the track finding at Belle II can be found in [5], the track-finding sequence is summarized in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: The Belle II tracking workflow (a), where VXDTE2 algorithm is planned to be replaced by SVDHough, and the example of the fitted tracks in the transverse plane shown together with the hits (b). The wires in CDC are visible as dots and SVD modules as line segments.

The CDC track finding consists of two independent algorithms and it is used as the baseline. In the second step, SVD hits are added to the previously found tracks making use of a Combinatorial Kalman Filter (CKF). The third step considers the unused SVD hits and tries to reconstruct tracks out of them. These SVD standalone tracks are then extrapolated to the CDC again via another CKF. Finally all independently found tracks are merged to a single collection that is then extrapolated to the PXD in the final step by a third CKF.

To find the tracks in CDC, first the global approach based on the Legendre parameters is used, consequently the remaining hits are found using Cellular Automaton which works better for tracks from the secondary decays.

2.2 SVD tracking based on Hough transformation

As mentioned in the previous section, in addition to the SVD tracks obtained by an extrapolation from CDC via CKF, the SVD standalone tracks are also considered (Fig. 2). This is especially useful for the low- p_T tracks which have high curvature and do not reach the CDC.

The algorithm, known as VXDTE2, which is still used by default, is based on filtering the track candidates using the relation maps between SVD sectors calculated by MC and on applying Cellular Automaton to find the tracks [5].

The newly developed algorithm SVDHough finds tracks in the Hough space instead [6]. First, the x, y coordinates* of the hits in SVD are transformed via a conformal transformation to x', y'

$$x', y' = \frac{x, y}{x^2 + y^2}, \quad (1)$$

so that circles are transformed into lines, see Fig. 3 (a). This transformation preserves track angle at the

*At Belle II the z-axis of the laboratory frame is defined as the central axis of the solenoid, with its positive direction defined by the direction of the electron beam. The distance between this axis and the actual interaction point changes in time and it has been always smaller than 0.1 cm.

Figure 3: SVD hits before and after the conformal transformation (a) and curves obtained from hits via Hough transformation (b) [6].

origin of coordinate system. Notice, that for the transformed track, the curvature is encoded into the distance of the line from the origin. In the next step, the Hough transformation (HT)

$$\rho = x' \cos \theta + y' \sin \theta \quad (2)$$

is applied on the hit coordinates (x', y') , Fig. 3 (b). It converts each hit to the sinusoidal curve. It would be computationally intense to calculate all the intersections analytically as there can be hundreds of hits in SVD. Therefore, the "binary" search approach visualised in Fig. 3 (b) is used to find the region with the highest density of curves. In this way, the $\mathcal{O}(n^2)$ problem is converted to $\mathcal{O}(n \log n)$. The division is stopped if less than three lines from different SVD layers pass it or if a maximal number of divisions is reached. This approach allows to find the local maxima, corresponding to the track candidates.

In Fig. 4 the performance of the both variants of the SVD standalone tracking is compared using simulated events. We define the MC tracks which are created using the true simulated hits. On the other hand, there are Pattern Recognition (PR) tracks found by the tracking algorithm. MC track and PR track are *matched* if the PR track contains at least 5% hits of the MC track and at the same time more than 66.6% hits of the PR track are from the MC track [6]. The MC track is *found* if it is *matched* at least to one PR track. The track finding efficiency plotted on the right is a fraction of *found* MC tracks w.r.t. all MC tracks in the event. Notice, that such definition considers only traces from MC particles that are in the fiducial volume of the Belle II and the finding efficiency of 100% is in principle feasible. It can be seen that the SVDhough performs better in the forward and backward region than the older algorithm. There can be multiple PR tracks *matched* to the MC track. That can happen for the low p_T curling tracks, which travel through the tracking volume multiple times, or if the track from the particle is found in multiple sub-detectors but these are not merged together. Even in this case, there is always a single PR track which has the best matching quality and the remaining PR tracks are tagged as clones. Fraction of clone PR tracks w.r.t. all PR tracks in the event is shown in left part of Fig. 4. It can be seen, that for the low p_T high-curvature tracks with $p_T \approx 0.05$ GeV, which are mostly in the SVD volume, there is a substantial reduction of the clones with the new algorithm.

3 Beam-related Parameters

3.1 Motivation

An important advantage of the B factories colliding electrons with positrons compared to the experiments based on hadron collisions (e.g. LHCb) is the clean even topology. At LHC there are hundreds of particles produced per bunch-crossing, both from the primary interaction as well as from the Pile-Up. Consequently, there is huge combinatorial background, especially for decays into neutral particles [7]. On the other hand, at Belle II in typical interaction ~ 10 final-state particles are produced which are the decay products of B

and \bar{B} in case of the $e^+e^- \rightarrow \Upsilon(4S) \rightarrow B\bar{B}$ processes. As no other particles than the pair of B mesons are produced, the kinematic properties of the B mesons can be constrained from the energy-momentum conservation using the momenta of the beams[†]. In addition, the knowledge of the production region of the $B\bar{B}$ pair, so-called beam spot, allows to improve the precision of the vertex positions as well as particle momenta. Belle II achieves high instantaneous luminosity by the nano-beam scheme, where the luminous region in the vertical direction has only ~ 100 nm and is planned to have 50 nm, when the instantaneous luminosity will be increased. Therefore, the y production coordinate is much more constrained than at Belle or BaBar where the vertical beam spot size was $\sim 5 \mu\text{m}$ [8].

Excellent Belle II tracking performance together with the tighter beam spot constraint allowed to measure lifetimes of the charmed hadrons like D^+ and D^0 [9] and Λ_c^+ [10] with the world leading precision although the luminosity of the analysed data was smaller compared to Belle or BaBar.

The knowledge of the momenta of the colliding particles is utilized to better reconstruct the invariant mass of the B meson. The beam-constrained invariant mass is defined as

$$M_{bc} = \sqrt{(E_{\text{beam}}^*)^2 - (p_B^*)^2}, \quad (3)$$

where $E_{\text{beam}}^* = \sqrt{s}/2$ and p_B^* is the beam energy and B meson momentum in the CM frame. Using this quantity one can achieve much better mass resolution and, consequently, better signal to background discrimination than with the classical invariant mass. Furthermore, the beam momenta are also used to perform the transformation to the CM system or, for example, to get the $\Upsilon(4S)$ velocity which is essential in the time-dependent CP violation measurements.

In addition, by measuring the beam momenta at Belle II we can monitor the performance of the accelerator, for example that it really operates with CM energy exactly equal to the $\Upsilon(4S)$ resonance mass.

Both the beam spot parameters and beam momenta in general differ to the nominal values and vary with time, therefore, they have to be continuously measured. At Belle II, we have two kinds of the simulation, run-independent and run-dependent, where in the second one the time dependence of the beam-related quantities is taken into account.

[†]By "beam momentum" we always understand momentum of a single particle in the beam.

Figure 4: Clone rate of tracks (a) as a function of track transverse momentum and the tracking efficiency (b) as a function of the dip angle λ of the matched MC particle. On top of that, the track density distribution with an arbitrary normalization is overlaid. The results using default tracking workflow (Fig. 2) are represented by orange lines. The blue lines indicate an alternative scenario where VXDTF2 is replaced by SVDHough algorithm [6].

3.2 Beam spot

By beam spot (also known as luminous region) we understand the spatial probability density of the primary interactions. This probability density can be approximated by 3D Gaussian function

$$p(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{\det^{\frac{1}{2}}(2\pi\mathbf{V})} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_{\text{IP}})^T \mathbf{V}^{-1}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_{\text{IP}})\right), \quad (4)$$

which is characterised by 9 parameters. It is the position of the beam spot center \mathbf{x}_{IP} (3 parameters) and the covariance matrix \mathbf{V} which is 3×3 symmetric matrix (6 parameters) describing beam spot sizes and orientation. Notice that the surface of equal probability density is an ellipsoid, \mathbf{x}_{IP} is its center, eigenvectors of \mathbf{V} are the principal axes of the ellipsoid and eigenvalues are proportional to the sizes measured in the direction of the respective eigenvectors. At Belle II the shape of this ellipsoid has typical "eigen" sizes $\sigma'_y = 0.1 \mu\text{m}$, $\sigma'_x = 13 \mu\text{m}$, $\sigma'_z = 320 \mu\text{m}$.

At Belle II both \mathbf{x}_{IP} and \mathbf{V} are continuously measured using $e^+e^- \rightarrow \mu^+\mu^-$ which is a process with clean topology and high event rate. In the past, the beam spot was determined using vertices reconstructed from the two muon tracks. However, this approach highly suffers from the tracking resolution, so that an algorithm was developed which directly takes track parameters as the input. This algorithm is inspired by the approach used at BaBar [8] or CMS collaboration [11].

The general idea is that for every track in the $e^+e^- \rightarrow \mu^+\mu^-$ event holds

$$\begin{aligned} d_0^{(1)} &= x_{\text{IP}} \sin \phi_0^{(1)} - y_{\text{IP}} \cos \phi_0^{(1)} + r^{(1)}, \\ d_0^{(2)} &= x_{\text{IP}} \sin \phi_0^{(2)} - y_{\text{IP}} \cos \phi_0^{(2)} + r^{(2)}, \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where $d_0^{(1,2)}$ and $\phi_0^{(1,2)}$ are the standard track parameters for the μ^+ and μ^- defined in [5] and $x_{\text{IP}}, y_{\text{IP}}$ are the coordinates of the actual interaction point. The $r^{(1,2)}$ denotes random factors related to the tracking resolution which have spread about $15 \mu\text{m}$, but are zero on average.

When many events are considered, the equations (5) written for every event can be understood as overdetermined system of the linear equations for variables $x_{\text{IP}}, y_{\text{IP}}$. In this way, the transverse coordinates of the beam spot center are measured. Knowing the $x_{\text{IP}}, y_{\text{IP}}$, the equations (5) can be transformed to the coordinate system with origin at $(x_{\text{IP}}, y_{\text{IP}})$. Then the product of the right-hand sides of (5) can be expressed as

$$d_0^{\prime(1)} d_0^{\prime(2)} = \sigma_x^2 \sin \phi_0^{(1)} \sin \phi_0^{(2)} + \sigma_y^2 \cos \phi_0^{(1)} \cos \phi_0^{(2)} - C_{xy} \sin(\phi_0^{(1)} + \phi_0^{(2)}) + R, \quad (6)$$

where $d_0^{\prime(1,2)}$ are $d_0^{(1,2)}$ in the transformed system, σ_x, σ_y are the beam spot sizes and C_{xy} is the covariance which is non-zero if the beam spot is rotated. When many events are considered, the equation (6) is understood as overdetermined system of linear equations for σ_x^2, σ_y^2 and C_{xy} . Notice that terms including r cancel on average if terms like $\langle x_{\text{IP}} r^{(1)} \rangle$ or $\langle r^{(1)} r^{(2)} \rangle$ are zero when averaging over many events. This condition appears to be well satisfied, therefore most of the resolution effects are canceled in this way and the beam spot sizes can be measured with high precision. More formally, this condition means that the statistical distribution of the overall residuum R has zero mean and shape of this distribution does not depend on the phase space region which is defined by $\phi_0^{(1)}$ and $\phi_0^{(2)}$ variables.

We sketched only the general idea of the algorithm, in reality all 9 beam spot parameters are measured, i.e. also the beam spot tilts w.r.t. the z -axis, z_{IP} and σ_z . At Belle II the beam spot position is measured in ~ 30 min intervals and the remaining parameters in intervals lasting about 2 hours. Some of the measured values for data from April 2022 can be seen in Fig. 5. The xz angle of the beam spot is related to the non-zero crossing angle of the beams and to the fact that x -sizes of the beams are not equal.

3.3 Beam momenta

By design the beams do not collide head-on, but with a horizontal crossing angle of 83 mrad, where nominally both beams share half of this angle. Since the actual angles can differ from the design values, both the energies and the angles of the beams are measured, that means 3+3 parameters.

Figure 5: The time dependence of the x -coordinate of the beam spot center, horizontal beam spot size and the beam spot tilt in the xz plane. The statistical uncertainties of the x_{IP} are depicted as the light blue band, but are too small to be visible. The uncertainties of the remaining variables are not plotted as they are not stored in the Belle II Conditions Database [12].

The momenta of the beams are not measured directly, instead they are derived from the boost vector β , CM energy of the collisions E_{CMS} and the angles $\theta_{\{x,y\}z}^{\text{CMS}}$ of the collision axis in the CM system. This quantities are defined as:

$$\beta = \frac{1}{E^{\text{H}} + E^{\text{L}}}(\mathbf{p}^{\text{H}} + \mathbf{p}^{\text{L}}), \quad E_{\text{CMS}} = \sqrt{(E^{\text{H}} + E^{\text{L}})^2 - (\mathbf{p}^{\text{H}} + \mathbf{p}^{\text{L}})^2}, \quad \theta_{\{x,y\}z}^{\text{CMS}} = \text{Angle}_{\{x,y\}z}[\text{Boost}_{-\beta}(p^{\text{H}})], \quad (7)$$

where $p^{\text{H}} = (E^{\text{H}}, \mathbf{p}^{\text{H}})$ and $p^{\text{L}} = (E^{\text{L}}, \mathbf{p}^{\text{L}})$ are the 4-momenta of the colliding electron and positron, respectively. The "Boost" operator performs boost of the 4-vector and operator "Angle $_{xz}$ " returns angle of 4-vector in xz plane, i.e. $\text{atan } p_x/p_z$ for vector p , and similarly for "Angle $_{yz}$ ". The quantities β , E_{CMS} and $\theta_{\{x,y\}z}^{\text{CMS}}$ are independent and represent 6 degrees of freedom, so that they fully constrain momenta of the beams. In the following, the procedure how to measure these quantities is briefly described.

3.3.1 Boost vector

The boost vector β can be interpreted as the velocity of the CM reference frame, or the $\Upsilon(4S)$ resonance if it is produced. Similarly as the beam spot, the boost vector is also measured using $e^+e^- \rightarrow \mu^+\mu^-$ events, where it is equal to the velocity of the $\mu^+\mu^-$ system. As the angles of the tracks are measured with much better resolution than curvatures, we use an approach inspired by the procedure in [8]. For every event a direction vector perpendicular to the $\mu^+\mu^-$ plane is calculated and parametrized by its azimuthal and polar angles ϕ and λ . Consequently, for every event holds:

$$b_x \cos \phi + b_y \sin \phi = -\tan \lambda, \quad (8)$$

where $\mathbf{b} = (b_x, b_y, 1)$ is the vector pointing in the direction of the boost vector. The parameters b_x and b_y are determined from the linear regression, similarly as in case of the beam spot position (5).

The magnitude of β is measured from the average rapidity $(y'_{\mu^+} + y'_{\mu^-})/2$, where both rapidities are evaluated w.r.t. the boost direction known from the previous step. As the muons are highly relativistic, rapidity and pseudo-rapidity are almost equal, therefore, the algorithm is nearly independent on the track curvatures (momenta of the muons). The resolution of the boost vector magnitude is very good and even allows to determine the boost vector spread caused by the energy spread of the particles in the beams.

At Belle II the boost vector is measured in time intervals of ~ 8 hours and the time dependence of the measured values can be seen in Fig. 6. The nominal value of the boost vector magnitude is $|\beta| = 276.11 \times 10^{-3}$ and 150.83 mrad for boost vector angle in the xz plane. The value of the yz angle is designed to be zero.

Figure 6: The time dependence of the magnitude and xz and yz angles of the boost vector. The light blue band represents statistical uncertainties.

3.3.2 Centre-of-mass energy of the collisions

We use 2 ways to measure the CM energy of the collisions.

The first approach is based on the hadronic B decays $B \rightarrow D^{(*)}\pi$, where both charged and neutral B mesons are considered. As the B mesons are nearly at rest in the CM system, the momentum of the B in the CMS, p_B^* , is highly sensitive to the E_{CMS} . The CM energy is then obtained from the fit to the $E_B^* = \sqrt{m_B^2 + (p_B^*)^2}$ which is peaking at $E_{\text{CMS}}/2$. Good E_B^* resolution even allows to measure the E_{CMS} spread, similarly as for the boost vector magnitude. The disadvantage of this method is low rate of the events and bias from the E_{CMS} dependence of the $e^+e^- \rightarrow \Upsilon(4S)$ resonance cross section which has to be taken into account.

Alternatively, we also measure E_{CMS} using invariant mass of the $\mu\mu$ system in $e^+e^- \rightarrow \mu^+\mu^-$ events, where the event rate is much higher. Unfortunately, the tracking resolution effects lead to a peak width of ~ 40 MeV which is much more than the E_{CMS} spread of ~ 5 MeV stemming from the energy spread of the beams. Also the systematic uncertainty of the muon momentum scale can affect the peak position by several MeV whereas for the first method the momentum scale uncertainty is much lower as the B meson decay products have much smaller momenta. The $\mu\mu$ method is still useful to track short time variations of E_{CMS} while the overall normalization and the E_{CMS} spread are fixed from the hadronic B decays. We also use $\mu\mu$ method for special runs not targeting $\Upsilon(4S)$ resonance, i.e. for runs with energy below $B\bar{B}$ production threshold or for runs at higher energies, up to 10810 MeV.

The historical time dependence of the E_{CMS} measured at Belle II is shown in Fig. 7. It can be seen,

Figure 7: The time dependence of the centre-of-mass energy of the collisions as measured by the Belle II. The nominal energy corresponding to the $\Upsilon(4S)$ mass is depicted as a green line. Only runs with nominal energy corresponding to $\Upsilon(4S)$ resonance are plotted.

that for a significant time period the detector operated slightly below the resonance. That was corrected in 2021-11-25, when SuperKEKB performed new energy scan to adjust the beam energies. From that time the energy slightly decreased again. Larger deviations from the nominal energy lead to lower $B\bar{B}$ event rate and should be avoided.

3.3.3 Collisions axis in the CMS and the beam momenta

The boost vector β allows to transform to the CMS. In this system, obtained by the Lorentz boost, the colliding particles have momenta of equal size and opposite orientation. However, in general, the collision axis is not aligned with the z' axis of the system. Therefore, to transform to the classical CMS, where particles collide in the z' direction, an extra rotation has to be performed by angles $\theta_{\{x,y\}z}^{\text{CMS}}$ defined in (7).

Experimentally, these angles can be measured in $e^+e^- \rightarrow \mu^+\mu^-e^+e^-$ events, where invariant mass of the $\mu^+\mu^-$ pair is required to be below 2 GeV. The flight direction of the $\mu^+\mu^-$ pair measured in the CMS obtained by the Lorentz boost directly corresponds to the $\theta_{\{x,y\}z}^{\text{CMS}}$ angles. This process has a high event rate, so the time intervals of ~ 8 hours can be utilized. Measured values of θ_{xz}^{CMS} and θ_{yz}^{CMS} are typically about 5.3 mrad and -0.2 mrad and slightly differ from the nominal values 5.8 mrad and 0 mrad.

From β , E_{CMS} and $\theta_{\{x,y\}z}^{\text{CMS}}$ the beam momentum vectors can be derived by inverting (7), see Fig. 8. These

Figure 8: The time dependence of the electron (HER) and positron (LER) beam angles in the xz and yz plane. In addition, the positron beam energy is plotted on the right plot.

momenta are important, for example, for the run-dependent Monte Carlo production, where they are used as an input. Since β and $\theta_{\{x,y\}z}^{\text{CMS}}$ differ from the nominal values also the measured angles slightly differ from the designed values which are 41.5 mrad in the xz plane and 0 mrad in the yz plane. There are differences also the beam energies, especially energy of the positron beam is slightly lower w.r.t. the nominal one as shown in Fig. 8.

It is worth to mention that the beam momentum vectors form a plane and this plane by design should coincide with $x'z'$ plane of the beam spot, otherwise the crossing of the beams is not optimal and there is a luminosity loss. From our preliminary studies we see a consistence between these two planes within statistical uncertainties.

4 Conclusions

The Belle II tracking shows excellent performance and with increasing integrated luminosity there are more and more physics results, including the world-leading measurements of the lifetimes of the charmed hadrons. The tracking software is being continuously developed, one of the latest improvements is the implementation SVDHough algorithm for the standalone track finding in SVD which is planned to replace VXDTF2 algorithm. To fully benefit from the clear topology of the e^+e^- collisions, the beam-related variables must

be continuously monitored. Quantities like beam spot, boost vector and CM collision energy are used for the data analysis, for the Monte Carlo production as well as for monitoring of the accelerator performance.

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